

**THE EXPERIENCE OF STUDENT SOJOURNERS AND
THEIR HYBRID IDENTITY DEVELOPMENT WHILE
STUDYING ABROAD: THE CASE OF ALGERIAN PhD
STUDENTS IN THE UK**

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Declaration

I hereby declare that this study is established on my original work except for the acknowledged quotations and citations. I also confirm that it does not contain any material that has been previously submitted for the reward of any other academic degree or diploma at the University of West of Scotland or any other institution.

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Abstract

This qualitative study investigates Algerian PhD student sojourners' perceptions of the impact of studying abroad on their identities. There is a lack of research on Algerian students' adjustment in English speaking countries, which necessitates more attention because of the increasing number of Algerians studying abroad. In addition, pursuing a doctoral programme can be considered as a complex process; however, undertaking it in a foreign country makes the adjustment to the new social and academic systems even more difficult. This study aims at providing a deeper understanding of Algerian PhD students' challenges, learning experiences and adjustment strategies during their sojourn using Bronfenbrenner's bioecological theory for explaining the different processes that the individuals' cognitive development goes through when interacting with new individuals, places and symbols. Data were collected using a questionnaire open-ended question and photo-elicitation interview as two complementary methods. The questionnaire was distributed on 120 Algerian PhD students across several universities in the UK, whereas ten Algerian PhD students at a Scottish university were recruited as interviewees. All in all, the experiences of the Algerian PhD student sojourners involved a short loss of the social networks and support sources, which resulted in emotional distress. Despite the challenges rooted within the social, academic and cultural contexts of study abroad, Algerian PhD students managed to cope with the transformation by engaging in complex and positive social interactions. Findings also suggest that the positive interactions with supervisors, staff and peers within the university, made the participants feel as equal and valued members of the academic community in the UK. Interestingly, female participants reported that they found new freedom and autonomy in the UK in contrast to the traditional familial and social contexts in Algeria. Developing a strong academic identity as doctoral students gave them more power to address the raised issue of gender inequality and traditional social roles in Algerian societies. Finally, findings showed that positive interaction people in different contexts can promote awareness of self and others. Based on these findings, I can challenge the structure of Bronfenbrenner's bioecological model conception of culture as a separate context situated in the macro system of individuals, instead, culture in the context of this study was introduced as an integral part that can directly influence the proximal processes and the behaviours of the group under study.

Keywords: *Algerian doctoral student; negotiating identity; adjustment strategies; photo-elicitation; proximal processes; bioecological model.*

Table of contents

Declaration	1
Acknowledgment	2
Abstract	3
Table of contents.....	4
List of tables	10
List of figures	11
Chapter 1: Introduction.....	12
1.1 Rationale of the study	14
1.2 Identity negotiation and development during sojourn.....	15
1.3 Research questions.....	16
1.4 Purpose and objectives of the study.....	17
1.5 Phases of the study.....	18
Chapter 2: The context of Algeria	20
2.1 Demography of Algeria.....	20
2.2 Education in Algeria.....	21
2.2.1 <i>The school system in Algeria.....</i>	<i>22</i>
2.2.2 <i>Status of Arabisation in Algeria.....</i>	<i>23</i>
2.2.3 <i>The failure of Arabisation in Algeria</i>	<i>25</i>
2.2.4 <i>Issues of education in Algeria.....</i>	<i>26</i>
2.3 Higher education in Algeria.....	27

2.3.1 <i>Examples of Internationalisation of higher education in the developing countries</i>	29
2.3.2 <i>Government Sponsorship and Algerian students in the UK</i>	32
2.4 Summary of the chapter	34

Chapter 3: Mobility, cultural transition, acculturation and adjustment of international doctoral students36

Introduction	36
Overview	37
3. 1 Understanding culture	39
3. 1.1 Features and characteristics of Culture	41
3. 1.2 Hall's classification of culture	41
3.3.2.1 <i>High contexts vs low contexts</i>	42
3.3.2.2 <i>Polychronic versus monochronic time orientation</i>	42
3. 1.3 Hofstede's cultural dimensions	44
3. 1.3.1 <i>Power distance</i>	45
3. 1.3.2 <i>Individualism versus collectivism</i>	45
3. 1.3.3 <i>Masculinity versus Femininity</i>	46
3. 1.3.4 <i>Uncertainty avoidance</i>	46
3. 1.3.5 <i>Long-term orientation versus short-term orientation</i>	46
3. 1.3.6 <i>Arguments supporting Hofstede</i>	47
3. 1.3.7 <i>Arguments against Hofstede</i>	47
3. 2 Theories of identity	50
3.2.1 <i>Identity construction process</i>	54
3.2.2 <i>Social identity theory</i>	56
3.2.3 <i>Cultural identity</i>	58

3.2.4 Academic identity.....	66
3.2.5 Identity and intercultural communication.....	68
3.3 Mobility, acculturation and adjustment.....	76
3.3.1 Internationalisation of higher education and student mobility.....	76
3.3.2 Students' intercultural experiences.....	79
3.3.3 Acculturation process of international students.....	81
3.3.4 Coping with stress and adjustment.....	84
3.3.5 Cognitive adjustment.....	84
3.3.6 Academic adjustment of international students.....	85
3.3.7 Identity and adjustment.....	86
3.4 Overview of the bioecological theory of human development.....	87
3.4.1 Main concepts of the bioecological theory.....	87
3.4.2 Strengths and weaknesses.....	90
Conclusion.....	92

Chapter 4: Methodology.....93

Introduction.....	93
4.1 Methodological framework.....	93
4.1.1 Ethical guidelines for the interview.....	94
4.1.2 The researcher's role.....	95
4.1.3 Pilot study.....	96
4.1.4 Data transcription.....	98
4.1.5 Reliability and validity in qualitative research.....	99
4.2 Research design.....	101
4.3 Maxwell's interactive model of research design.....	103

4.4 Research objectives (goals).....	105
4.5 Theoretical perspective.....	107
4.5.1 Positivism	108
4.5.2 Interpretivism	108
4. 6 Conceptual framework	109
4. 7 Research questions.....	111
4. 8 Research methodology	112
4. 8.1 Sampling.....	113
4. 8.2 Limitations.....	114
4. 9 Research methods	114
4. 10 Questionnaires and surveys.....	118
4. 11 Photo-elicitation interviews (PEI)	120
4. 11.1 The process of photo-elicitation interview (PEI).....	121
4.11.2 Advantages	124
4.11.3 Ethical issues with visual research.....	125
4.11.4 Anonymity and confidentiality.....	126
4.12 Analysis	127
4.12.1 Thematic analysis	127
4.12.2 Thematic analysis process.....	129
4.12.3 Advantages of thematic analysis.....	131
4.12.4 Disadvantages of thematic analysis	132
4.12.5 Trustworthiness.....	132
4.12.6 Reflexivity.....	133
Conclusion.....	134

Chapter 5: Findings135

Introduction	135
5.1 Emerging themes from the open-ended question and the photo elicitation interviews (PEI).....	135
5.1.1 <i>Feeling frustrated</i>	137
5.1.1.1 <i>Feeling like a stranger</i>	139
5.1.1.2 <i>These are my best buddies</i>	142
5.1.2 <i>Becoming a better version of myself</i>	145
5.1.2.1 <i>Feeling more open</i>	148
5.1.2.2 <i>Religion and identity negotiation</i>	149
5.1.2.3 <i>Feeling more comfortable (PEI)</i>	151
5.1.2.4 <i>Feeling powerful and autonomous</i>	152
5.1.3 <i>My life as an academic</i>	154
5.1.3.1 <i>The PhD life is very hard for me</i>	155
5.1.3.2 <i>Engaging in academic activities</i>	156
5.1.3.3 <i>My relationship with supervisors, staff and other academics</i>	157
Conclusion.....	159

Chapter 6: Discussion160

Introduction	160
6.1 Considerations.....	160
6.2 Question one: What are the different adjustment strategies used by Algerian PhD student sojourners to cope with the experience abroad?	161
6.2.1 <i>Academic adjustment</i>	161
6.2.2 <i>Sociocultural adjustment</i>	162

6.3 Question two: What aspects of the Algerian PhD student sojourners' identity are affected during the experience abroad and in what way?	165
6.3.1 <i>Personal identity</i>	165
6.3.2 <i>Academic identity</i>	166
6.3.3 <i>Culture and religious identity</i>	167
6.4 Implications for host universities	168
6.5 Implications for Algerian international students	169
6.6 Limitations of the study	169
6.6.1 <i>Researcher bias</i>	169
6.6.2 <i>Time restriction</i>	170
6.6.3 <i>Sampling</i>	170
6.6.4 <i>English language</i>	170
6.7 Future research directions	170
6.8 Conclusion	171
6.9 Reflections as a researcher	174
List of references	177
Appendices	247

List of tables

Table 1: Monochronic and Polychronic Cultures	43
Table 2: Comparison of long term and short-term orientations	47
Table 3: The process of thematic analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2006).....	129

List of figures

Figure 1: Levels of human mental development (Hofstede, 1994).....	44
Figure 2: Acculturation process and context: framework for studying immigrants and sojourners (Ward and Geeraert, 2016).....	83
Figure 3: Elements of research design (Crotty, 1998)	92
Figure 4: An interactive model of research design (Maxwell, 2005).....	95

Chapter 1: Introduction

Travelling, studying, working or living abroad are signs of a developing openness towards a more international future of the world (Tomlinson, 2012). There is a growing interest in the academic research literature exploring cross-cultural communication (Gudykunst, 2003; Thomas and Peterson, 2017). In addition to the permanent migrant populations living abroad, the numbers of sojourners such as multinational employees, students and refugees have increased in the last decades (González et al., 2010; Beine et al., 2014).

The process of leaving one's home country to pursue work or studies necessitates separation from what is familiar such as people, support systems and cultural aspects. It also calls for interaction with different people from a different culture using a different language (Berry and Sam, 2006). This shift of places and cultural systems may bring positive possibilities and negative outcomes (Epprecht, 2004; Birman and Taylor-Ritzler, 2007 Presley et al., 2010; Kim et al., 2011; Li and Guo, 2018).

Algerian students, the focus of my study, represent a population that has not been researched before in terms of study abroad in an English-speaking country, and identity development through living and studying abroad. Identity development in the context of this study focuses on how individuals construct meaning from their life experiences. The concept of identity development relates to the development of people's consciousness and the meaning making mechanisms that "are not simply replaced as they grow, but incorporated into more complex systems of mind" (Kegan, 1994, p.9). In this research, I focus on the experiences of the Algerian PhD students' experiences in the UK and their perceptions about identity development/negotiation during their time abroad. Moreover, this research draws attention to:

- (1) The benefits of being a student abroad (with regard to personal and cultural experiences),
- (2) Problems and issues faced by the sojourners,
- (3) The adjustment strategies used to deal with the differences between host and home cultural structures.

Using thematic analysis, as illustrated in Chapter 4, I examined the previously mentioned areas with reference to Bronfenbrenner's ecological framework. As a part of a scheme organised by

the Algerian government in 2014 to fund a group of 500 students to study for a PhD in the UK. The Algerian government granted PhD scholarships to different UK universities in an attempt to develop capacities in English across Algerian universities and to expand international partnership. Students were selected to take part in this plan after completing both BA and Master's Degrees in English. The three students on top of their classes in Algerian universities were selected to take part in a national exam, which include English literature and French. All the selected students were from either the School of linguistics or the school of English literature in the English departments. Some of the successful applicants started immediately their PhD application process, while others went for pre-sessional courses that lasted 4 months in one university in the UK. The students had the freedom to choose the establishment, contact potential supervisors and apply for enrolment and study Visa.

This thesis explores the experiences of Algerian PhD students from the first two cohorts and their impact on their identity development. I think that this research is important for pushing the boundaries of knowledge about the development of identity of the Algerian doctoral students during their stay in the UK and in giving a general idea about the adjustment strategies used to cope with the cultural social and academic differences.

The UK was not previously a popular destination for Algerians to pursue their higher education studies. Most of the students go to France, or any other French-speaking country since their mastery of the French language can help them doing so. The English language in Algeria was and is still taught at the secondary school (11-12 years old) with very basic and traditional methods of teaching (Naima, 2017). This may be the reason why Algerian students do not think of travelling to the UK or English-speaking countries to continue their studies. Another reason may be related to the economy of the country. For instance, the Algerian currency is very low in comparison to the currency of the UK pound, and most Algerians have a low income that does not allow them to study abroad. However, in 2015, the Algerian Ministry of Higher Education made a step forward to encourage the Algerian-UK sojourn by providing 500 funding packages to the interested Algerian students, who had successfully completed their master's degree and passed a national exam of selection. Many of the Algerian PhD student sojourners in the UK receive financial support from the government, which is an important variable to acknowledge in regard to financial problems generally experienced by other international students during their sojourn (Altbach and Knight, 2007).

People who are leaving their original country for work or for study may experience some changes at the level of their identity, culture and interaction competences, which makes it an interesting phenomenon for studying to provide more understanding on how and why these changes take place. Young adults and students usually travel to the UK to improve their English language competence, which is now a key element within the global economy (Fairclough, 2007; Grey, 2017; Pennycook, 2017). Likewise, international students may gain qualifications and learn skills that can increase their employability rates (Crossman and Clarke, 2009; DiPietro, 2015).

Motivations for travelling abroad can be different for students in comparison to immigrants (Altbach and knight, 2007; Chen and Chen, 2015). For instance, immigrants may travel for economic reasons such as work, or political reasons including war refuge. In contrast, student sojourners have a short term stay in the host country with a specific rationale in mind. Moreover, student sojourners' understanding of themselves their cultural membership are often transformed during their time spent abroad (Ward, 2001; Zhou et al., 2008; Gu, 2015; Jackson, 2015).

1.1 Rationale of the study

Literature about student sojourners advocates that the different experiences lived by students abroad may affect their self-concept in terms of personal and social identities (Crawshaw et al., 2001; King and Ruiz, 2003; Sigalas, 2010). Facing new situations in the new context requires them to develop new strategies (William, 2005; Gu and Schweisfurth, 2010). They can face many issues that can be caused by the difference between their home culture and the culture of the host country (Ward et al., 2005; Cullingford, 2017). Students may struggle within the new culture because their original systems of beliefs and values do not make sense within the new cultural context (Ward et al., 2005; Furham, 2012; Gunn, 2017). They may experience a list of psychological adjustments that may not be noticeable or expected before the sojourn. Although the number of Algerian PhD students in the UK is tiny in comparison to the total percentage of the student sojourners' body, their presence is expected to increase in the future so investigating their experiences of adjustment and identity development can be appropriate at this time. Usually, research focusing on study abroad students' experiences, including this study, try to explore the different processes associated with acculturation and adjustment to have a deeper understanding of the subjective sojourn experiences.

Most of the studies on study abroad experiences appear not to consider the wider psycho-social contexts of international students (Khawaja and Stallman, 2011). For instance, previous research has been generally quantitative in nature, comprising large scale inquiries producing statistical data without considering deeper individual analysis (Moore and Popadiuk, 2011). In fact, most of the studies are prevalent in places such as the United Kingdom, the United States of America, Canada and Australia, mostly investigating Chinese, Mexican student communities, using quantitative methods (Ward and Kennedy, 1999; Yeh and Inose, 2003; Ward et al., 2005), and no previous research has been done on Algerian students studying in the UK. More research about Algerian student sojourners and students from countries in the north of Africa who have similar cultures may expand the discussion on the development of identity while studying abroad and adjustment strategies.

In this study, I chose a qualitative research methodology using a deductive thematic analysis, taking into consideration the gap in the literature, the previous methods, the theoretical framework and the cultural features of the sample population. This is explained in more details in Chapter 4 about methodology. My purpose was to answer the research questions by identifying sequences of meaning from the data about the perceptions of the Algerian PhD participants on the effect of studying abroad on their identity development. Thematic analysis can set the grounds for identifying and classifying the findings, which are connected to the existing literature about the main theoretical concepts being investigated (intercultural communication, identity development, sojourning). Studies that use different methodological perspectives, like this one, may have practical advantages. For example, findings can be used in the future to inform and prepare students, who share similar cultural backgrounds, to the experiences, academic difficulties and cultural differences expected when pursuing their studies abroad. Moreover, some findings can be used to provide a deeper understanding of the experiences shared among international PhD students. Findings from this work may also contribute to the knowledge about hybrid identity development systems and adjustment strategies, with a specific focus on the Algerian population and people with similar cultures.

1.2 Identity negotiation and development during sojourn

Throughout this research, I adopted Bronfenbrenner's model of bioecological systems of human development, which basically deals with perceptions of people of the environments where they live and interact. This work is essential to my study since it focuses on the influences

of the environment (culture) on the individual's cognitive development. During any sojourn, people's perceptions about their own culture and identity, and the host cultures can change through interaction with the new environment, hence affecting their identity negotiation/development processes and transforming their understanding of self and others. Bronfenbrenner's model may help to understand the identity development process in this research and will be further explored in Chapter 3.

The bioecological theory is used as a framework in this research since it covers the multiple variables in this study providing more legitimacy and coherence to the findings. Extracting systems of identity development from qualitative data can be a hard task, but, using Bronfenbrenner's multi-systems theory and keeping it in mind throughout the research, would provide more validity and reliability for the findings.

One of the major goals that student sojourners focus on is to successfully complete their degree, but in doing so, they need to navigate successfully within the new academic and social contexts. Adjustment to these new contexts can be challenging sometimes and may be affected by the students' country of origin, race and ethnicity, language skills and belonging to a collective or an individualistic culture (Wu et al., 2015; Baba and Hosoda, 2014; Wang and Hannes, 2014). As Jones and Abes (2013) explained that the study of identity is like an investigation of the stories of one's life when developing a sense of self shaped by the external world. Using Bronfenbrenner's bioecological theory, supported by theories such as dimensions of culture (Hofstede, 1994), processes on identity formation (Tajfel and Turner, 1985), and adjustment process (Ward et al., 2001) can be noted.

1.3 Research questions

This research aims to explore the experience of Algerian PhD student sojourners in relation to their identity development and adjustment strategies. Investigating the data relate to the sojourn experience of the Algerian PhD students, the following research questions were used and answered.

- What are the different adjustment strategies used by Algerian PhD student sojourners to cope with the experience abroad?

- What aspects of the Algerian PhD student sojourners' identity are affected during the experience abroad and in what way?

These research questions are at the core of this study, their importance is mostly evident in organising the ideas generated from the collected data, conforming to the methodological procedures discussed in later Chapter 4. Excerpts from questionnaires and interviews are presented in the findings Chapter 5, while answers to these questions are in the Discussion Chapter.

1.4 Purpose and objectives of the study

Putting in mind the research questions, theoretical framework and thematic analysis, the aim of this study was to explore the experiences of Algerian PhD student sojourners in the UK and their subjective perceptions on identity development during their journey. In exploring identity development during the sojourn and acculturation experiences of Algerian PhD students, my focus was on addressing the students' negative and positive experiences that accompany studying overseas. Findings from this research strongly suggest that, according to Bronfenbrenner's (ppct) model of development, Algerian doctoral students have suffered from emotional distress due to the sudden changes in social and academic environments.

Findings also suggest that Algerian PhD students who prefer engaging in complex and positive social interactions reported positive development of cultural awareness, openness and overall satisfaction of their experience in the UK. Moreover, Addressing the adjustment issues in relation to the academic context, findings suggest that the type of support that the participants received from different proximal processes, including positive interactions with their supervisors and staff within the university, made them feel equal, appreciated, and valued members of academic community in the UK.

Interestingly, most of the female participants reported that they found more freedom and autonomy in the UK in contrast to the traditional familial and social contexts in Algeria. Developing a new academic identity as doctoral students gave them more power to stand against gender inequality and traditional social roles in Algerian societies.

These findings would be useful in training future Algerian PhD students to successfully adjusting to the new cultural, social and academic environments, and in increasing their cross-cultural empathy and global awareness.

1.5 Phases of the study

Chapter One contains an introduction to this research including the rationale of the study, some key terms and definitions related to the subject of identity and study abroad. I summarised the context of this study by stating the background and significance of this work, together with the fundamental theoretical concepts and frameworks and the allocated methodology selected to facilitate assessing identity development. I presented the participants in this research, Algerian PhD students in the UK. All the participants were current students, but at different stages of their PhD programmes. I hope to contribute to the literature in this field via utilising the shared experiences of the participants during their time abroad. I employed the research questions and the methodology to help in guiding the themes, which are aimed to explore the preceding concerns of adjustment strategies, acculturation and identity development during the sojourn.

Chapter Two discusses the context of acculturation in general by presenting a brief historical review of the development of Algeria and its education systems since its independence in 1962. To do so, some fundamental reasons such as globalisation of higher education, English language proficiency and the UK as a destination for studying were taken into account. Moreover, relationships between higher education, globalisation and identity were also considered.

Chapter Three contains a critical analysis of the literature about central elements in this research such as culture, identity formation and negotiation, sojourners' adjustment and acculturation processes. Links between these theories are explained in the conceptual framework to provide a comprehensive understanding of the Algerian PhD student sojourners' experiences.

In chapter Four, I reviewed the methodology and explained the use of thematic analysis in this study. For instance, I organised the ideas that frequently occurred in the data into themes and later connected them to the research questions. This process is confirmed to be beneficial, considering that it can organise and analyse the generated data; in addition, it allows exploring the prevailing perceptions and beliefs related to concepts like culture, identity and adjustment. Moreover, thematic analysis, as a qualitative method, is useful in exploring the attitudes of

groups who have not been previously investigated by providing a profound understanding of the views of student sojourners about their experiences. Knowing that thematic analysis was not a popular method among other studies about students' experiences abroad, I elucidated the theories supporting thematic analysis and accentuated the importance and the reliability of this methodology with regard to the aims of this research I illustrated the steps taken to design the procedures and questions of the photo-elicitation interviews to comply with the research ethics, by pointing out the procedures, concerns and precautions during the data collection phase. I also clarified the processes taken during data transcription, coding and interpretation.

Chapter Five presents the emerged themes and categories in the data from the questionnaires and photo-elicitation interviews of Algerian PhD student sojourners. Findings have been organised in a way that they answer the research questions and explaining the sojourn experiences affecting the Algerian PhD students' identity and adjustment processes.

Chapter Six demonstrates the main conclusions in relation to the research questions and the main theoretical models. It explains the relationship between the conceptual framework of this research and the findings by reviewing the theories and the frameworks used to assess the students' hybrid identity development during sojourn. It also discusses the limitations of this study, practical implications and suggestions for future research.

Chapter 2: The context of Algeria

2.1 Demography of Algeria

Algeria is situated in the north of Africa facing the Mediterranean Sea. It is the largest country in Africa with a surface of more than two million square kilometres. Amazigh people are its original inhabitants. Today, only twenty per cent of the population speak different dialects of Tamazight, whereas the rest of Algerians who are “Arabised Berbers” speak Arabic dialect (Tiliouine and Achoui, 2018). The Algerian constitution states that Arabic and Tamazight are the official languages, and Islam is the religion of the country since the clear majority of the population are Muslims. Statistics from the National Office of Statistics (2017) show that the Algerian population reached 41.2 million in the first trimester of 2017. Most of the population are considered to be very young since 80% are under 45 years.

The Algerian economy depends heavily on the gas and oil exportation revenues. Since 2015, the production of oil and gas has been declining besides their prices in international markets. Moreover, employment in Algeria can be considered as one of the major problems in the present days because unemployment rates are still high especially among university graduates (Souag and Assaad, 2018).

The Algerian society represents a collectivist culture where members value in-group relationships that are characterised by cooperation, dependency, and interconnectedness. Men usually manage families in Algeria. For instance, in the Algerian culture, the man’s/ husband’s role within the family is centred on being the family provider. On the other hand, the women’s/ wife’s role is limited to taking care of the house and children. Members of the same family are expected to support one another and maintain the family’ name and honour (Dwairy and Achoui, 2012). Young people are expected to appreciate and respect older people especially family members. However, because of factors such as globalisation and urbanisation in large cities, family values became more individualistic supporting values such as competition and independence, which may sometimes cause conflicts within collectivist societies and values (Tiliouine and Achoui, 2018).

In Algeria, the majority of the population are Muslims, which can be seen through the people’s value systems and lifestyles. For instance, Islamic teachings, practices, and values are apparent from the individuals’ daily practices such as prayers, weekly group prayers on Fridays, and

yearly practices such as Ramadan. It is easy to observe that religion and traditional values and practices have great importance in relation to the life of Algerian families.

In recent years, Algeria's efforts in making more access for women to health, empowerment and economic activity are noticeable but without a significant impact. For instance, in the recent Gender Development Index (GDI) report, Algeria was placed very low in 129/144, which reveals issues concerning equal opportunities to employment comparing both men and women. In the case of current Algeria, higher education is a tool for empowering females in a society that is still seen as traditional in many angles. Despite the high rates of female school attainments at all levels, there is still a clear imbalance of employment that favours men over women (Furceri, 2012).

2.2 Education in Algeria

The educational system in Algeria has its roots from the historical French colonial system and Arabisation policy, which was introduced as a reform. After independence in 1962, literacy rates were alarming; statistics show that less than 1/3 of Algerian Muslim youth were in primary schools, around 30% in the secondary schools and less than 10% were enrolled in tertiary education (Rose, 2015). Since independence, the education sector has been always a high priority for the Algerian governments, which consider it crucial for building the nation and developing the other sectors. The total expenditure on education from the Algerian state budget was almost 28% in the early 1990s and today education receives 1/5 of the gross domestic product (GDP) of the country.

All Algerian students are eligible for free education at all the levels as long as they successfully pass the previous phase. All the three phases, which take 12 years, are mandatory; however, the first two phases have a very high rate of attendance in comparison to secondary education, which knows a remarkable decrease in attendance. Usually, students' advancement from primary school to middle school and to the secondary school and then to higher education is controlled by exams at the end of each phase. Almost in all the stages of education, pedagogy is conventional, teacher centred and based on information recitation.

In the Algerian context, education ensures much but gives less, which can be seen in the statistics from 2006 that show a much higher rate of literacy (72%) for the entire population; however, employment rates are quite low (Tiliouine and Achoui, 2018). The clear majority of

higher education institutions in Algeria belong to the state sector as stated in the decree of 1976. Even though the regulations were modified in 2004 and 2008 to allow more private education, the number of private institutions is still not significant (The Human Capital Report, 2013).

2.2.1 The school system in Algeria

The Algerian school system comprises of three cycles, which were modified in the last decade to 5 years in primary school, 4 years in middle and 3 years in secondary school. Over the following years, this reform has shown many of the negative outcomes of the previous system concerning class size, high dropout rates that reached over 50 000 students and repetition rates that reached between 10% and 16%, lack of competent teachers and poor quality of teaching programmes.

In 2014, around 8.024,000 pupils enrolled for primary and secondary education with almost 43% in primary schools (World Bank, 2014). In 2009, there were 370,000 teachers assigned across 24,600 schools at all levels. The advancement from primary education to middle one is assessed by an exam in which many students fail the first time and repeat the whole year. In 2010, more than 35% of pupils failed to transit to middle school due to the huge number of pupils. At the end of middle school cycle, pupils must undertake another exam, Brevet d'Enseignement Fondamentale (BEF), to progress to secondary school. The success rate in the (BEF) exam in 2010 was low as only less than two-thirds pupils managed to pass to the secondary education.

The first year of secondary education is a foundation year in which all the pupils study the same programmes. In the next two years of secondary education, pupils are being directed into one of the three main specialties, which are general education, scientific stream and technical education. By the end of the third year, students will undertake the baccalaureate exam in that specialty.

The reforms of the Algerian education system started in 2003, yet, according to the council of secondary school in Algiers (CLA) they were 'unsuccessful', or 'partly implemented' as described by SNAPEST, the official counterpart of CLA (Rose, 2015). They complained about the low level of most pupils in reading, writing and arithmetic. Their demands emphasised on reforming the curriculum, classes and schools into ones that encourage the students' self-expression and providing them with a 'universal knowledge' (Messekher and Miliani, 2017). It

is hard to make a comparison of the quality of education in the Algerian context since Algeria has not participated in TIMSS, PIRLS or PISA assessments.

2.2.2 Status of Arabisation in Algeria

After its independence on July 5th, 1962, the Algerian government decided in favour of the policy of Arabisation, which intended to establish Arabic as an official language. Currently, Algerian Arabic and Berber are dominant languages in Algeria, whereas standard Arabic is the official language and French is the second language, preserving an important position as the major academic language at university, especially in the scientific fields. English is considered as the second foreign language with a highly influential value. Unlike some countries in the Middle East, which did not face any significant problems in adapting Arabisation, north African countries, such as Algeria, Tunisia and Morocco, experienced a great deal of disorder that can be seen detected through their languages, cultures and identities.

During the French colonisation, many regions in Algeria used the Arabic language, which was associated with Islam, to distinguish themselves from French people (Grandguillaume, 2004). Throughout the colonial period, Arabic was taught, and furthermore, shared equal status with French in both Morocco and Tunisia. The Arabic language Algeria was mainly taught in religious schools, which created a strong link between the language and the religion of Islam (Mostari, 2005).

As from 1962, Algeria was a linguistically pluralistic country, but the Arabisation policy denied any existence of these languages and promoted the literary classical Arabic, which is considered as the dominant language of middle-east regions (Benrabah, 2007). One of the major amendments made in independent Algeria was to promote the Arabic language across the country via education. For the president and the government members in power, the most important step for Algeria to begin reconstructing itself was by uplifting the status of Arabic and Muslim identity. Their claim clearly excludes the existence of indigenous languages and cultures such as Kabyle, Shaoui and many others.

Arabisation of the Algerian education system, which was pursued from 1962 to 1975 is considered as a major landmark in independent Algerian, which formed one of the most prominent markers of Algerian identity. The Arabic language is considered as the national and official language while the French language was used temporarily. One of the appointed

ministers of education was Ahmed Taleb Ibrahimi; religious-conservative ideology was introduced to the Ministry of Education with a clear intention to spreading Arabisation and creating a “new Algeria” (Taleb Ibrahimi, 2006). On October 1962, the linguistic Arabisation started at the elementary school (Grandguillaume, 2004); Arabic was introduced ten hours per week in all schools. The first grade of primary school was totally arabised in 1964. As indicated by Benrabah (2007), during the period from 1962 to 1963, about 10,000 new teachers were recruited, but the number of students was beyond expectations. He adds that the Algerian government had compensated for the lack of Arabic language teachers by signing up 1,000 Egyptian and 1,000 Syrian teachers. In 1966, the number primary school teachers was around 13,000, of whom 3,500 (27%) foreigner, and only 1,500 of them were teachers and the other 2,000 were just instructors (Benrabah, 2004).

The foreign teachers lacked proper qualifications and, in addition to that, their accent represented a handicap. The majority of the immigrant teachers were members of the Muslim Brotherhood who taught the Arabic language through the religious medium, which helped in spreading their ideology (Saad, 1993; Daoudi, 2018). Most of them followed a conventional teaching approach, which makes use of memorisation and physical punishment (Grandguillaume, 2004). By 1974, the primary school was fully arabised with French being taught at the fourth grade. At the secondary level, one-third of the math and sciences sections were Arabised.

Until the 1970s the educational system structure consisted of the primary school, middle school, and the secondary school, lasting 5 years, 4 years and 3 years respectively (Benrabah, 1999). In 1976, the new reforms of the schooling system introduced the fundamental school, which was a fusion of the primary and middle school (9 years) with all the subjects taught in Arabic except the foreign languages (Saad, 1993). These last reforms were not sufficient to deal with the education problems in Algeria because of the Arabisation policy that had a considerable impulse during Boumediene’s presidency (1965-1978) and that was aligned with a dramatic decline in educational quality (Saad, 1993). In April 1977, Lachraf replaced Ibrahimi as the Minister of Primary and Secondary Education. He suspended the fundamental education plan, dismissed the proponents of monolingual Arabic in his ministry, reinstated teacher training in French and reinserted bilingualism at the primary school level with scientific subjects (Mathematics, Algebra and Biology) taught in French. Lachraf resigned a year later, in 1978,

after the president's Boumediene's death. The total Arabisation policy was restored by the next Minister of Education Kharroubi in 1979 (Benrabah, 2007).

In 1993, the introduction of a foreign language into the primary school level was delayed to the fourth grade. The same year, the Algerian government introduced English as the first foreign language in primary schools instead of French. The English language was first introduced to Grade 4 in some pilot primary schools then the program was stopped because most of the parents preferred French to English (Bellalem, 2014). The major changes that are taking place with the latest reform since 2002 are that the French language has to be taught starting from the second grade of primary school while the second English language would be taught in the sixth grade and subjects like Science and Mathematics would be taught using French terminology.

In sum, the Arabisation system which aimed at fostering a sense of Arab and Muslim identity into Algerian young generation was first introduced in the primary schools then it began to be introduced as the language of instruction at the secondary level. After independence, Different languages were used at different levels French was taught as the first foreign language, whereas English was considered the second foreign language. Many specialists argue that the inconsistency of language policy used in education is partially responsible for the collapse of education system in Algeria (Le Roux, 2017; Daoudi, 2018).

2.2.3 The failure of Arabisation in Algeria

The hasty enforcement of the Arabisation of the educational system in Algeria may be the main reason for its failure (Grandguillaume, 2004). In 1970, the Algerian Ministry of Education was divided into two separate ministries including a Ministry of Primary and Secondary Education and another ministry of Higher Education. This split within the educational system distorted the Arabisation policy since it went at an accelerated pace in the primary and secondary levels, when in fact it was held back in higher education levels. For instance, Arabisation was applied in most of the primary and secondary education, whereas the French language was dominant at higher levels of education (Rose, 2015).

From 1986, the decrease of the country's financial resources and the total Arabisation of the primary and secondary school, the educational system recorded a state of extreme decline (Grandguillaume, 2004). During that period, pupils in secondary school level of the Arabised education system did not have a full command of either Classical Arabic or French (Entellis,

1981; Taleb-Ibrahimi, 2006; Miliani, 2011). For instance, the curriculums of primary and secondary school were arabised, but the language of instruction changes to French at higher levels. Language inconsistency prevented most of the students from coping effectively with French-language instructions and impeded them from understanding course content (Entellis, 1981).

Lack of qualified teachers

By the year 1962, about 25000 teachers from all over Algeria left towards Europe, which led Algeria to approach other countries, such as Egypt and Syria. Grandguillaume (2004) reports that there were tutors, instructors and teachers and any holder of a French speaker certificate or the equivalent for Arabic speakers were hired as tutors at the primary school level. Individuals who had the certificate of intermediate education (Brevet de l'enseignement moyen) were employed as instructors. The students who were trained in the teacher-training college, in Algiers, were recruited as teachers. During the school year 1968/1969, the total number of primary school teachers were 36,255, but only 6,892 were trained to be actual teachers (Le Roux, 2017).

The rejection of the students' mother tongues

During the 1970s, UNESCO issued a report on the low standards of education in Algeria, which obliged the government to call for Arabisation delay (Taleb Ibrahimi, 2015). Teachers in Algeria were divided into Arabic speakers and French-Arabic speakers, but the bilingual system shrank, due to the policy of Arabisation applied by the local authorities. In addition, Benrabah (2007) argues that Arabisation pedagogy rejected all the other languages spoken in Algeria, Algerian Arabic and Tamazight. Therefore, students were forced to switch from their mother tongue to the Arabic used at school, which is the standard form of Arabic that is not used in any country.

2.2.4 Issues of education in Algeria

Although the Algerian government's efforts in promoting education may have been impressive, yet the educational system still suffers from frequent unsolved problems. First, there still high rates of failure of exams at the final years of middle school and high school and the. Second, there is still a high percentage of drop-outs that can be estimated to 500.000 pupils leaving

school every year without any qualifications. Third, grade retention is another problem since many pupils repeated at least one year. At the university level, some pupils sit for the baccalaureate two or three times in order to get the high marks, which allow them to choose the field they want. In addition to that, orientation problems at university level make the students repeat their first year as many as four times.

2.3 Higher education in Algeria

Article 53 of the Constitution of 1996 details three main characteristics of Higher education in Algeria. First, all Algerian students have a guaranteed right to education. Second, all Algerians have the right to free education. Finally, basic education is compulsory.

According to Benouar (2013), the Algerian higher education system constitutes of 91 institutions covering the 48 provinces all over the country. The network of higher education institutions comprises forty-seven universities, ten university centres and nineteen Higher Education national schools, five teachers training colleges, ten preparatory schools and two integrated preparatory classes. The number of students attending institutions of higher education reached more than two million students in 2013. Mami (2013) states that in the academic year 2004-2005, the Algerian Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research introduced the Bologna process (three-cycle degree system) in 2004. This system (Bachelor, Masters and Doctorate) is believed to be designed to promote European education, which makes it more competitive in the international market (Mami, 2013).

Higher education institutions are directly and exclusively dependent on the state. They are administrated by a rector or a director appointed by the ministry in charge. Each institution receives a budget assigned by the government, but they may also avail themselves of funds from public or private sources. Universities are autonomous in determining curricula according to their areas of specialisation and the needs of their socio-economic environment.

All universities are governed by the rectorate, which has the highest authority. At the second level comes three or four vice-rectorates. For instance, vice-rectorate for graduation, continuing education and degrees; vice-rectorate for postgraduate studies, university accreditation and scientific research; vice-rectorate for external relations, cooperation, activity management and coordination, communication and scientific events; vice-rectorate for development, strategy and careers guidance. At the third level, there is an administrative council and an academic

council, both of which are headed by the rector. Universities are divided into faculties that are subdivided into departments breached split by subject areas. As stated by the Minister of Higher Education and Scientific Research, Mohamed Mebarki, more than 1,300.000 students will join the academic institutions across the national territory, during the academic year 2014-2015 (Benrabah, 2007). Only holders of the Baccalaureate or an equivalent certificate can pursue higher education.

The academic year is organised into semesters. The average duration of a semester is 16 to 18 weeks. The license is ensured in 6 semesters in which 4 semesters are called the common core. The European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System (ECTS) is being implemented and a semester counts for 30 credits. By the end of the Master's degree, the total number of credits is thus 300. For instance, students accumulating credits for two semesters of the first year move automatically to the second year. Similarly, students who obtain a bachelor's degree with 180 credits are automatically admitted to the first Master year (M1). In case students fail to get all necessary credits, they subsequently need to complete the missing credits in order to pass from the first to the second year. To assess students' progress, a final examination takes place at the end of each semester. Students who fail may be permitted to retake one or more examinations.

Tertiary education in Algeria has been growing and developing fast for the last two decades. Algerian higher education system was highly influenced by the French system, which dominated the tertiary education since independence in 1962. In the year 2004, there have been several significant changes to the education system, including the implementation of Bologna process LMD, as an attempt to making Algerian higher education internationally comparable and more focused on outcome learning (Rose, 2015).

The number of students has increased rapidly from 2809 in 1962 to 423,000 in 1999 and it reached 1.6 million in 2017. The number of academics is around 52,000; however, only one-third of them has a PhD. As part of the reform to improve the quality of the higher education sector, the Algerian government has funded large scale post-graduate study abroad programmes with several foreign universities in different countries including the UK (Rose, 2015).

One of the biggest problems of Algerian higher education institutions is the failure to construct graduates with skills relevant to the local labour market (Rose, 2015). For instance, almost one-fifth of university graduates are unemployed, which is as twice as the unemployment national average (10%).

2.3.1 Examples of Internationalisation of higher education in the developing countries

Altbach and Knight (2007) define globalisation as the economic, political, and societal forces pushing 21st century higher education toward greater international involvement. Globalisation results can be seen in two main ways. First, English is widely used for scientific communication. Second, in the various uses of information technology (IT), namely: facilitating communication; storage efficiency, classification and distribution of knowledge and e-learning (Altbach and Knight, 2007). They believe that countries with well-developed education systems and institutions encourage more international academic mobility. Northern institutions and corporations own most knowledge, knowledge products and IT infrastructure. Consequently, initiatives and programmes are often coming from the north focused on the south. Currently, international higher education is seen as a commodity to be freely traded and higher education is seen as a private good, not a public responsibility (Altbach and Knight, 2006).

Internationalisation has become a wide-ranging term that covers different dimensions. It may include degree mobility, academic exchange, curriculum development and franchise and branch campuses. According to Altbach and Knight (2007), financial income could be a powerful stimulus for all internationalisation projects in the for-profit institutions and for some non-profit universities. For instance, some countries, like Qatar, Singapore and the United Arab Emirates promoted internationalisation by establishing local campuses of world-class foreign universities to attract local and foreign students. Other countries, which have a developed education system, like Australia, Canada and the United Kingdom, have altered visa and immigration policies to attract a larger number of full-fee-paying internationals (Altbach et al., 2009).

De Wit (2017) argues that the presence of international students is appealing to universities, governments and many other organisations that make the higher education corporate. A survey made by Knight (2006) notes that traditional non-profit universities also entered the international market. Their aim is not only financial, in the sense that they aim at improving research and knowledge resources and to expand intercultural understanding.

Altbach and Knight (2007) think that the initiatives of internationalisation worldwide have created a massive demand for obtaining access to international higher education.

The European authorities engaged in academic internationalisation for more than two decades, as part of moving towards political and economic union. Since 1987 over three million students

across 33 European countries contribute to this programme (De Wit, 2017). Altbach and Knight (2007) argue that the Bologna process has incorporated the European academic systems to guarantee equal academic qualifications throughout the EU. The Bologna Process and the European Union's Lisbon Strategy (2000) have increasingly become a driving reason for the internationalisation of higher education, which arranged to make Europe one of the most competitive knowledge sources in the world (Jones et al., 2015).

Like the developed countries, developing countries seek to attract foreign students to their universities to earn more income increase the quality education and interculturality and to gain prestige. For instance, India is one of the most significant host countries for international students from other developing countries. For example, Bhalla (2012) states that Indian higher education institutions receive more than 8,000 students from abroad and 95% of them are from developing countries. Likewise, China, Malaysia and the Philippines are developing strategies to attract more students and to export educational programs and institutions.

Related to this point, Altbach and Knight (2007) claim that developed countries have higher education universities and institutions that deliver the most attractive and appreciated services. For instance, a report made by The European Commission (2014) classifies more than 250 branch campuses with English speaking countries as the main providers of knowledge. A common phenomenon in developed countries is the mobility of students, programmes, and academic staff abroad.

For example, the Middle East area has known a rapid growth in the higher education sector. For instance, the American University was established in Egypt more than 80 years ago. In addition, in the last few years, the German University and the L'Université Française d'Égypte have been established, while the new British University is under development. In Israel, Poland is running a new project to establish a private medical institute. In this program, students will be taught for 3 years before moving to the Medical University in Gdansk where they will spend three years doing clinical training before returning to home for an internship. Saudi Arabia is attracting many institutions namely the University of Arizona and UNESCO, which are joining together to establish a private university. In addition, The Stevens Institute of Technology is cooperating with the Boeing Company and the French defence firm Thales to create Dar-Al-Faisal University. Moreover, Harvard University is arranging to construct a branch campus in the United Arab Emirates (Altbach and Knight, 2007).

In addition, Vietnam is an emerging centre of activity. Its engagement in active partnerships between local and foreign institutions is steadily increasing. For instance, the University of Hue in Vietnam recently developed a franchised and joint degree bachelor's program in tourism with the University of Hawaii. Furthermore, Hanoi University of Technology is currently offering bachelors and master's degrees with higher education institutions from Belgium, France, Germany, Singapore and the United States. Thailand is increasing its cross-border education activities by the effective engagement with several countries such as Australia, China, Egypt, German and the United Kingdom. For example, there are 13 Australian universities and nine U.K. universities operating in Thailand besides The Thai-German Graduate School of Engineering. Moreover, Swinburne University of Technology (Australia) has operated a branch campus since 1998, whereas Al-Azhar University from Egypt and Jinan University from China plan to open a branch campus there.

Moreover, Russia had recently some major economic reforms, which have important implications for the higher education sector. According to Altbach and Knight (2007), Russia is a hot spot of joint and double degree programmes, twinning, and franchise arrangements. For instance, The British Open University has 80 business-training centres across the country. In addition, the London School of Economics runs a double degree program with the Russian Higher School of Economics. Additionally, the Stockholm School of Economics from Sweden operates in St. Petersburg. The Russian-Indian Centre for Advanced Computer Research was recently established in Moscow and India plans to offer masters and PhD courses through this centre.

Furthermore, in 2000, Laureate Education purchased the Universidad Del Valle de Mexico; it plans to open a new branch in Guadalajara. Laureate also owns Universidad Inter-Americana, a private university with campuses in Costa Rica and Panama and part of three private universities in Chile. Bologna University, in Italy, is one of the few foreign institutions with a branch campus in Argentina.

Africa shows the fewest international and cross-border initiatives, with the partial exception of South Africa. The private Universiteit Nienrode or Netherlands' Business School, in partnership with the African Leadership Forum, recently established a branch campus in Nigeria. Kenya is home to two private non-profit universities. Pakistan's Aga Khan University opened a branch university campus in Kenya in 2002 that specialises in nursing education and Alliant

International University from the United States provides education in social sciences and the humanities.

The number of foreign programmes offered in South Africa has plummeted because of strict new government regulations and accreditation processes. Only a few foreign institutions have branch campuses, including Bond and Monash from Australia, De Montfort (United Kingdom) and the Netherlands Business School. Three foreign institutions are leaving because of accreditation issues related to a recent review of all MBA programs. Monash will remain (it does not offer an MBA program), as will the British-based Henley Management College, primarily a distance provider. Mauritius is trying to establish itself as a “cyber island” by attracting foreign IT firms from the West and India.

2.3.2 Government Sponsorship and Algerian students in the UK

Internationalisation has stimulated transformation and development in different sectors such as economy, politics and education, which led local and national institutions to be transformed by developing several policies to promote internationalisation. For instance, the internationalisation of higher education can involve incorporating a global dimension into the process of education, which can influence its purpose, functions, or delivery (Knight, 2004). The process of internationalisation can be affected by foreign mediators that are independent of local education systems. For instance, international governmental organisations (IGOs), like the United Nations and the World Bank, are sponsoring global educational schedules that support different educational discourses such as multiculturalism, industrialisation, and the development of the economy.

In addition, the Non-Governmental Organisations, especially those who focus on environmentalism and human rights, have also an impact on the transformations of schools' curricula around the world. In addition, academics from different parts of the world are calling for international cooperation in both research and teaching by making use of information and communications technology solutions that may facilitate the internationalisation processes (Sanderson, 2011)

Internationalisation has been affecting the realm of higher education since a long time by means of academic cooperation between universities and the flow of academics and knowledge. It is hard to deny that the current time of globalisation is highly influencing higher education

especially the internationalisation processes. There is a growing trend towards universities selecting international partners with which they intend to form deep relationships where there might be exchanging both faculty and students, building research teams across their campuses.

I think that internationalisation directly contributes to the main objectives of the university in two essential ways. For instance, students who graduate these days can join the global labour force, working for companies that are multinational and working alongside co-workers coming from different parts of the world. To have successful careers, they may need to be internationally mobile across the globe.

Graduate students who want to be successful in the global labour market may need a global worldview and awareness of the different cultures and languages and to be comfortable in that space (Gunn, 2017), which is why most leading universities in the world focus more on having a diverse international population on campus. In addition, they have a connected curriculum with opportunities for mobility (Fung, 2017). Another objective relates to the notion of ontological shock that aims at turning graduates into critical independent thinkers by exposing them to different cultures and other ways of doing things. For instance, students who studied abroad and immersed themselves into other cultures may show signs of maturity, cultural awareness, and open-mindedness.

The opening of Algeria to the international market appeared through the creation of many private international companies, which created an urgent need for foreign languages, especially English and French. After the events of 9/11/2001, the Algerian government came under pressure to transform its institutions and to embrace internationalisation as part of the global war on terror (Karmani, 2005). English has blossomed in Algeria when the country was heading toward socio-economic prosperity thanks to its gas and oil revenues (Bouhadiba, 2006). During that period, English learners had access to the British Council and the Afro-American Institute, which motivated them to master the English language along with the culture. Besides Algerian teachers of English, there were other educators from Pakistan, India, the U.K. and the U.S. In addition, the Algerian government introduced massive programmes in the early 1980s to train Algerian teachers of English, mainly in the UK (Bouhadiba, 2006). In 1996, English replaced French as the main foreign language taught in school (Crystal, 2012).

The Ministry of Higher Education in Algeria has recently adapted programs that provide significant learning quality inspired by the Bologna process that is officially embedded in their

education systems and has become part of the national strategy. The Bologna process was adopted for the reformation of the higher education curricula and the degree requirements to accord to a Bachelors- Master's PhD system used in the European countries. This approach attempts to permit the mobility of teachers, students and labourers across nations (Buckner, 2011).

International cooperation is necessary for the Algerian government to fulfil its development objectives and to open up to the world. The Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research initiated a process, which identified several priorities. One aim was to create cooperation based on the partnership with the sharing of findings and expenditure, involving researchers who possess equivalent levels of competence. For instance, in May 2012, Algeria signed an agreement with Morocco aimed at exchanging information and expertise on a variety of educational topics including curricula development, human resources development and administration (The Report: Algeria, 2015).

Another aim is to create integrated joint training and research universities. For example, in 2013, the Algerian and Tunisian governments agreed on a cooperation project in higher education. This project works to establish a common university degree and allows student and professor exchanges (The Report: Algeria, 2015). Additionally, the Algerian government aims at underpinning new opportunities for multilateral cooperation, especially with the European Union (Tempus IV and Erasmus Mundus). Moreover, the state aims at building capacity in English in its universities. In January 2014, the Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research with the cooperation of the UK Government agreed to fund 500 Algerian PhD scholars in English to UK universities over a five-year period (British Council, 2015).

2.4 Summary of the chapter

This study aims at exploring the concept of identity development regarding the experiences of studying abroad for Algerian PhD students in the UK. It also addresses the different views on the effects of the shifts between spaces, cultures, and lifestyles in relation to the values that construct the Algerian students' identity. This chapter sets the context of this research by introducing the social context of Algeria as well as the education system, which includes different issues of the education system and some of the policies used to remedy those issues. Training students abroad is one of the proposed remedies to the education system in Algeria, however, it also presents several challenges to students such as cultural transition and adjusting

to the new cultures. Other related literature on students' mobility, acculturation process, and academic adjustment will be discussed in relation to different theories about culture identity development will be discussed in the following chapters.

Chapter 3: Mobility, cultural transition, acculturation and adjustment of international doctoral students

Introduction

This chapter provides a critical analysis and discussion of the relevant literature and discusses some prominent theories concerning international doctoral students' sojourn experience to explore concepts and frameworks used in this study. This literature review provides a context to the research and depicts how it has developed throughout time. This chapter is organised into four main sections, which explore the main theoretical concepts in this study that are related to (1) culture, (2) identity negotiation, (3) mobility, adjustment, acculturation processes and (4) an overview of Bronfenbrenner's bioecological theory of human development.

In each section, I will provide a short overview explaining the complexity of the key elements in this study. I emphasise that theories used in this research were not used as a whole, however: I specifically focused on some features, which are significant in relation to this research.

I start with reviewing the literature on adjustment strategies and acculturation process abroad attempting to explain the way home culture affects the identity development of Algerian doctoral sojourners in the UK. In addition, I will explore the different coping strategies that are used by students from different cultural backgrounds since this is a critical point for the first research question:

- 1) What are the different adjustment strategies used by Algerian PhD student sojourners to cope with the experience abroad?

I continue the critical analysis by reviewing the literature on the terms 'culture' and 'identity' and how the related theories have emerged and developed through time to explain how these complex and multifaceted terms influence each other. In addition, I will explore the different aspects of Algerian sojourners' identity that might be affected when living in a different culture.

- 2) What aspects of the Algerian PhD student sojourners' identity are affected during the experience abroad and in what way?

Also, in this chapter, I will explore the Algerian Doctoral students' experiences and the perceived outcomes through the existing literature on study abroad programmes.

Overview

This chapter presents a critical literature review that affects my research and may help stimulate future research on the Algerian doctoral student sojourners' experiences in the UK. Theories about culture, identity negotiation and adjustment strategies are subjects related to people who live in a different environment that has a different culture than their original one, this could involve migrants, refugees, workers and students.

In this study, I used the research questions as a literature search strategy. I first constructed the research questions and highlighted the key concepts, including: identity, acculturation strategies, and Algerian PhD students in the UK. The next step was thinking of different synonyms and different word-combinations for the aforementioned concepts. Most of my research took place on the internet with material accessed onsite or remotely using library resources. I also used databases such Google Scholar and Research Gate, which contain a high percentage of scholarly articles. It was important to include different combinations of search terms such as “identity development”, “hybrid identity”, “identity development of international students”, “cultural identity”, “doctoral identity”, “mobility of international students”, “social identity theory”, “personal identity theory”, “mobility, acculturation and adjustment” that are likely to appear in articles written by scholars. This allowed me to make the search as broad as possible, and to capture as many papers as I could, which were related to this study.

Unlike using the library catalogue, the use of Google Scholar allowed me to instruct the search engine to prioritise documents that contain all the highlighted combinations of research terms. In order to refine the search a little further, Google Scholar allowed me to select the year of publication, which made it easier to access the more recent publications.

There are different views concerning the definitions of the terms ‘culture’ and ‘identity’. Postmodernist theorists view that the modernist understanding of culture and identity can be incomplete. Many scholars argue that the modernist approach to defining and explaining such terms is based on normative conceptions and practical definitions (Josephs, 2003; Bhatia and Ram, 2004; Brooker, 2014; Lash, 2014). On the one hand, some theories, which focus on personal identity such as the theory of cognitive consistency view identity as fixed or constant (e.g. Suh, 2002; Dhar et al., 2010; Dunkel and Worsley, 2016). On the other hand, other theories consider identity as fluid across contexts and can be negotiated in different social contexts (Darvin and Norton, 2015; Schachter, 2014).

This chapter focuses on two main elements including the definition of culture and an inspection of the main approaches used to differentiate between the different dimensions of cultural values. First, various definitions of culture and the various levels of culture – from underlying values to visible behaviours- are discussed and it has been shown that culture can be viewed as an onion-like construct, made up out of different levels that each influence the higher levels. Several approaches to classifying culture have been provided in the following section. These can be classified from single concepts, like the perception of time, to non- verbal behaviours.

Interacting with their environments, people generally develop some key characteristics such as beliefs, norms and values. Studies in anthropology (e.g. Sokefeld, 1999; Ross, 2000) argue that culture can affect and shape different identity aspects. Identity aspects can be defined as the set of characteristics and qualities that are essential to a person's self-awareness and by which he/she is recognisable in terms of collective categories (Simon and Hastedt, 1999). For instance, Weinrich and sonderson, (2005) state that identity can be affected by different aspects such as ethnicity, race, gender, and socio-economic class. International Doctoral students are not an exception since they live in a different cultural environment and interact with different individuals in different social and scholarly contexts using different language.

Many studies on acculturation examine certain aspects of adaptation concerning identity development; a shift between two or more different cultures may create a spectrum of realities that are needed to be explored and understood. People who study abroad and use a different language than their own mother tongue in their interaction may show signs of transformation in identity. Identity transformation can be defined as a process that includes widening perceptions, challenging norms and reworking personal characteristics and attitudes (Ellwood, 2011). This can appear when one's original system of values and beliefs is challenged and cannot create meaning from unfamiliar social and cultural systems (Laitin, 1998; Dolby, 2004; Angulo, 2008; Bosma and Kunnen, 2008). Consequently, the environment in which individuals live and interact can have a major impact on identity negotiation/ development and the used coping strategies.

Despite the great efforts in defining the term culture, there is still no common “correct” definition of the concept. Additionally, this chapter presents a section about intercultural communicative competence, which starts with the history of the concept and its development.

3. 1 Understanding culture

Culture is one hard concept to define because it encompasses several fields, such as anthropology, sociology, history, literature, philosophy, psychology and linguistics. That is why it is difficult to find out one valid definition that covers all the aspects of culture. Scholars, such as Kroeber and Kluckhohn (1952), have critically reviewed concepts and definitions of culture and collected a long list of different definitions and statements about culture. The first usages of the term culture appear to exclude a large percentage of people from society, by considering only a small portion to have culture. Nowadays, however, this usage of the culture might be referred to as high culture in contrast to popular culture (Storey, 2006). As a reaction to the first usage of culture, scholars like Tylor (1870) argues that culture is a complex entity that is comprised of knowledge, belief, art, morals, law, custom and any other capabilities and habits acquired when living within a society.

The third usage of culture developed in anthropology in the work of Boas (1911) and his students in which they reacted to the social evolutionists for the reason that they stressed the universal character of the varied cultures of different individuals or societies rather than emphasising their uniqueness.

The more recent works still stress the notion of culture as knowledge. For instance, cognitivists, such as Goodenough (1969), define culture as the knowledge people must acquire to function in a specific society. Other scholars, such as Holland and Quinn (1987) used concepts from schema theory and they defined culture as an internal mental schema for understanding the world and deciding how to behave. Another refining concept of culture is put forward by Hall (1989) who sees culture as an invisible mechanism operating in our subconscious cognitive system. In his view, an individual becomes aware of culture when it is seriously questioned, for example, by the exposure to different people from different cultures. Cognitive theories have been criticised for focusing too narrowly on internal cognitive processes and separating the impact of external interactions with the environment.

Recent cognitive researchers have taken great consideration to the relationship between internal mental processes and meanings and externally shared meanings (Strauss and Quinn, 1997). Additional criticism has come from critical cultural theories that reject the unproblematic portrayal of culture in cognitive theories. To some extent, cognitive theorists have addressed this criticism by considering culture as multiple entities that have no fixed boundaries.

For example, Malinowski (1944), an anthropologist who travelled in the early 20th century to the islands of Papua New Guinea to study the natives in their "original environment". Malinowski writings represent them as the possessors of a distinct culture, which has remained uncontaminated by any freeing influence. Conversely, Bhabha (1994) contends that such a notion of pure uncontaminated culture is a myth. All cultures are characterised by interconnectedness, which Bhabha refers to as "Hybridity". Another modern-day anthropologist Clifford (1992) in his essay: *Travelling cultures* takes up the case of Malinowski (1922) and argues that the representation of Papuan culture as pure, static, unchanging and uncontaminated is an illusion that is constructed by most of the anthropologist writing about their field studies about culture far from "the west". The illusion is created by stressing on the isolation of the field of study leaving away details about how the researchers made their way to that "isolated location". This illusion, argues Clifford, will immediately be destroyed by providing a detailed account of the travel, which connects the anthropological field with the metropolitan world. Another important point here is the way anthropologists communicate with the inhabitants of remote cultures. This might suggest a form of translation that researchers used to understand the culture of the native inhabitants. As Malinowski's case suggests, no culture is isolated enough to maintain its purity that remains static over time. The alternative of this idea of a static culture or identity, Bhabha suggests that culture is characterised by change, flux, transformation and interconnectedness (hybridity).

Almost every individual belongs to several different groups and categories of people at the same time and so people contain several layers of culture within themselves (Hofstede et al., 1990). Similarly, Giddens (2005) refers to the ways of life of the members of society, or of groups within a society as the 'culture'. He suggests that it includes their clothes, their marriage customs, language and family life, their patterns of work, religious ceremonies and even leisure pursuits.

In this research, culture is understood through a post-colonial lens as Bhabha, (1994) sees it as multiple, fluid and changeable arguing that creative cultural forms can be created as a way of pushing against the colonisers' political force or as he calls it "cultural third spaces". In the context of this study, culture is seen as the context affecting the individuals' constant development of hybrid identity. As the Algerian doctoral students travel abroad to the UK and study for several years, there would be several changes including several cultural, social and academic contexts.

3. 1.1 Features and characteristics of Culture

According to Spencer-Oatey (2012) culture is manifested in three main layers: (a) observable artefacts, (b) values and (c) basic underlying assumptions. At the first level, data related to observable artefacts, visible and audible pattern behaviours, can be easy to collect, but hard to interpret. For instance, Hofstede (1991) shows three levels of cultural manifestations. At the first level come Symbols, which may include words, gestures, pictures or objects that carry a specific meaning, which is only recognised by those who share the culture. At the second level come, Heroes, who are persons possessing characteristics that are highly prized in culture and, accordingly, can serve as models for behaviour. At the third level come Rituals, which are collective activities that are considered as socially essential. Hofstede (1998) regards values as the core of culture and describes them as trends to prefer certain characteristics over others. People may implicitly acquire some values at a young age; therefore, they may not be able to directly observe them, nor can they discuss them with others. They can only be inferred from the way people act under certain circumstances. For instance, the way some people greet others can be easy to describe by observing a group of people in their environment and patterns, which can be recognisable among the members, but often, it is hard to understand why a group behaves the way it does. To do so, a qualitative analysis must be carried out on a deeper level of values and assumptions. Values are manifested by the group of the society, but the underlying reasons behind their behaviours remain unconscious (Argyris, 1982). They are defined as the culturally defined principles of desirability, goodness, beauty and many other things that serve as broad guidelines for the social living (Griswold, 2012). Generally, assumptions of a cultural group may comprise values that are taken for granted; therefore, they become less debatable and unconscious (Spencer-Oatey, 2012). For this reason, deep interviews with key members of that society or analysis of artefacts, like documents and charters, are needed to extract the values that influence behaviours. Understanding a culture requires deciphering certain values via deep exploration into the underlying assumptions.

3. 1.2 Hall's classification of culture

Hall (1976) noticed ideas between different cultures about interpersonal relationships, attitudes to time and personal space. He did not study cultures, but the relations between cultures. He believes that cultures could be placed in a line and compared in terms of attitudes to time,

personal space and interpersonal relationships. This section will provide further details about the different classifications

3.3.2.1 High contexts vs low contexts

Some cultures are explicit in their use of language and communication, while other cultures use implicit understandings and non-verbal cues to get their point across. With regard to communication, cultures can be separated into two groups, high context cultures and low context cultures (Hall 1976). On the one hand, the low context communicators may be verbally direct to the point with a strong emphasis put on the literal meaning of the words employed. In addition, low context communicators tend to favour a more informal mode of communication. On the other hand, the high context of communication involves a lot more reading between the lines. It is about interpreting the nuances of language, facial expressions and gestures. For example, a high context communicator may imply something rather than stating it directly. High context communicators favour more formal modes of communication. The high/low context classification considers the importance of context in decoding the communication and more broadly a set of aspects related to the interaction among individuals.

The high/low contexts concepts are considered among the most frequently used concepts when analysing communication. The distinction between high-context and low-context communication helps to understand whether the communication situation is in individualistic or collective cultures (Oetzel and Ting-Toomey, 2003).

At the linguistic level, it may be difficult to determine the extent of directness since communication is a complex phenomenon that includes explicit as well as implicit meanings (Ting-Toomey et al., 2000). In addition, it could be a hard task to identify whether a given country is categorised as high or low context due to the limited statistical evidence.

3.3.2.2 Polychronic versus monochronic time orientation

Hall's concept of polychronic versus monochronic time understanding deals with the ways of structuring time. Every culture views and values time in a different way (Hall, 1976). Table 1 gives a brief overview of the two different time concepts and their resultant behaviour. Generally, the monochronic time cultures tend to follow a sequential orientation “one thing at a time”, while the polychronic cultures focus on the ability of handling multiple tasks

simultaneously and that time orientation is important in determining the different ways in developing interpersonal relations (Dahl, 2004).

Table 1: Monochronic and Polychronic Cultures

	Monochronic Culture	Polychronic Culture
Interpersonal Relations	Interpersonal relations are subordinate to present schedule	Present schedule is subordinate to Interpersonal relations
Activity Coordination	Schedule co-ordinates activity; appointment time is rigid.	Interpersonal relations co-ordinate activity; appointment time is flexible
Task Handling	One task at a time	Many tasks are handled simultaneously
Breaks and Personal Time	Breaks and personal time are sacrosanct regardless of personal ties.	Breaks and personal time are subordinate to personal ties.
Temporal Structure	Time is inflexible; time is tangible	Time is flexible; time is fluid
Work/personal time separability	Work time is clearly separable from personal time	Work time is not clearly separable from personal time
Organisational Perception	Activities are isolated from organisation as a whole; tasks are measured by output in time (activity per hour or minute)	Activities are integrated into organisation as a whole; tasks are measured as part of overall organisational goal

(Adopted from: Victor, 1992, p.234)

Monochronic cultures tend to be focused on the schedule, on doing one thing after another, usually in sequence. Many Western cultures fit the transcription of being are monochronic, particularly, countries like the United States, Switzerland and Germany. For instance, it is common for people from these cultures to schedule a day full of meetings with agendas ending promptly and moving to the next meeting one right after the other. This approach may not work well in the east and Middle East regions, where culture may be more polychronic. The sequential approach can send the wrong message and often offend people from polychronic cultures. Focusing on the schedule rather the human interaction may send the wrong message, which can result in misunderstandings. Differently, polychronic time orientation could be considered as a very practical plan on doing more than one thing at the time. For instance, individuals who come from a polychronic culture may choose to take the time to build the relationship and expect people to do the same for them as they plan on doing multiple things at one time. A key limitation of Hall's research is that it follows a paradigm, which describes the social sciences and the human behaviours as static entities. Dahl (2008) asserts that despite the usefulness of Hall's concepts, they are over simple and ambiguous, which make them difficult to apply within a framework of a more analytical approach.

3. 1.3 Hofstede's cultural dimensions

Many scholars addressed the absence of comprehensive frameworks that can accurately classify cultural patterns. One of the most cited works in the area of culture research is the study of Hofstede (1991), which provides a general framework for analysis that can be helpful in exploring everyday encounters.

Hofstede (1991) defines the term culture as “the collective programming of the mind” (P.12) that can distinguish one group of people from another. The human mental programming model presented by Hofstede (Figure 1) illustrates the relationship between the three different levels that are, personality, culture and human nature. Mayer (2007) defines personality as “the organised, developing system within the individual that represents the collective action of that individual’s major psychological subsystems” (p. 14). Spencer-Oatey (2012) adds that personality is the unique personal set of mental programs that is not shared with any other human being. Pursuant to Hofstede (1994) the individual’s identity can be both inherited and learned, which can highlight the diversity of individual personalities within a particular culture.

In comparison to personality, Hofstede et al., (2005) consider that culture is the learned collective programming of the mind that separates one group of people from another, while human nature is what all human beings have in common, such as the ability to feel fear, anger, love, joy, sadness, the need to associate with others, to play and exercise oneself, the facility to observe the environment and talk about it with other humans. In fact, many researchers have criticised the notion of human nature, which Hofstede is considering as a shared concept whereas he does not focus on the personal self.

Figure 1: Levels of human mental development (Hofstede, 1994)

Hofstede's work has emphasised the importance of cultural differences across national borders and his model has become an indispensable part of intercultural communication studies. His work is based on the results of an international survey conducted by the American multinational corporation IBM between 1967 and 1973. The company's international employee attitude survey program focused on employees' values across nations. From the results he obtained, Hofstede (1994) has created a four-dimensional model, which looked at culture in relation to power distance, individualism vs. collectivism, masculinity vs. femininity, uncertainty avoidance, and long-term vs short-term orientation.

3. 1.3.1 Power distance

Power distance can be related to the distribution of power between members within societies, institutions, and organisations (Hofstede, 1994). For instance, in some countries, institutions, or organisations, some members can be more powerful than others, and less powerful members of institutions may expect and accept that power is unequally distributed. In other words, individuals in cultures demonstrating a high-power distance are very respectful to figures of authority and generally accept an unequal distribution of power. In all societies, inequality is present, but in some societies more strongly than in others (Erdman, 2018; Lee and Lalwani, 2017). For instance, organisations with high power distance centralise power and subordinates expect to be told what to do from their superiors, whereas organisations that exist in cultures demonstrating a low power distance can show a fairly decentralised with flat hierarchical systems where subordinates and superiors consider each other as existentially equal (Hofstede et al., 2005; Christiansen et al., 2014).

3. 1.3.2 Individualism versus collectivism

The second dimension proposed by Hofstede (1994) is Individualism versus Collectivism in which he sees that individualistic cultures encourage competition rather than cooperation. Samovar et al., (2014) illustrate how individual initiatives and achievements are stressed and how individual decision making is valued. Dahl (2004) clarifies that in individualist cultures, minimal consideration is given to other groups when goals are set, while in collectivist cultures, other groups are taken into account in a major way when goals are set.

3. 1.3.3 Masculinity versus Femininity

Hofstede's third dimension Masculinity vs. Femininity does not mean actual males and females; however, their meaning can be understood in relation to gender identity, which can be the same as their designated sex at birth or can be different from it (Bakir et al, 2015). For example, a man can be feminine and a woman can be masculine. A society can be called masculine if the emotional gender roles are distinct in the sense that males are expected to be tough, and focused on material success, whereas females are expected to be focused on the quality of life. On the other hand, feminine societies appear to have no role separation or a weaker role separation. Most societies are somewhere in between. In feminine societies, people try to balance family and work; however, in a masculine society, work may be more important than family and sometimes it is an acceptable excuse to neglect the family. Within the family, in a feminine society, the father and mother deal with feelings whereas, in a masculine society, the father deals with facts and the mother deals with feelings (Merkin, 2018). All societies use a set of gender classification on which the social identity of individuals is established in relation to other society members.

3. 1.3.4 Uncertainty avoidance

Uncertainty avoidance can often be seen when people from certain cultures feel uncomfortable when they face uncertainty during unknown situations (Hofstede, 1994). It is the final dimension present in his original work where he compares two extreme types of societies including uncertainty avoiding societies on the one hand, and uncertainty accepting societies on the other stating that most of the societies are somewhere in between. Uncertainty avoiding societies perceive uncertainty as a threat that must be fought, which makes people in those societies more stressed and anxious, in comparison to uncertainty accepting societies, in which people admit uncertainty and accept changes in life.

3. 1.3.5 Long-term orientation versus short-term orientation

In a more recent work, Hofstede (2001) introduces a fifth dimension in which he compares long-term-oriented cultures with short-term oriented cultures. This dimension is the result of his co-operation with Michael Bond, who links this dimension to the work of Confucius.

Table 2: Comparison of long term and short-term orientations

Short-term orientation	Long-term orientation
Effort should produce quick results	Perseverance, sustained efforts toward slow results.
Social pressure toward spending	Thrift, being sparing with resources
Respect for traditions	Respect for circumstance
Concern with personal stability	Concern with personal adaptiveness
Concern with social and status obligations	Willingness to subordinate oneself for a purpose
Concern with “face”	Having a sense of shame

Source: Hofstede (2001) p. 366.

Long term orientated cultures tend to value more aspects, such as persistence, parsimony and the individuals’ sense of shame. In contrast, individuals from short-term-oriented cultures value aspects related to personal stability, reciprocation of favours and gifts, and there is a pressure for immediate spending.

3. 1.3.6 Arguments supporting Hofstede

Søndergaard (1994) believes that Hofstede’s research success is due to the favourable conditions, which existed for his research at the time of its publication. For example, many businesses, which were just entering the international arena, were experiencing many difficulties and needed advice. During the same period, academic research attention shifted toward culture and Hofstede was considered a pioneer and pathfinder (Søndergaard, 1994).

3. 1.3.7 Arguments against Hofstede

Some scholars criticised and some complimented the Hofstede work on cultural dimensions. Like, for some of the economists, the research work of Hofstede is highly controversial. Key issues, which run against Hofstede’s are:

Relevancy

Many researchers criticise that the survey is not an appropriate instrument for an accurate measurement of cultural disparity. Schwartz (1999) argues that the inclusion of values is problematic in some cases, some variables being more sensitive to one culture and not for another. This is especially apparent when the variable being measured is a value.

Cultural Homogeneity

Most nations are groups of ethnic units, yet Hofstede's study regards the domestic population as a homogenous whole (Baskerville, 2003; Jones, 2007). In other words, Hofstede assesses individuals and applies findings to an overall community (Dorfman and Howell, 1988). Therefore, the analysis is constrained by the character of the individual being assessed; the outcomes have a possibility of arbitrariness.

National Divisions

McSweeney (2002) believes that cultures are not necessarily bounded by borders. For that reason, nations are not the proper units of analysis. DiMaggio (1997) adds that recent research has found that culture is fragmented across the group and national lines.

Political Influences

The outcomes, especially those related to Femininity vs Masculinity and Uncertainty Avoidance, may have been sensitive to the time when the survey was conducted (Søndergaard, 1994; Jones, 2007). For instance, during the time Hofstede collected his data, there were many political instabilities such as the Cold War in Europe and similarly, there were the communist rebellion wars in Asia and Africa.

One company approach

The research approach of Hofstede is based on data from one company IBM, which possibly cannot provide accurate information on the entire cultural system of a given country (Søndergaard, 1994; Jones and Alony, 2007). I assume that the findings of one company can't explain the overall culture to ascertain cultural dimensions. Nevertheless, Hofstede (1998) argues that the cross-sectional analysis was appropriate for this study because he was not making an absolute measure, but he was merely estimating differences between cultures.

Outdated

Despite the great impact that Hofstede's research made, some researchers claim that his work is old fashioned and cannot richly illustrate some modern values due to the rapidly changing global environments and internationalisation. Nonetheless, Hofstede reasons that recent

findings have supported the idea that culture will not change overnight for the reason that the cross-cultural outcomes are based on centuries of indoctrination.

Too Few Dimensions

I assume, as many researchers do, that five dimensions may not give sufficient knowledge about cultural differences. This approach may not be convenient in all situations and several dimensions should be added to this work (Hofstede, 1998). In addition to that, the binary classification approach of the cultural dimensions seems to raise some doubt since culture is considered a complex entity. Hofstede has oversimplified it by trying to explain it via a few dimensions. I believe it would be more appropriate if the concept is illustrated via a spectrum because cultures are dynamic and heterogeneous.

Statistical integrity

Jones, (2007) claims that there are still some interesting and relevant problems to be addressed, such as using the same questionnaire items on more than one scale and several have significant cross-loadings. Furthermore, Dorfman and Howell (1988) clarify that Hofstede's analysis is limited since the analysis comprises of 32 questions with only 40 cases or subjects, and that would increase the possibility of sample error (Dorfman and Howell, 1988).

Binary opposition and classification

Hofstede is using binary or dichotomous thinking for framing the concept of culture. The five dichotomies he used are individualism v. collectivism, masculinity v. femininity and uncertainty avoidance and long-term v. short term orientation. Hofstede's original work contained only four problem types and it was criticised for his predominantly Western European biased. Moreover, it seems more logical that the elements of culture are explanatory when they are part of a meaningful system (Jones, 2007).

Limitation of value framework

Identifying cultural values helps to understand broad cultural differences, but it is important to note that not everyone in each society holds the dominant value (Kirkman et al., 2006). Another limitation of value framework is that they tend to assume that a group membership is the essential characteristic of a given member in all contexts and all times (Taras et al., 2010).

3. 2 Theories of identity

Within this literature review, along with the presentation of the constructs that frame my research project, I consider it important to highlight the fact that it is also intended to show why is it necessary to study and do research on the concept of identity in EFL settings and its possible effects on a further reconstruction or, at least, awareness of the dynamics of the process of foreign language teaching and learning.

In this study, identity is seen from the poststructuralist viewpoint that considers it as multiple, dynamic, complex and socially constructed (Miyahara, 2015; Norton, 2018). Identity has various meanings in the literature, but these definitions share the notion of identity as a relational phenomenon. Terms such as self and identity are very popular in language-learning literature and relevant volumes and papers that are published every year. This is not surprising, given that language is the main vehicle of expressing the self (Tabouret-Keller, 2017). In the field of English language teaching (ELT), many contemporary researchers have defined identity as a process of continual emerging and becoming (Leung et al., 2014; Cook, 2016). This notion recognises identity as the perception of individuals towards others and mutually the perception of others towards them (Lawler, 2015). Varghese et al., (2005) consider identity as a process that changes over time whenever the context changes. Moreover, identity can be related to the understanding of the relationship between people and their surrounding environment, also the way that relationship is changing across time and space (Norton and Toohey, 2011).

Within the field of education, there are several definitions and interpretations of identity. These definitions can be classified into essentialist and non-essentialist views. On the one hand, non-essentialists view identity as dynamic and multiple entities that can be co-constructed; whereas essentialists view it as an integral, unified, and a complete entity (Hall, 1991). Many researchers, such as Taylor (2017); Ting Toomey (2017); Gardner and Willey (2016); Garner and Kaplan (2018), employ the non-essentialist notion of identity, particularly fluidity, contingency, plurality and complexity, to review identity issues in their studies.

In a later work, Hall (1997) addresses the non-essentialist view of identity and suggests two ways of seeing the identity. He views identity as an incomplete product that is still and always will be in process and never be constructed in isolation from history, language and culture. In this definition, Hall (1997) implies that he is against the views that consider identity as the unique, shared values that composed of a collective *one true self* and includes superficial and

artificial imposed *selves*, which people with a shared history have in common. He follows that identity could be seen as a reflection of the collective historical knowledge and common cultural values that generate a constant framework of meaning for individuals. The second position that Hall (1997) supports is that identity is both an issue of *being* as well as an issue of *becoming*; it includes both past and future. In other words, identity has a history and it is continually changing. This notion of identity as multiple may result in contradictory identities existing within one individual that may need a process of negotiation in several contexts.

Following the non-essentialist viewpoint on cultural identity, Bhabha (1994) introduces the idea of *third spaces*, which is a process of cultural hybridity in contrast to cultural polarity and binaries (Bhabha, 1994). Using the term *hybridity* in relation to identity may imply that identities are not fixed, restricted and isolated units. This view overlaps with numerous studies that confirm the development of identity as an on-going process a view held in various disciplines. That development is believed to have a great impact in helping individuals in interpreting themselves as a certain kind of a person in different contexts (Beijaard et al., 2004). For instance, Hall (1992) argues that identity becomes changeable in the sense that it is constantly formed and transformed according to the surrounding cultural system. Similarly, Dolby (2000) argues that identity can be produced and reproduced to adapt itself into the new contexts in which it is situated. Classic arguments support the idea of identity as only a process of becoming making use of terms such as changeable and constructed, a view that partially ignores the role of the history, language and culture in the process of becoming (Hall, 1992).

Moreover, Oyserman (2009) argues that the individual's identity can be adaptable in the sense that it focuses on some features of the immediate context to provide a meaningful explanation. Studies such as Burke, and Stets (2009); Danielewicz (2014) confirm that identities cannot be unified or fixed, considering that they are constantly changing, multiple and continually reconstructed. For instance, Norton (2013), who studied the case of immigrant women in Canada, reports that some of her participants exhibit some complex multidimensional identities such as being a wife, a mother, a language learner, a worker and an immigrant at the same time.

From the discussion above, research on identity has become an independent research area and is generating much debate and motivating many researchers in the field of language learning and teaching including this research. In the last few decades, the field of identity has become

interdisciplinary (Gao, 2007) since it contains works from anthropology, sociology, postcolonial and cultural studies, and education (Norton, 2013).

Terms such as culture, communication and identity, all of which are central to the present study, have been a subject of debate. By definition, these terms are attempts to derive generalised and broad understandings of complex processes. On the one hand, there is the modernist aspect, which considers these terms as fixed entities that describe and influence all individuals and groups on the globe. On the other hand, I find the post-modernist perspectives that acknowledge the variability, flexibility and constant flux, as well as the complexity of defining the human experience.

Even though there are disciplinary, terminological and categorical differences, it is important to focus on identity research and to reflect upon the process that links psycho/social factors and linguistic expressions, particularly when they occur in intercultural and multilingual settings. As a rich and complex concept, “identity” has been discussed in many disciplines such as sociolinguistics, linguistic anthropology, sociology, psychology, history, literature, gender studies and social theory.

In this study, the concept of identity is very important since it is considered as an analytical tool of understanding among individuals in society (Gee, 2001). Like many fundamental terms and concepts in psychology, the concept of identity is hard to define in a direct and specific way. One of the various ways to think about identity is the self-concept, which can be considered as a multidimensional cognitive structure made up of multiple identities (King and Smith, 2004; Settles, 2004; Burke, 2006; Jones et al., 2007; Leary and Tangney, 2011; Oyserman et al., 2012). In its essence, identity can be defined in terms of how someone thinks about, perceives, evaluates herself or himself, and that the self is closely connected with moral practices involving agency and responsibility (Harre, 1984). Indeed, identity can be a tricky and a complex idea to understand since it comprises cognitive, perceptual, affective and evaluative dimensions (Hoge and Renzulli, 1993; Roccas and Brewer, 2002) and because it is both stable and dynamic and combines structural and process properties (Hitlin, 2003).

In the past few decades, the concept of identity has been defined broadly in sociology and other fields. For instance, many of the definitions of identity in sociology give the impression that individuals may be trapped in their social and symbolic universe; whereas, in philosophy and psychology, identity appears to be analysed in isolation from its social construction of reality

(Shoemaker and Tobia, 2018). In fact, many researchers illustrate the changing beliefs concerning how people think of themselves and their surrounding environment. For instance, Beck and Beck-Gernsheim (2009) describe a shift from a situation where people were tied to the value system and shared goals to the contemporary attention on individualism, self-enlightenment and self-liberation. Cultural hybridity can be seen as a transformative space in which the different elements from distinct cultures blend to form new identities (Bhabha, 1994). This position challenges other essentialist views about culture and identity as static and unchangeable. Similarly, Werbner (2001) argues that cultures transform during the cultural encounters between the colonised and the colonisers, which result in creating hybrid identities. This shift of identity understanding may be apprehended as a shift from the understanding of identity as rigid in what was considered as homogenous societies to hybrid and multiple identities that embody constant changeability and fluctuation in heterogeneous societies.

Bhabha's work (1994) has been important in explaining the development of culture and identity within conditions of colonial history. In today's world, the accelerating process of globalisation and the unprecedented increase of interconnectedness between different cultures across the globe comes with more challenges. For instance, the use of cultural dichotomies such as (homogeneous vs. heterogeneous, individualistic vs. collectivistic) can negatively affect the understanding of culture and self. Different notions, such as an independent, pure, and fixed cultures are becoming an illusion (Clifford, 1992) since traditional conceptions of cultural dichotomies are challenged in three major points: the increasing cultural connections, the impact of the global system, and the accelerating cultural complexity (Hermans and Kempen, 1998).

I believe that the concept of identity is very important since it is considered as an analytical tool for understanding individuals in society. Its importance can be seen through the shift of focus towards the concept of identity and its dimensions within several fields of study (Block, 2017). For instance, De Fina (2012) explains that the shift towards social constructionism indicates that research on culture and identity shifted from the macro-level that focuses on society in general to the micro-level that focuses more on individuals' experiences, perceptions and beliefs. For instance, identity is created by interactions with other people and reactions to different expectations of society therefore identity can be fluid and multiple and changeable in different contexts on interaction.

According to Clark (2013), the subjective dimensions of identity predominate in the literature, where it is a sociocultural phenomenon that comes from and within local, interactional discourse contexts that are social and cultural in nature, as fixed social categories. Consequently, different interactive identities could exist simultaneously social, cultural, national and individual. Thus, identity can never be included in a single analysis in all its complexity. For instance, individuals in this research study can have different identities depending on the context in which they are interacting. For example, when interacting within the academic establishments, identities such as international student, Algerian doctoral students, researchers might be accentuated, whereas outside academic establishments, identities such as friends, Algerian culture ambassadors, and Muslim people could be more dominant.

Similar to Bhabha's notion of "third space", the relationships of the elements of "one's own" and "the other" were shaped as a process of interaction, in which the elements are mixed, but not assimilated (Griem, 1998. pp. 220-221). The concept of "hybrid identity" in this study can be understood in relation to the notion of blurring boundaries of national identities in "global postmodernism" (Hall, 1999. p. 425). For instance, recent identity studies started focussing on the identity processes of individuals in contexts that encourage negotiating social boundaries and manage different experiences and expectations (Clarke et al., 2009; Garcia and Hardy, 2007; Ybema et al., 2012). In the context of this study, Algerian PhD students in the UK may experience complex situations that can affect their identity development and tend to mark the beginning of the process of hybrid identity. This process can be characterised by embracing a multiplicity of attitudes and a combination of various identity aspects that do not usually go together (Golden-Biddle and Rao, 1997).

3.2.1 Identity construction process

Identity can be seen as a life-long process that is a combination of several sub-processes (Lipiansky, 2008). For instance, it contains many simultaneous processes including a process of individuation and differentiation through which individuals start to see themselves as different beings. The process of identification is another way to identity formation; it allows individuals to spot differences and patterns of their environment, and it fosters their feeling as members of some communities. In addition, identity formation can go through a process of attribution by which individuals can explain the causes of their behaviours, events and the feedback that comes from others; in other words, it allows them to understand their own identity

and mechanisms of meaning-making. Furthermore, identity construction can be seen as a process of narcissistic valuation where individuals may develop a high appreciation of the self in comparison to others. It also comprises a process of conservation in which individuals may feel the continuity of one's self-awareness or feel unchanged throughout time and space. Finally, identity formation process can contain a process through which individuals may feel that identity cannot be related only to past events, but also to the future possibilities through the seeking for an ideal image of the self.

The previously mentioned processes can be dynamic and continuous, and they are not age restricted since they may differ at the levels of importance at different ages. The sense of identity development is far from being linear since there can be changes associated with the different experiences during the individual's life.

In this study, identity is seen as a multidimensional system that is structured around different aspects of continuity, consistency, valuation, internal differentiation, external differentiation, assertiveness, originality and resilience (Orbe, 2008; Pope and Reynolds, 2017). Taking that into consideration, I believe that future research on identity must take into consideration all those aspects and processes, in addition to considering that people are living in a globalised, fast-changing multi-dimensional sociocultural world.

Camilleri and Malewska-Peyre (1997) suggest the theory of "identity strategies" to explain the evolution and the perception of multiple identities. They highlight the difference between a 'real identity' and a 'value identity'. For instance, a real identity is what individuals are like at any present time, which may include their personality traits, in some cases, it may include even the categorical attributes that can be related to the individuals' social roles and statuses. Some individuals may embody some of their beliefs that they value the most. These beliefs may come from the culture and the religion of the society in which the individual lives. This develops a new dimension of identity that can be called value identity. For Muslim women perhaps, in some cultural systems, *value* identity can be understood in relation to social roles expectations that may establish boundaries of values and behaviour, which in turn, can affect real identities. If value identities and real identities are diverse from each other, individuals may try to reduce the differences by negotiating their identities (Camilleri and Malewska-Peyre, 1997). In this present study, this can be clearly seen when sojourners engage in intercultural contact.

Negotiated experience is another concept with which identity correlates (Wenger, 1998). This research suggests that, during the different experiences in social life, people might experience several different identities and later they would choose among those previous identities, which can be a source of struggle (McKay and Wong, 1996; Pavlenko and Blackledge, 2006; Svensson et al., 2014; Edwards and Burns, 2016; Ting-Toomey, 2017). Building on the previously cited studies, I can argue that foreign language learners would experience identity negotiation not just when they learn a new language, but also when they live in a new cultural environment, which is different from their original one, before constructing the identity they prefer.

Identity classification is a socially negotiated process that is learned from a young age. Negotiation does not mean a contract or an agreement, but also it does not mean a conflict. According to Ting-Toomey (2015), Identity negotiation happens during any social interaction with our social environment outside and within ourselves. In other words, it is the way that an individual forms meaning within themselves during any interaction that they have within their environment while deducing things about other people who they are interacting with. Throughout this negotiation process and identity negotiation theory, groups are formed and different alliances are chosen based on the value content of the interlocutors.

3.2.2 Social identity theory

In the field of social psychology, identity is studied from the viewpoint of how individuals perceive the relationship between them, and a given social group. During the early 1970s, the notion of social identity was developed by Tajfel (1979) who defines it as a part of the individual's self-concept that is originated from the knowledge of a social group (or groups) membership and the emotional connotation accompanied to that membership. In this definition, group membership may contribute to individuals' self and world conception. In addition, some aspects of the perception of the relationship between the self and the physical and the social world are originated from the membership of particular social groups or class (ibid). According to social identity theory, socio-cultural identities are complex and can comprise of several components including ethnic group membership, social class identity and personal identities (Ting-Toomey, 2012). This theory has its roots in psychology, and it relies on experimentation to explain the relations between the group members from the group viewpoint. Moreover, it also analyses the group members' behaviour from the personal perspective of the group members.

Social identity theory has many advantages including its thoroughness and flexibility in scope, as it aims to examine a variety of both individual and collective reactions to intergroup relations. Secondly, the theory switches the attention of identity study from the objective perspective of the researcher to the personal experience of the individual. In other words, the social identity theory approaches identity as a functioning entity rather than passive.

The volume of research that has used Social Identity Theory is likely to encounter the occasional experimental rejection in revealing ambiguities that are related to the concepts used. This theory has two main limitations. First, social identity theory stresses on binary categorisation of in-group and out-group to provide a methodological comparability crosswise the wide range of identities to which people applied the theory. Second, the use of self-categorisation can be very limiting in the sense that it does not allow sufficient room for interpretation of one's identity in relation to others. In other words, it can be clearly seen that identity is constructed of the individuals' understanding of self as well as the mutual recognition of the individual in relation to the others (Joseph, 2016).

In this study, the notion of social identity is important in explaining the impact of knowledge derived from group membership in shaping the Algerian PhD students' identities and adjustment strategies when living in the UK. In other words, I will see the importance of home knowledge in affecting the individuals' attitudes, emotions and activities throughout their daily life in the UK. I believe that using the photo-elicitation interview method as a stimulant to talking about the experiences of Algerian doctoral students would reveal deeper information about their relationships with family members, friends from home, new friends, university colleagues, research fellows, and other people from the host culture. In fact, several research studies that investigate the immigrants' communities report that social support networks are a very important aspect in the development of the individual's personal and social identities (McLean, 2015; Schwartz et al., 2017; Ting-Toomey, 2017). According to Bronfenbrenner's Bioecological Systems Theory, aspects of the family are considered as proximal contexts, which directly influence children and their development (Bronfenbrenner, 1989). In this model, the family is placed in the microsystem, which indicates that the family has a direct influence on the individual's life through interaction. For instance, Birman and Taylor-Ritzler (2007) show that positive relationships in the family are usually associated with reduced anxiety among immigrant adolescents. Similarly, Newland (2014) introduced a model of family well-being that focuses on different factors that can impact parents and children suggesting that there is a

strong link between parents' well-being and child well-being. Family can be considered as a source of support and encouragement for individuals, but sometimes, family involvement may hinder them from engaging in different experiences and activities because of negative contextual conditions (Belsky and Pluess, 2009).

As mentioned earlier, the social identity theory proposed by Tajfel and Turner (1979) suggests that an individual possesses multiple selves that can be stimulated in certain situations. These different identities can be coherent, fragmented, and sometimes conflicting (Ryan and Irie, 2014). Many investigations including Norton (2000); Hemmi (2014); have proven that language learners exhibit a complex multidimensional identities. In the context of this study, Algerian Doctoral students may exhibit several identities such as international student, PhD, Muslim and so on, as they interact with different people in different social and academic contexts.

3.2.3 Cultural identity

Culture and self-identity are two major forces that are co-constructed and are in a continuous state of development and negotiation, which can influence individuals' sense of self (Hall, 2014; Ting-Toomey, 2017). These two concepts are hard to define because of their complexity (Morris-Suzuki, 2015). For instance, it is hard to tell where one culture ends, and another culture begins. Consequently, this study does not aim to define clear boundaries between cultures and identity formation processes, but preferably to explore the central aspects of the experience of sojourning transition for Algerian PhD students and its effects on their own identity.

The following sections present important dimensions of cultural identity in its basic format in association with relevant research and theories. For example, some of the aspects that may contribute to the formation of cultural identity are languages, self-concepts, national identity, religious morality and gender structures.

3.2.3.1 Language

Language is an essential element of culture and self-identity. In the Algerian multilingual context, the official language used in the country is standard Arabic, which is taught at school and it is the language used for most official documents. Algerian Arabic is different from the standard Arabic spoken in different parts of the world since it comprises many borrowed words

from other languages such as Berber, French and Turkish. Arabic has been the official language of Algeria since independence and, recently, Tamazight, a native language from North Africa, became a national language since it is used by almost 25% of the Algerian population. French is still often taught at school and widely used in higher education and within government administrations. The use of English for Algerians has been dramatically increasing since the 1990s (Belmihoub, 2018).

The special relationship between language and culture was accentuated since the last half of the 20th century by Wolf (1956) and Sapir (1979) who proposed a theory promoting that verbal codes can influence thought systems (Boroditsky, 2011). Therefore, to speak a language may not be just a way of communication, but it is a complex system that can connect the individual to different cultures. Language can join members of different communities together through communication using a common language and it can cause alienation to others who cannot use the target language (Kinging, 2015). For instance, student sojourners in the UK may feel the need to speak English in most of the domains in society as a way of feeling more integrated. However, when being amongst other members from the home culture, using the mother tongue in communication can be a way of feeling like a part of a national group, which can also be considered as a source of social support.

Identity has various meanings in the literature, but these definitions share the notion of identity as a relational phenomenon. Miller et al. (2009) assert that in the field of English language teaching (ELT), many contemporary researchers have defined identity as a process of continual emerging and becoming. Norton and Toohey (2011) consider identity as the understanding of the relationship between people to the world, the way that relationship is developed across time and space and the way people perceive the future. Additionally, in Varghese et al's. (2005) definition of identity, they describe it as a process of transformation that changes in different contexts, and that is created and negotiated through language and discourse. In line with this definition, identity can be context-bound in the sense that it is related to social, cultural and political contexts in the sense that people can create multiple identities in accordance with the discourses and contexts they take part in through membership, context and language use (Kumar et al., 2015; Swann and Bosson, 2016; Ting Toomey, 2017).

Although learner's identity is a relatively new focus in the field of language learning (Block, 2014), many researchers assume that the study of identity and language learning has become

one of the busiest research areas in the field of applied linguistics (Dörnyei and Ushioda, 2009; Auer, 2016; Norton, 2013; Cook, 2016; Toohey, 2018). Numerous studies confirm that the development of identity is an ongoing process that takes place in inter-subjective fields. For instance, the individual's identity can be adaptable in the sense that it focuses on some features of the immediate context to provide a meaningful explanation (Oyserman et al., 2012). More specifically, identities can be closely assimilated to knowledge and use of a foreign language (Korhonen, 2014). In addition, language learners' identities cannot be unified or fixed, considering that they are constantly changing and continually reconstructed (Burke, 2006; Norton, 2016; Jackson, 2016).

Moreover, Schmitt et al., (2010) emphasise the importance of identity as a social factor that might be associated with linguistic patterns that may be related to social and personal aspects of identity, in addition to raising peoples' awareness of their multiple identities when using different languages. Post-structuralism approach of language-learning regards language as the basis on which the identity is constructed (Bucholtz and Hall, 2004; Norton and Toohey, 2011, Kinginger, 2013). This approach challenges notions that present language learners' identity as resistant to change and stagnated in the original culture (Pennycook, 2017). For example, identity was understood as a stable and rigid entity, which controls one's actions and perceptions of the world (Marx, 2002), while in fact, language learners may establish new identities and simultaneously maintain their old ones. In other words, considering that identity is socially constructed, dynamic and constantly changing over time and space, language learners may possess multiple identities that are changing and flexible, in the sense that they can be members of different ethnic and social groups at the same time (Early and Norton, 2012; Josselson and Harway, 2012; Block, 2015).

Recently, there has been a debate in the USA between Norton, Pavlenko and Block on the one hand and Kramsch and others on the other hand. There is this talk that identity is associated with the fight for civil rights and for social justice. Norton (2000) talks about identity as the consciousness and the awareness of self that will give individuals a voice in the public sphere; it will give them a social-political identity with which they are going to be able to claim rights, privileges and entitlements in a democratic society. In her work, she interviewed new immigrants coming to Canada. Pavlenko (2005) talks about immigrants coming to industrialised societies and the processes of deconstructing and reinventing themselves to become good Americans and having access to the American dream. Block (2014) argues that

foreign language learners, such as Erasmus students, even after one year abroad cannot possibly be the kind of lasting identity work that is required to develop a kind of intercultural personality. His use of the term ‘work’ may imply that identity construction is heavy duty. He also minimises the impact of studying abroad on the students’ identities.

Norton explains that identity is not just psychological self-awareness, but it can also be political consciousness. Similarly, Kramsch (2009) argues that foreign language learners should acquire political consciousness and she links that to the concept of subjectivity. Pavlenko (2005) in her research argues that the experiences of immigrants coming to industrialised societies who must learn the English language to have access to the different daily life needs differ from north-Americans who learn a foreign language in the classroom environment. She concludes that learning the language while living in a foreign country necessitates deconstructing and reconstructing identities.

Pavlenko (2005) uses economic vocabulary such as the terms ‘accessing resources’ which is maybe less appropriate for foreign language learners, however she emphasises the importance of contexts in the learning process that may affect the development of identities. Block (2014), on the other hand, explains that foreign language learners can even achieve third place subject positions in the target language. Moreover, Kramsch (2009) notes that subject positions refer to how people represent themselves, psychologically, socially and culturally using languages.

3.2.3.2 Religion

Religion is another aspect of cultural identity, which may influence the sojourners' experiences. The relationship between religion and identity formation was emphasised by many studies, which argue that the definition of one’s self may shift when religious affiliations change (Thumma, 1991; Peek, 2005). Some researchers discuss the way in which individuals practise religious activities on a daily basis may have an impact on individuals’ psychological functioning (Schwartz and Huismans, 1995; Ysseldyk et al., 2010; Saroglou, 2011; Horowitz, 2013). When living abroad in a different country with a different culture, people may explore different perspectives concerning how do they see themselves and how others see them. For instance, religion is integrated into almost all aspects of life for a Muslim (food, marriage, social relationships etc.), so it is assumed that Algerians would focus significantly on religious contexts during their acculturative experiences, and that may force them to negotiate their identity when interacting with people who are different from them.

The belief system deep-rooted in any religion can explain the different reasons why some individuals have a stronger feeling of belonging to their religious group. Religion is a system of beliefs and guidance that can provide meaning about individuals and the world around them. For example, religious systems provide and shape the meanings of different belief systems, which include beliefs about sex and gender (Nynäs, 2016); personality and emotions (Robinson and Kirkeby, 2005; Paloutzian, 2016); and even political ideology (Jost et al., 2008; Mitchell, 2017; Lee, 2018). Furthermore, even national identity is viewed as an ongoing process that is reconstructed daily, for example, through the exposure to significant historical events (Gutierrez, 2017).

As suggested in the social identity theory proposed by Tajfel and Turner (1979), there is a strong relationship between individuals and social groups with which they are affiliated. Religion or ethnicity can be included within the complex social system as they can affect people's psychological and social states. For instance, individuals who associate themselves with a given ethnic group may gain a sense of individual and collective self from that membership, since they share several common beliefs and consider their religious membership as essential to their identity formation (Beyer et al, 2018).

3.2.3.3 Social Relationships

Social relationships, which encompass family relationships, can affect the acculturation process in many ways. Many studies were conducted to explore the importance of these relationships when living abroad (Birman 2006; Chen et al. 2015; Oppedal and Idsoe, 2015; Cano et al., 2016). Findings suggest that the positive relationship in the family may reduce levels of stress and anxiety between immigrants and/or sojourners.

Family can be an ongoing source of help and support for sojourners, but too much involvement may result in restraining their child from engaging in all the experiences that may help in developing their cultural learning and awareness. Kinship relations between people are considered to be stronger than any other relations and can influence peoples' identity development (Martin and Nakayama, 2013; Samovar et al., 2014). Algerians' identity appears to be influenced by many aspects including cultural attitudes, religion and family membership. Breaking the cultural and religious norms by making independent choices may entail negative consequences for Algerians, who may be socially alienated in their own culture. Therefore,

feeling accepted and supported by their family and home society are variables worth considering for student sojourners who will return to live in their home country.

3.2.3.4 Gender structures

Gender also can influence the student sojourners' experiences and their process of acculturation (Chereni, 2014; Anderson and Lawton, 2015). Women appear to experience more difficulties regarding intercultural relationships (Chaudhry et al., 2011). The criteria for successful acculturation can vary from one person to another depending on their goals after the sojourn. For some groups, successfully adapting to the host culture means a successful sojourning, for others may perceive it as negative since the initial aim of the sojourn is not to change their culture or identity, but for educational purposes.

As stated earlier in this chapter, Camilleri and Malewska-Peyre (1997) introduced a theory that explains the different strategies of identities development; they highlighted the difference between real identities and value identities. 'Value identity' is what an individual believes as an ideal self that she/he would like to achieve and 'real identity' is what an individual is like at the present moment. Value identity can be defined, for example, in terms of social role expectations, which define characteristics of what are the appropriate values and behaviours in a given setting and what are not, which can influence the persons' real identity. Student sojourners may experience this situation when they engage in intercultural relationships in which their value identity is different from their real one, they tend to try to reduce the difference.

3.2.3.5 Self and other

Creating territories may establish boundaries that can unify and separate space including everything within that space. The notions of 'us' and 'them' is the result of in-group biases that can be created when merging some groups of people and resources and separating them from other groups and resources (Durkheim, 2014). For example, over the second half of the 20th century, many then colonised nations gained their independence from their colonial rulers. Colonialism has a clear and persistent legacy, and post-colonialism is an umbrella term that could be used to describe a set of theory and practices, which seek to explore the legacy of colonialism in the present day.

As for the focus of this study, I am only going to be largely focusing on understanding the various influences of cultural legacy of colonialism, and some of the ideas and theories that have come to be used to explore the cultural legacy of colonialism in the present day that may affect the Algerian PhD students identity development.

Claiming a single theorist or single book as being the originator of the entire field is an oversimplification of the truth. However, Edward Said 1978 book "Orientalism" can lay claim to popularising some of the key ideas, which now sit as the foundation of post-colonial theory. Within it, Said argues that

Ideas, cultures, and histories cannot seriously be understood or studied without their force or precisely their configurations of power also being studied.

(Said, 1978. p.12)

Because of many years of colonial rule, "the West", a term that is largely used to refer to nations that were not colonised, has had more power in dictating global culture than "the East", a term that usually used to describe nations which were colonised. Said suggests that "the West" limited "the East's" ability to represent and to define itself. Instead, "the West" came to define "the East" in a manner that is useful for its own terms.

In Said's words:

The imaginative examination of things Oriental was based, more or less exclusively upon a sovereign western consciousness out of whose unchallenged centrality an oriental world emerged

(Said, 1978. p.14)

The central argument of Said (1978) is that in a global culture dominated by "the West", "the East" is usually represented as being different, mysterious and illogical. In contrast, "the West" is often represented as logical and cultured or as "the norm". Another key Scholar in the development of the post-colonial theory, Spivak (1988) argues that the result of this process was to "*constitute the colonial subject as other*" (p.76).

There two main ideas that are represented in the foundation of post-colonial theory. The first is the ideas of "the West" and "the East" or "the non-West" are complete fabrications as Hall (1995) argues that they are much of an idea, as they are a fact of geography. The second idea is that it points to the specific manner in which this forced binary has being used to portray the west as being "the Norm", whereas cultures from other places are defined as being strange and "other".

Under colonialism, many colonised nations were forced to take the language of their coloniser as the official language using it for education and law. Talking about power dynamics between the cultures using terminology such as "the West" and "the East" suggests that the coloniser culture is somehow superior to that of the colonised nation. For example, during the French colonial subjugation of Algeria, the French culture was promoted as superior, whereas the native cultures of Algeria were perceived as inferior through the use of binary oppositions system that supports hierarchical relations of authority. However, as proposed by Bhabha (1994), culture is not about fixed essences, but it is about the ever-changing processes. In his theory of "cultural hybridity", he suggests that colonialism can be perceived as a mixing up of cultures of that of the coloniser and that of the indigenous people, which results in a mixed identity that can affect the individual identity and the communal identity in colonised nations. Therefore, the notion of a superior French culture in the colonial discourse in Algeria that describe colonialism as a civilisation mission cannot be accepted since there are no inherent essences of superior or inferior cultures, and the cultural justification to colonialism does not work and colonialism is revealed as an exploitation of other people's lands and resources through brute force.

In the study abroad context, Algerian PhD students in the UK are exposed to a new culture, which is different from what they have experienced before. Their experiences can be challenging and complex since they need to learn to adapt to new roles, such as being international students or PhD candidates, in the new cultural and educational systems. During their time abroad, they learn about other cultures, different from their own, by interacting with new people from other countries, a situation where they can learn about their own culture and identity (Drexler and Campbell, 2011).

3.2.4 Academic identity

Academic identity can be viewed as the identification of oneself as an academic, or can be related to feelings of belonging to academic communities. Doctoral academic activities may vary in their degree of formality. For instance, formal experiences such as working on elements of the PhD like data collection and analysis; semi-formal experiences such as meetings with the supervisory team or attending workshops and conferences; informal activities such as meetings and discussions with doctoral peers and colleagues (McAlpine et al., 2009). Engaging in academic activities determines the development of individuals' academic identity (Starke-Meyerring, 2011).

Identity development is a process that lies at the centre of doctoral experience starting from being PhD students to becoming doctors. In the context of this study, this development process of Algerian PhD students in the UK can be affected by other individuals, events, and cultures that can support, or hinder, their identity as academics and researchers.

In this research the notion of academic identity is important to understand the Algerian PhD students' experiences within the academic environments in the UK and how these experiences would shape their views about their identity development. For instance, doctoral students were usually understood through socialisation point of view; however, some studies view doctoral students' development in just in the professional context (e.g. Coldbeck, 2008). Literature about undergraduate students shows that they are growing cognitively, developing personal, interpersonal, moral and professional skills (Steinfeld et al., 2008; Maunder et al., 2013), while doctoral students development is generally seen as preparation to professional life (Gardner, 2010). However, doctoral students show signs of development and growth during their experiences in academia (Gardner, 2009). The identity development process can be framed in relation to individuals' understanding of oneself identity, roles and performance, and perceptions of others from a particular community (Tonso, 2006). Academic identity, therefore, can be viewed as the identification of oneself as an academic or can be related to feelings of belonging to academic communities. Nevertheless, PhD students may experience tensions and conflicts between the different values in a novel academic context or a different environment, which may affect the student's academic performance and motivation.

Studying at a doctoral level, Algerian students may get involved in different activities and interact with people within their university premises that can affect the way they see themselves.

The literature about the doctoral students shows that most of them feel a sense of agency and pride when they engage with academic activities such as doctoral meetings, research projects, and even when talking about future academic roles (McAlpine et al., 2013). The identity development process can be framed in relation to individuals' understanding of oneself identity, roles and performance, and perceptions of others from a particular community (Tonso, 2006). Upon beginning a doctoral program, students may interact with multiple academic cultures within the practices of scholarly communities, and begin to undertake a number of identity changes (Foot et al., 2014). PhD students strive to adjust to the new cultures and communities by developing new identities such as a doctoral student and /or a member of academia (Baker and Pifer, 2011). For example, during their time as PhD students, Algerian students may interact with others when engaging in tasks related to different academic cultures. As a result, they can develop new roles and identities within that culture by negotiating contexts such as the institution, fields of study, relationship with supervisors and other staff within their departments (Holley, 2011).

Nowadays, learning to do research and to become independent researchers is an important aspect of a doctoral degree (Dowling et al., 2012). Doctoral degrees are usually known as a learning process that offers deep learning experiences (Baker and Lattuca, 2010). The process of becoming a researcher includes interacting with other individuals from the academic context and beyond (Hopwood, 2010). There are many studies, which focus on the academic identity development of early academic researchers after finishing their PhD degree.

Interactions with others are fundamental at any level of a doctoral journey since they can provide PhD students with a chance to reflect on their experiences with their social networks. For instance, Algerian doctoral students can reflect on the way they interact with different networks and determine the ways that might influence their identity development (Foot et al, 2014). Studies on doctoral students' socialisation highlight the importance of interaction and collaboration between peers and other doctoral students from other disciplines (Taylor and Coia, 2009). For instance, Algerian PhD students can understand the experience of transitioning into new roles and can provide social support to one another through positive and constant interactions within the academic establishment (Lindvig, 2018).

International doctoral students

Universities in the UK are globalised institutions where international students engage with others in intercultural interactions. Understanding the Algerian doctoral students' experiences of development must be related to the broader intercultural context (Pennycook, 2005). Identities are developed and negotiated during interactions within intercultural contexts, which may include negotiations of language, power and cultures (Pavlenko and Norton, 2007). Therefore, it is crucial to understand the students' backgrounds, history, and future aspirations (Norton, 2014).

Doctoral students usually emphasise social support and interaction with other researchers as being important in their doctoral experience (Basturkmen et al., 2012). However, international PhD students may experience some challenges related to the negotiation of power dynamics when interacting with academics from the UK or other staff from the establishments in which they are enrolled (Fotovatian and Miller, 2014). For instance, Algerian doctoral students can face high stress and uncertainty, in addition to other challenges such as adapting to new academic environments and cultures during their doctoral studies in the UK. Academic cultures can be different from one institution to another and international PhD students may face the pressure of adjusting to the institution's environment and culture. Interacting with people within powerful academic and social networks can help Algerian PhD students in building durable relationships, resources and networks within those institutions (Norton, 2005).

In sum, identity development during the process of doctoral study is a continuous learning experience that includes a great deal of transformation in different aspects of identity. Becoming a doctor of philosophy does not happen in social isolation and that can be affected by different aspects such as living in different cultural environments, interacting with different social networks, and adapting new practices.

3.2.5 Identity and intercultural communication

Since the post-structuralism view of the world has emerged, it has become influential in the social sciences (Block, 2015). Recent social theories, including the publications from Giddens (1991), Bauman (2013), Lemert and Elliott (2009), and Triandis (2018) promote new trends towards individualisation, reflexive self-identity and new individualism. This approach came about as a response to previous approaches that, generally, take biology or social structure as a principle of identity.

A social-structuralism approach to identity involves the search for universal laws of human behaviour. This approach originated in the psychology of Durkheim and Wolff (1964) and developed through functionalism and anthropology (Talcott, 2013). The social-structuralism approach considers cultural identity as a fixed, unified, unchangeable entity and views people as homogeneous groups. Delanty (2003) asserts that the modern understanding of self is that of social self in which identity is seen as a socially-constructed product that is shaped by the culture where individuals are influenced by their association in social categories established the social class, gender, ethnicity, education, family and many other variables.

Recently, the essentialist view of identity has been questioned by post-structural theorists. Here, the term post-structuralism is used as an umbrella term to all that surpasses structuralism via the search for multi-levelled and complicated framing of the world. Smart (1998) notes that poststructuralist researchers became concerned with several issues, namely the crisis of representation related to the fluctuation of meaning, the shortage of assured groundwork for knowledge, and the analytic significance of language, discourse and text. The poststructuralist approach to identity in relation to language socialisation and language learning has been growing increasingly in conceptualising identity in applied linguistics.

Many researchers have adopted the poststructuralist approach to identity either completely or partly. This can be clearly seen in the publications of, for instance, Norton (2013) who focused on studying the relationship between language learning and identity in the case of immigrant women in Canada; Pavlenko and Blackledge (2004); Block (2006) who focuses on the negotiation of identities in different language, cultural and political contexts. In addition, Block (2014) explains the social scientists' focus on identity as a bridge between the micro level of the individual and the macro level of the social system. In addition, Block (ibid) explains the shift to viewing identity as fluid, socially constructed and multidimensional (including age, gender, class, ethnicity culture and many others). Further, social constructionist and poststructuralist models have allowed language and identity researchers to investigate how different aspects of identity inter-animate and how participants adapt, emphasise and discard particular identity properties (Lytra, 2016).

3.2.5.1 Intercultural communication

Communication can be defined as a dynamic process that involves interactive and symbolic elements. For understanding intercultural communication, Kim and Gudykunst (2005) use the

term 'stranger' to refer to the most unfamiliar people. A stranger has limited knowledge of their new environment, culture, values and norms. Generally, communicating with other people involves predicting their responses. Kim and Gudykunst (2009) identify three levels of communicative prediction. First, the cultural level, which involves data about culture, norms and values of the others. Therefore, a better understanding of the people's cultures grants better prediction. Second, the sociocultural level that includes information about other people's group membership. This is the most important data most relevant to intercultural communication. At the third level comes the psycho-cultural knowledge. It is related to the individual's characteristics and it is used when communicating with friends, for example. I believe that the more Algerian PhD students are aware of their own communication behaviours, the more effective they will be in intercultural communication during their sojourn in the UK.

Some researchers distinguish between the two terms, intercultural and cross-cultural, based on how they define culture. These two terms are using different modifying adjectives that overlap in their meanings. This overlap causes a lot of confusion mainly because the two terms are closely related. On the one hand, in the context of foreign language teaching, the cross-cultural approach seeks to understand the other on the other side of the border by learning his/her national language (Kramsch and Widdowson, 1998). By this definition, she understands the term cross-cultural as a meeting of two cultures across the political boundaries of nation-states. On the other hand, intercultural may also refer to communication between people from different ethnic, gendered, social cultures, within the same nation. Another approach to differentiating these two concepts is taken from the field of language education. Fries (2009) highlights that the term cross-cultural applies to something that covers more than one culture and implies a comparison of chosen aspects of the given cultures, whereas intercultural involves an interaction of the two cultures.

A third approach to describe these terms is brought by Gudykunst (2003) in which he suggests that cross-cultural communication involves a comparison of communication across cultures, whereas intercultural communication involves communication between people from different cultures. He implies that cross-cultural studies are a subfield of intercultural studies. There are, however, two important aspects on which cross-cultural communication and intercultural communication can be differentiated. The first one is related to the focus of study, which in the case of intercultural communication is the interaction between cultures, whereas in the case of cross-cultural communication it is the comparison of cultures. The second aspect is related to

how culture is defined. For example, in the case of intercultural communication there is a broader view of culture, whereas, in the case of cross-cultural communication, there are well-defined boundaries of the given culture.

3.2.5.2 Language and Intercultural communication

Intercultural communication is not confined to one academic subject area. The term *intercultural* refers to the concept of between cultures (Spencer-Oatey and Franklin, 2009). Interculturality can be seen as a co-constructed phenomenon for situations that are created in the process of communication blending cultural norms from previous experience of interlocutors (Kecskes, 2012). The growing need for intercultural communication can be traced to the mid-1940s after the end of the Second World War. During that period, a large number of Americans, such as government officials, diplomats and business leaders, were assigned to work in several newly independent and developing countries (Rogers and Hart, 2002; Kumaravadivelu, 2008). Their lack of knowledge of foreign cultures and communication styles impeded the efficacy of communication of the Foreign Service Institute (FSI), which began offering the officials programmes with the aim of developing their intercultural communication competence. The institute hired a team of anthropologists and linguists to develop methods and materials that can be used to improve intercultural communication. Edward Hall and George Trager were among the scholars the institute hired. The work of Hall and Trager (1953) introduces a hypothesis and a methodology for analysing different cultural systems. They established a framework for mapping cultures by highlighting many dimensions including communication, which is considered as one of the most important dimensions in their model, with an aim to facilitate communication between cultures.

3.2.5.3 Communicative competence and intercultural communication

The concept of *communicative competence*, developed by Hymes (1972), moved the emphasis of linguists from the study of language as a system in isolation towards the study of language as communication in contexts. Hymes defines communicative competence as the knowledge and the grasp of social rules needed to interpret messages in order to participate in a speech community. The concept has been gradually developed by Canale and Swain (1980) as comprising of sub-competencies such as grammatical competence, discourse competence, sociolinguistic competence, and strategic competence. They see that grammatical competence is associated with the mastery of linguistic codes of language while discourse competence links

meaning with spoken or written texts in various genres. In addition, they consider sociolinguistic competence as the understanding of appropriate utterances within the context in which they are articulated, whereas strategic competence applies to the verbal or non-verbal strategies that communicators adopt to initiate, maintain, terminate, repair and redirect communication. Therefore, knowledge of linguistic forms, meanings and functions are all required to successfully and effectively accomplish the purposes of communication (Savignon, 2017).

Arguments against communicative competence

Canale and Swain's (1981) model seems not to address interaction among people, but it focuses much on the individual speaker and the mastery of the four dimensions of the communicative competence. Moreover, this model seems that it does not address the need to develop observational skills or strategies, which might be of great importance in intercultural learning. Additionally, it appears to overlook the ability to understand one's own and others' attitudes towards different groups and different ways of speaking and how such attitudes affect communication and relationships.

Van Ek (1986) has contributed to the elaboration of the concept by emphasising that foreign language teaching is not just concerned with training in communication skills, but also with the personal and social development of the learner as an individual. Byram (1998) summarises Van Ek's definition of the six competencies as follows:

- 1) *Linguistic competence*: “the ability to produce and interpret” meaning formed in agreement “with the rules of the language concerned”
- 2) *Sociolinguistic competence*: “the awareness” that our “choice of language forms” is determined “by setting, a relationship between interlocutors, communicative intention, etc.”
- 3) *Discourse competence*: “the ability to use appropriate strategies” to construct and interpret texts
- 4) *Strategic competence*: “communication strategies”, such as rephrasing “to get our meaning across”
- 5) *Social competence*: familiarity with differences in social customs, empathy and motivation to communicate with others

- 6) *Sociocultural competence*: the ability to function in several cultures, which supposes some familiarity with the sociocultural context in which a language is situated (p. 10).

The model of Van Ek (1986) is similar to Canale and Swain's (1981), but it comprises two additional perspectives, *sociocultural* and *social competence*, which focus on values and beliefs, on one side, and attitudes and behaviours, on the other. I believe that these two aspects are important in explaining some of the experiences and adjustment strategies for Algerian PhD students in the UK.

Social interactions for individuals who live abroad are so complex since they require a combination of cognitive abilities, awareness of personal and cultural beliefs related to interpersonal relationships, which may promote autonomy and develop their social responsibility (Van Ek, 1986). Social competence for Algerian PhD students in the UK would refer to adjusting to new social contexts in the UK by interacting with different people in the host country, forming and maintaining close relationships with them. The sociocultural competence might be referred to as the pragmatic knowledge used by speakers to communicate and understand the social and cultural contexts (Celce-Murcia, 2008). From a sociocultural perspective, Algerian PhD students using English for communication can influence their identity and self-images when confronted with different social, linguistic and cultural encounters during their sojourn (McLean and Thorne, 2006).

Critiques of Van Ek's model

In the definition of sociocultural competence provided by Van Ek, he assumes that language learners should learn the language spoken by native speakers and implies that there is only one native context (Byram and Zarate, 1997). In general, the communicative competence model was questioned by Alptekin (2002) in which he asserts that this model employs standardised native speaker norms, therefore, it is found to be utopian, unrealistic and constraining. Byram (1998) criticises Hymes's emphasis on sociolinguistic competence on the basis that it is misleading to suggest that language learners should model themselves on native speakers; this, he stresses, ignores the importance of learners' social identities and cultural competence' in cross-cultural interactions.

On the basis of Alptekin's criticism, it can be noted that this model is inadequate for foreign language learners in intercultural contexts. Accordingly, he suggests that intercultural

communicative *competence* must be developed by providing the learners with both linguistic and cultural behaviours and awareness of differences and the strategies for managing these differences. Byram (2001) stresses the importance of developing learners as intercultural speakers who have the “ability to interact and to accept other perspectives and perceptions of the world, to mediate between different perspectives, to be conscious of their evaluations and differences” (p. 5).

3.2.5.4 Intercultural communicative competence in foreign language learning

In the present day, English is the language that connects us. For foreign language learners, learning about the language is not enough; they need to develop an understanding about cultures and how to navigate between them. Previous models of communicative competence focus more on the code itself grammatical competence, sociolinguistic competence discourse competence and strategic competence (Canale, 1981). Even though culture is included in the sociocultural competence in terms of its relation to language, it is not explicitly addressed. This model focusses more on the individual speakers and the individual’s mastery of the four dimensions of communicative competence; it does not address interaction across different cultures. Focussing on the individual also, communicative competence does not address the need to develop strategies and skills for intercultural learning to develop one’s ability to understand different attitudes towards different cultures, and how such attitudes might affect relationships and communication. It also does not address the need to develop intercultural understanding in relation to issues such as ethics and power.

In this section, I am going to go through three ways of looking into intercultural communicative competence. The first one is from Baker (2012) in which he addresses the focus on the language and knowing meaning, roles and relationships to the idea of using linguistic and communicative resources to negotiate meaning, roles and relationships. In other words, he shifts the focus from the code itself to social interaction and also negotiation and adjustment among speakers. He also emphasises on the point about negotiation and mediation because, for example, Algerian PhD students in the UK will interact with others who speak a range of varieties of English. Another key scholar in the field of intercultural communicative competence is Byram (1998) who believes that intercultural competence requires different aspects namely attitudes, knowledge, skills of interpreting and relating, skills of discovery and interaction, critical cultural awareness and political education.

He indicates that attitudes incorporate the willingness to interact in relationships of social and political equality stating that political refers to any form of power such as linguistic, social and economic. Attitudes address the willingness to analyse the individual's own linguistic and cultural frames of reference and to discover those of others. For developing their intercultural communicative competence, I think that the knowledge of Algerian PhD students in the UK must include and go beyond linguistic and sociolinguistic knowledge to include knowledge of relationships between the cultures in contact. Knowledge also goes beyond strategic competence to repair miscommunication to an understanding of the different types and causes of them.

The skills that Byram (1998) suggests need to be developed also go beyond the linguistic and sociolinguistic skills to ways of identifying and understanding ethnocentrism misunderstanding and dysfunction, skills for mediating conflict and interpretations, skills of knowing how to acquire new linguistic and cultural knowledge. To develop good intercultural communicative competence, I believe that Algerian PhD students in the UK need to master not just the "*know what*" of communicative competence, but also the "*know-how*" of intercultural communicative competence. Critical awareness emphasises the intercultural communicative competence is valued and intercultural exchanges often require negotiation and acceptance of different practices and different values. I believe that Algerian PhD students would experience many changes due to the negotiation process, and that may appear at the level of their identity, which may result in the development of new hybrid identity in the UK.

The last one that I am going to address is Slimbach (2005) who emphasises a lot of the same points as Byram (1998) like communicative competence includes language proficiency but he emphasises that intercultural communicative competence requires understanding and acknowledging the different perspectives and the source of cultural assumptions. He also discusses ethnographic skills like Byram (1998) emphasising that to be culturally competent, people need to have the skills to observe the practices of others and understand these practices. He brings in global awareness the need to understand the conditions systems, ideologies and institutions affecting peoples' lives and choices. Finally, Slimbach, (2005) focusses more than the others on the affective development, which he describes it as the ability to express personal qualities and principles such as empathy, inquisitiveness, initiative, flexibility, humility, sincerity, gentleness, justice and joy within intercultural contexts.

3.3 Mobility, acculturation and adjustment

Nowadays, the process of internationalisation of higher education institutions seems to be unstoppable. Higher education institutions are engaged in a network system and they are associated with both the local and global levels in terms of finance, policy-making, global links and mobility (Marginson, 2013). Steadily, global mobility and new technology are making the world move towards being a “world society” where information, ideas and people are shifting between different institutions around the globe.

3.3.1 Internationalisation of higher education and student mobility

Internationalisation in higher education can be defined as a process that incorporates international, intercultural, or global dimensions into the purpose, function, or provision of higher education (Knight, 2004). I agree that this definition may be broad and vague, yet it still expresses the existence of many motives of internationalisation and the complexity of the term itself that can be understood in different ways. Although the UK government considers international students as fundamental in the higher education sector, many research papers on internationalisation of higher education show a great focus on the political and economic rationales from both international and institutional viewpoints, but only a partial attention is given to students and/ or staff (Jones and De Wit, 2012).

In the last decade, there have been major developments that affected many different education systems at the global level. For instance, at the secondary school level, a performance indicator of the school level named the Programme of International Student Assessment (PISA) has become principal in many parts of the world (Hopfenbeck et al., 2017). Many countries are interested in increasing their PISA ranking by implementing programmes that highlight science and mathematics development. In nations like Finland, China and Korea there are intense international programmes, which need support from nations that are highly ranked at the level of policy-making (Marginson, 2016).

Another reason is the rapid growth of online courses provided by for-profit corporations at Stanford, MIT and Harvard universities (Marginson, 2016). For instance, the Massive Open Online Course (MOOC) offers a variety of programmes from well-known universities presented by world experts. The students enrolled in this programme are assessed via multiple choice online exams. Even though, only a few students complete the programme successfully

and receive a certificate, these kind of programmes are reported to be desirable substitutes for being free of tuition and certified from global brand universities. Both the ranking system and the (MOOC) show the western dominance of higher education that attracts students from all over the world, but the rising higher education and science powers in East Asia are represented by China, Hong Kong, Taiwan, Korea and Japan, is another reason that affects internationalisation and students' mobility (Hawkins et al., 2018). In the coming years, it is estimated that East Asian countries will radically transform western dominance on the flow of information and generate most of the world's knowledge. For instance, a comparison between China and the US shows that the number of published papers in China is half of the amount in the United States and it is increasing by almost 17% every year (Marginson, 2013; Tran et al., 2016). In addition, China is one of the greatest countries in the fields of engineering and chemistry by producing world-class research papers that are classified among the most cited works (Tian and Liu, 2018). Similarly, Japan, Singapore, Korea and Taiwan are escalating quickly (Hazelkorn, 2015; Tan et al., 2016; Marginson, 2018).

Research on international students' mobility has attracted a number of researchers who look at trends in global higher education and discusses trends in academic research across several countries (Altbach, 2003; Knight, 2015). Moreover, many studies looked at migration and the globalisation of tertiary education and international student mobility, but fewer studies consider the experiences of international Muslim students and their motivations to leave their homeland to study in English speaking countries.

There are opposing views about the students' mobility around the world. From one side, many researchers believe that students continue their studies overseas in response to the scarcity in educational training at their home countries (Brooks and Waters, 2011). This idea ruled the development of thinking during the post-colonial era in Africa, Latin America and Asia. Many researchers argued that, at that time, there was a shortage of scientists, engineers and managers in higher education institutions that required training abroad. To cover this deficiency, many agencies, private institutions and non-governmental organisations supplied scholarships programmes during the 1960s and the 1970s to send thousands of students to North America and Western Europe. Developing countries, on the other hand, have fewer institutions of higher education, which encourages students to go abroad to continue their education (Murray Brux and Fry, 2010).

From another side, students' migration can be associated with migration for employment that would provide them with better economic opportunities and higher incomes (Rosenzweig, 2008; Chiswick and Miller, 2010; Beine et al., 2014). Based on this argument, the reason behind student migration could be having a better opportunity in staying abroad because of the high rates of non-employability, low salaries and poverty in students' original countries.

There are several studies on the students' influx to industrialised countries that found different reasons from the previously mentioned ones. For example, Beine, et al., (2012) found that students' number is positively correlated with the number of immigrants from students' origin countries. To put it differently, the more immigrants from the students' origin country in the host country, the more likely the students will choose that country to complete their studies. They also found that students were willing to pay higher tuition fees to study in countries they perceive as having higher education quality; a conclusion that was confirmed by Caruso and De Wit (2010) who found that countries with higher expenditures per student attracted more students. Another reason suggested by Van Bouwel and Veugelers (2013) is the quality of education in the host countries. In their research, they focused on 31 European origin and destination countries and found that undergraduate students were attracted to countries that are perceived to have prestigious higher tertiary institutions.

With progressively globalised economies, cultural communities' mobility and knowledge distribution via higher education institutions, research on the intercultural experiences of international students has become more and more important. According to Gu and Schweisfurth (2015), there was a considerable increase in the number of the students studying overseas during the period between the late twentieth and early twenty-first centuries, which led to the rapid internationalisation of higher education institutions in several parts of the world. In addition, some universities from developed countries are considered to be world class universities, which have high international status (Hazelkorn, 2015; Van Der Wende, 2015).

In the world of higher education, internationalisation of education would refer to students' mobility, staff mobility, internationalisation of research, language policies, internationalisation at home and internationalisation of the curriculum (Leask, 2015). I think that internationalisation directly contributes to the core mission of universities in two fundamental ways. First, students who are graduating today and joining the labour force will be working in companies that are multinational. Therefore, graduates would need to be internationally mobile

across countries to have successful careers. Fresh graduates would also need to develop a world view and to appreciate difference between cultures, languages and religions and to be comfortable in that space. The second contribution is more subtle, which connects to the notion of ontological shock. Students who spent a year abroad and have been immersed in another culture would show more maturity and a global mind-set. Successful universities aspire to produce graduates who are critical, independent thinkers by exposing them to other cultures and doing things that challenge them to understand different ways of doing things.

3.3.2 Students' intercultural experiences

The literature on international students in the UK is considerably expanding through fostering profound understandings of their intercultural experiences. Generally, in this literature, the data is generated via surveys, which are widely utilised when reporting broad trends. Moreover, many small-scale studies focus on one cultural group, such as Chinese students, or with a narrow focus, like their motivations for studying overseas (Schweisfurth and Gu, 2009). Unlike previous studies, the discussion in this research is going to focus on perceptions of Algerian PhD students about how they think studying in the UK might transform/ has transformed aspects of their identity.

The relationship between studying abroad and the challenges of adaptation that the students might face during their experience abroad had a considerable focus on research (Marambe et al., 2011). Ward and Kennedy (1993) propose two major types of intercultural adjustments namely psychological adjustment and sociocultural adaptation. The psychological adjustment can be considered as a transformative process that takes place in relation to the well-being or gratification connected with stress, whereas sociocultural adjustment is believed to be related to social skills and based on cultural knowledge (Hirai et al., 2015; Ozer, 2015). The relationship between studying abroad and the reality of the adaptation challenges that face the students is further analysed in cross-cultural studies (Vermunt et al., 2013; Martínez-Fernández and Vermunt, 2015; Sakurai and Pyhältö, 2018). Regardless of the different challenges facing the student sojourners, successful intercultural experience may have many positive outcomes including personal, academic, and career development (Coker et al., 2018).

Intercultural experiences may have a strong link to learning and growing in a different cultural and educational settings regarding the student sojourners life abroad (Gu et al., 2011). The term *intercultural* can be used to establish a link between the different domains that share the notion

of experience between two or more cultures. Intercultural experience is not just in relation to others, but also in relation to oneself. Growing throughout an intercultural experience can include any kind of experience that leads people to question their values and conventions. In other words, when people feel uncomfortable about some values and start questioning what they consider as taken-for-granted in their native cultures about themselves and their environment, they begin to be intercultural. I argue that intercultural experience can provoke self-reflection that can help in exploring new ideas, skills and knowledge (Taylor, 2017). Many studies have found that studying abroad can develop intercultural awareness, global mind-set and communicative competence (LeCrom et al., 2015; Potts, 2015; Gould, 2018).

Moreover, other studies identify learning outcomes from the students' experiences abroad in the areas of language proficiency, independence, self-confidence, social skills and interpersonal attitudes (Kinginger, 2017; Martin-Rubió and Cots, 2018; Nunan and Richards, 2015). I believe that student sojourners who are ready and enthusiastic to be temporary residents in the host society may be less likely to experience strangeness and unfamiliarity, and this can lead them to adapt successfully.

For example, Roberts et al., (2011) explain how studying abroad can amplify the learning experience arguing that experiential learning is valuable for two reasons. First, regarding the learning about others, in the sense that overseas students learn about the host society, communities and language. Second, regarding the learning about oneself and increasing reflexive knowledge of social and cultural practices. Moreover, experiential learning can result in developing reflexivity when encountering newness and otherness during intercultural experiences.

Intercultural competence can be another outcome from the study abroad experience and it can be understood as a learning process that includes self-reflection and interaction across different cultures (Tangen et al., 2011). Sojourners who are successfully navigating their way through cross-cultural encounters while living in an environment that contains conditions that may challenge their original values, assumptions and stereotypes may be more likely to acquire intercultural competence (Carmona et al., 2016; Wolff and Borzikowsky, 2018). Moreover, I may argue that intercultural competence meaning can extend to connect with multiculturalism, sense of social justice and diversity awareness (Sorrells, 2015; Murray, 2015; Bell et al., 2017). These concepts are becoming more and more significant across higher education

acknowledging that intercultural competence is equally important in the majority of contexts, which are becoming multicultural and more diverse (Ang and Van Dyne, 2015). Several research projects in different countries show deep learning transformations in students through international experiences in various environments (Gordon, 2015; Gu, 2015; Irie and Ryan, 2015; Landon et al., 2017; Nada et al., 2018).

A further aspect of the literature relates to international study and employability. Many studies suggest that it is desirable from new graduates to develop intercultural awareness and sensitivity to show that they are able to live and work effectively in a global society (Messelink et al., 2015; Baumann and Vialleton, 2017; Weber et al., 2018). In some countries, having overseas qualifications may considerably increase employment opportunities and rewards (Brooks et al., 2012; Di Pietro, 2015; Potts, 2015). For instance, employers may give greater value to people who have studied abroad arguing that, with their international experience, they can provide different ideas and viewpoints and different ways of learning and working, in addition to their exposure to different people and cultures (Petzold, 2017; Van Mol, 2017). Similarly, several studies report a similar observation in the UK where the number of students enrolling in full-degree programmes abroad is increasing as an attempt to be distinct from other students (Brooks et al., 2012; Deakin, 2013). Many scholars highlight the importance of study abroad promoting projects and programmes that can award dual degrees, which offer prolonged international experience (Culver et al., 2011).

3.3.3 Acculturation process of international students

The process of internationalisation and the presence of student sojourners can motivate universities to create a rich international context that may enhance their intercultural experience (Gu and Schweisfurth, 2011). Bochner et al., (2001) suggested a model that focuses on friendship connections in which they propose that international students generally belong to one of the three categories of social networks and each one serves a specific psychological purpose. The primary network, can be called Monoculture, includes individuals who interact most of their time with friends and people from their home society. The second network, Bi-cultural, comprises the individuals who interact with students and teachers from the host nation and learn cultural relevant skills that may help in their academic performance. The third type of networks, can be referred to as Multi-cultural, consists of those who have friends from

different cultural backgrounds, mutual social support and experience social recreational activities.

The interaction of international students with people from the host culture may have social, psychological and academic benefits. For instance, many studies reported that a greater time spent in interaction with the host nationals can be associated with fewer academic issues (Costello, 2015; Alder and Aycan, 2018), less social problems (Coleman, 2015; Mesidor and Sly, 2016), a better adaptation and communication skills (Beaven and Spencer-Oatey, 2016; Ting-Toomey and Dorjee, 2018). Moreover, other studies present that friendship with students from the host culture may have greater benefits for student sojourners, such as satisfaction of the experience overseas (Van Mol and Michielsen, 2014; King and Sondhi, 2016), less stress levels (Crowne and Engle, 2016) and a better psychological adjustment (Hirai et al., 2015; Szabo et al., 2016). The international students' psychological state might be enhanced, during the sojourn, through the social interaction with both host and co-nationals (Rui and Wang, 2015; Schartner, 2014; Zhou and Cole, 2016). Although the interaction with people from the host culture is believed to have many advantages, yet it may be minimal in some cases (Wu et al., 2015; Gautam et al., 2016). Generally, international students interact more with co-nationals, which they consider as their best friends (Taha and Cox, 2016; Thomson and Esses, 2016). Interaction with people from the same culture can be associated with having a strong national identity (Schartner, 2014; Liu and Turner, 2018). Many studies employ terms such as *alienation* and *culture distance* to describe the weak communication between host sojourners (Elliot et al., 2016; Newsome and Cooper, 2016; Zhu and Bresnahan, 2018). Generally, social support from both co-national and host nationals can mitigate homesickness and other psychological difficulties associated with life abroad (Rui and Wang, 2015; Sullivan and Kashubeck-West, 2015).

Figure 2: Acculturation process and context: framework for studying immigrants and sojourners (Ward and Geeraert, 2016, P.99).

The acculturation process is important to comprehend the structure and the different aspects of the home culture in comparison to the host culture regarding similarities and dissimilarities. The increased dissimilarity between the home culture and the host culture may cause more acculturative stress and that could impact the psychological and the socio-cultural state of sojourners (Demes and Geeraert, 2014; Van Oudenhoven and Benet-Martínez, 2015; Ward and Geeraert, 2016). The model shown in Figure 2, suggests that a successful intercultural contact may involve managing the different acculturation stressors as well as raising cultural awareness of both home culture and the host culture by acquiring, maintaining and/or changing cultural practices, beliefs and identities (ward and Geeraert, 2016). This model also considers different contextual factors such as family, institutions and society to possibly influence the acculturation processes and consequences. Several studies reported many outcomes, which have been associated with positive experiences when living abroad such as being amiable, emotionally stable, socially initiative, culturally intelligent and open-minded (Lokkesmoe et al., 2016; Mihai-Florin et al., 2016; Tracy-Ventura et al., 2016; Lee, 2017; De Oliveira Andreotti, et al., 2014).

3.3.4 Coping with stress and adjustment

During sojourn, individuals involved may feel anxious and stressed about the new context, which might affect their perception of identity (Van den Berg and Russo, 2017). Several studies focus on the relationship between stress and adjustment strategies used by student sojourners (Cho and Yu, 2014; Meghani and Harvey, 2016; Petersdotter et al, 2017; Jamaludin et al, 2016). The process of coping and adjustment is influenced by many variables, including friendship patterns, quantity and quality of interaction with host country nationals and length of residence in the host culture (Gu, 2015; Irie and Ryan, 2015; Sullivan and Kashubeck-West, 2015; Young et al., 2015; McFaul, 2016; Mesidor and Sly, 2016; Arthur, 2017). During the process of adjustment, international students may experience changes in the way they perceive the world around them like reflecting on their cultural groups and value systems (Peng et al, 2014; Wu et al., 2015; Beaven and Spencer Oatey, 2016). Sojourners abroad engaging in cross-cultural interactions with host nationals and other international students appear to develop more resilience, emotional intelligence and cross-cultural awareness (Mesidor and Sly, 2016).

3.3.5 Cognitive adjustment

Many studies on cognitive adaptation in the process of acculturation have focused on the perceptions of international students on their relations. Unlike the previously mentioned studies, which indicate that interaction between the international students and the host nationals may often be beneficial, there are studies which show that interaction and adjustment may happen only under certain circumstances (Gautman et al., 2016; Mesidor and Sly, 2016). Other studies report that many student sojourners perceive prejudice and discrimination during their interaction with people from the host culture (Wei et al, 2015; Mikkonen et al., 2016; Szabo et al., 2016). Other studies show that more contact with the host nationals may result in increasing stereotypes over time (Pham and Tran, 2015; Heng, 2018; Jamaludin et al., 2016).

On the other hand, international students can benefit from interaction with host nationals socially and psychologically (McFaul, 2016; Arthur, 2017). For example, a greater amount of interaction with host nationals has been associated with better academic performance, fewer social difficulties, improved communication competency and better general adaptation to life overseas (Sullivan and Kashubeck-West, 2015; Elliot et al., 2016; Lee et al., 2018). Additionally, contact and friendships with local students are associated with emotional benefits such as sojourner satisfaction and lower levels of stress and predict better psychological

adjustment (Wu et al., 2015). From the previous studies, international education is seen as an ongoing process of self-forming under different social conditions in which student sojourners can develop more reflexivity to cope with the different circumstances abroad.

I believe that employing the notion of identity as a process of self-creation rather than a process of adjustment to the local requirements challenges previous views that consider the original cultural identity of students as an obstruction to their experience abroad (Marginson, 2013). Usually, adjustment paradigms appear to be in harmony with classic functionalism, which puts first the assimilation of the migrant population including students. For instance, the process of adjustment generally considers international education as a journey of assimilation from the original cultural values to the host culture ones. Within this approach, studies that focus on individuals' adjustment in a different cultural system vary in the extent of presenting notions of hybrid identities (Shaheem, 2014; Young et al., 2015; Ting-Toomey, 2017).

3.3. 6 Academic adjustment of international students

Several studies have looked at the experiences of international students and the different academic challenges they faced when studying at universities in English speaking countries. For instance, many studies investigated challenges such as English language problems (Altbach, 2003; De Wit, 2017; Heng, 2018; Saha and Karpinsky, 2018) and differences in the academic cultures between the original institutions and the host institutions (Wu et al., 2015; Heng, 2018; Luttenberger et al., 2017). Research in the field of international study indicates that language proficiency is one of the major problems that international students face during their study abroad (Mak et al., 2015; Savignon, 2017).

Focusing on the adjustment of postgraduate students to the new culture, Martirosian et al., (2015) explain that most of the overseas students may face more difficulties adjusting to the new academic context. For instance, the lack of knowledge about the academic culture can be one of the most common issues among international students, which can affect their cultural and academic adjustments within the host institutions (Handa and Fallon, 2006). Similarly, PhD students may face more challenges during the adjustment to the new academic context, which involves finding out the hidden curriculum in a new academic culture (Elliot et al., 2016).

The literature about the difficulties and issues that student sojourners may encounter during their experience abroad include cultural disputes (Adrian-Taylor et al., 2007), students-

supervisors relationship (Adams and Cargill, 2003; McClure, 2005; Winchester-seeto, 2013), thesis writing difficulties (Bitchener et al, 2010; Wang and Lee, 2011), critical thinking as a research culture (Kamler and Thomson, 2014), financial problems and support (Leong, 2015; Elliot et al., 2016; Lee, 2017) and the use of information technology and digital education (Zhang and Kenny, 2010). These studies clearly indicate that there are many factors affecting the experiences of international students who pursue their studies in foreign establishments. The difficulty/ease of adjustment of student sojourners to the host academic culture differs from one individual to another depending on factors such as openness towards the new academic culture and proficiency of English language, which may lead to successful academic acculturation (Meng et al., 2017).

3.3.7 Identity and adjustment

Study abroad can be one of the most powerful aspects of global movements (Gordon, 2015). Many studies on overseas education show many positive outcomes, such as developing cultural intelligence (Peng et al., 2014), broadening the students' perspectives and impacting the way they live and think (McLeod et al., 2015) increasing communication skills and self-efficiency (Yang et al., 2018). Understanding the process of identity negotiation would prepare student sojourners for the changes that may occur during their experiences abroad.

During their sojourn, individuals, as well as groups of people take part in intercultural interaction, which may result in instances of conflict that necessitate negotiation from all parties to achieve satisfactory outcomes (Berry, 2005). People may react differently to the process of acculturation. For instance, at the group level, acculturation may result in changes in religious and cultural practices of the group including the clothes, food and language (Berry, 2003). However, acculturation can affect individuals' values attitudes and behaviours through exposure to the new cultural environment.

Sojourners appear to negotiate identity and develop hybrid identities whenever they are faced with novelty in the new cultural contexts (Comănaru et al., 2017). Moreover, throughout the sojourn, students may deepen their understanding of the others, and equally expand their understanding of self (Young et al., 2015). As a result, hybrid identities can be created during the process of purposefully adopting or keeping some elements from home culture, while also purposefully adopting or keeping some elements from the host culture (Weinreich, 2009). Students who successfully navigate their experiences abroad usually show higher self-esteem,

lower signs of depression and prosocial behaviour (Ward et al., 2011; Nguyen and Benet-Martínez, 2012; Hong et al., 2016). The degree of how easy or how difficult is to integrate within the host society depends, to some extent, on the degree of similarity between the individuals' home culture and the host culture (Rudmin, 2003).

3.4 Overview of the bioecological theory of human development

This theory proposed by Bronfenbrenner (1979, 1997) is considered as a combination of some theories related to developmental psychology. Bronfenbrenner's early theory was called "Ecological Systems Theory". It intends to explain the different systems that influence human development in which he described four systems (microsystem mesosystem exosystem and macrosystem) to conceptualize environmental contexts. These systems were later included in his updated version (bioecological theory) under the name of context. This will be further explained in the following section. He suggested that both individuals and their environments constantly influence one another. However, this early model was criticised for not putting enough focus on individuals' biological and identifying characteristics in their development, which necessitated further development. In the context of this study, the notion of contextual forces affecting the individuals' development is important to understand the Algerian doctoral students' experiences in the UK, but it is not sufficient to provide a complete understanding of the different internal and external processes of identity development within those contexts.

In his definition of the bioecological systems theory, Bronfenbrenner argues that it is important to understand the subjective meaning attributed to the environment in order to understand human behaviour. He further claims that his bioecological approach serves well as a theoretical framework that will lead to further progress in finding the different processes and the circumstances of human development. For this reason, I believe that this theory might be useful for this current qualitative research that aims to explore the Algerian postgraduate international students' perspectives about their identity development during their study at several UK universities in time frame between 2015 and 2017.

3.4.1 Main concepts of the bioecological theory

Human development is a continuous process of physical, emotional, cognitive and behavioural changes. Throughout the different processes and experiences that occur during a life time, individuals of different ages may develop different attitudes and beliefs that influence their

views, roles, and choices. Many developmental theories such as Bronfenbrenner's bioecological theory, and Vygotsky's proximal development theory, advocate that genetics and environment can affect people's development arguing that learning and development occur when interacting with the environment. Bronfenbrenner (2001) introduces his bioecological theory as "an evolving theoretical system for the scientific study of the human development over time" (pp. 6963-6964). The bioecological systems theory of human development focuses on the interaction between four main elements: process, person, context and time (Newman and Newman, 2015).

Process

The term process / proximal process is used by Bronfenbrenner to refer to any interaction between an organism and the environment. Proximal processes are believed to be important means that connect the individual with people, objects and symbolic representations in the environment. For these processes to have an impact on the person's development, they must occur on a consistent basis over long periods of time.

Person

The process may affect the development of individuals in a variety of ways depending on personal characteristics.

Demand characteristics

Demand characteristics are about the capacity to encourage and discourage reactions from the social context. For instance, the biological aspect of personal characteristics such as age, gender, skin colour, physical disability may encourage or disturb the process of psychological development (Bronfenbrenner and Morris, 2007). Additionally, cultural community, family beliefs and preferences can change the nature of proximal processes (Newman and Newman, 2015). Demand characteristics are often visible in comparison to dispositions and resources.

Dispositions

Dispositions (or forces) can set proximal processes in action in a specific environment as they can be both positive and negative (Bronfenbrenner and Morris, 2007). For example, they can be personality, motivation and persistence (Newman and Newman, 2015).

Resources

Newman and Newman (2015) state that resources can be of a cognitive nature such as knowledge, past experience, specific skills, humour, self-regulation and emotional control. Moreover, they can be material resources like a healthy diet, access to health care, safe home.

Context

Bronfenbrenner's theory is composed of a layered sub-system, each inside the other like the Russian doll. This model is comprised of five different contexts, the microsystem, mesosystem, exosystem, macro system and chronosystem. Each of the sub-systems put an emphasis on the individual's perceptions of the activities, roles and interpersonal relations within the individual's environmental contexts. At the centre of this model lies the microsystem where the individual is located. Within the microsystem, individuals develop direct and close interactions with people, objects and places, in the immediate environment, through social activities with, for instance, family members, school, students in the classroom, roommates, neighbours, etc. Bronfenbrenner (1979) believes that microsystem is the most influential level of the bioecological system because the relationships are bi-directional. In other words, reactions to the people in the microsystem will affect how they treat you in return. The next level of bioecological systems theory is mesosystem. It consists of the interconnections and influences of the distinct parts of microsystem on one another. These interactions have an indirect impact on the individual. The exosystem refers to a setting that does not involve the individuals as an active participant but still affects them. For instance, social, environmental, governmental forces indirectly influence the individual's course of development. The fourth level of the bioecological systems theory is the macro system. It encompasses the cultural environment where individuals live and all other systems that affect them, like attitudes, ideology and subcultures.

Time

The chronosystem is the final level of the bioecological systems theory. Bronfenbrenner (1994) defines it as the dimension of time and major events in relation to a person's development. He adds that the chronosystem encompasses any change or consistency of a person or the environment where that person lives. For instance, the family structure, socio-economic status,

or place of residence. Time can also be an influence because of historical events or conditions that exist during the individuals' lives (e.g. War or Brexit).

3.4.2 Strengths and weaknesses

Newman and Newman (2015, p. 304) suggested a list of both strengths and weaknesses of the bioecological theory as the following.

Strengths

The bioecological theory made a major influence of the study of development by providing a new perspective on contexts of development and the individuals' ability to adapt to multiple contexts. In addition, the concept of the proximal process stresses the importance of reciprocal interactions among individuals and the people, objects and symbols in supporting or hindering the development. For example, the mutual relationship between children and their caregivers, students' and teachers' relationships, or even workers and supervisors. Another strength is that this model can be considered both simple and complex at the same time. On the one hand, it is composed of only four components to identify the process of development. On the other hand, each of the composing components may contain various factors, which may add complexity to the model. Moreover, it highlights the importance of describing the proximal processes that take place between settings. These processes may differ across settings that have the same name or label (e.g. classroom or workplace). Furthermore, the model emphasises the importance and value of observing behaviour in natural settings. Bronfenbrenner argues that behaviours can be observed in a laboratory, but they cannot be generalised to real-life settings. In addition to being frequently cited as a framework for research of human development, the bioecological model inspired new initiatives in longitudinal studies that focus on development in changing time and contexts.

Weaknesses

Newman and Newman (2015, p. 304) provide a list of weaknesses that can be summarised as follows. The concept of *person* is not sufficiently developed since it provides a minimal reference to the importance of psychological aspects such as motivation and emotions. Another weakness in the theory is that it does not explain the development process in relation to an

individual's reasoning, or self-understanding. In addition, it does not provide enough details on how specific proximal processes provide support for the individual's development during different periods of time (e.g. childhood, adulthood). Even though the concept of time is among the principal elements of this model, it is still not clear. Furthermore, many views from biological ecology and psychological ecology, which they might be useful in identifying the nature of development, are not integrated within the theory. This model of development ecology established by Bronfenbrenner makes a considerable addition to our knowledge about the effects of contexts on the peoples' roles and behaviours at different levels. When considering study abroad experiences and the development /negotiation of identities, I believe that this model is a substantial tool for explaining the different powers affecting the processes of development.

In this study, I used the bioecological theory of Bronfenbrenner to determine the different proximal processes influencing the Algerian PhD students' identity development in the UK. Bronfenbrenner's model is one of the most prominent theoretical frameworks across a variety of fields of study in the social sciences (Vélez-Agosto et al., 2017). Even though the bioecological theory has gained wide popularity and importance in the field of early childhood development in the 1980s, it seems that this model can be used with adults' development as well. Several published studies based on this model have successfully used it with adult participants (e.g. Woods et al., 2019; Way et al., 2008).

For instance, Adamson and her colleagues (2007) investigated the difference between two groups of fathers, biological fathers and step-fathers, in terms of involvement and quality of father-child interaction using elements from Bronfenbrenner's model. Findings showed that fathers were the developing as persons by assessing the fathers' position in the family, age, race, marital wellbeing and belief about parenting. Woods and his colleagues (2019) explored college students' leadership development in relation to the use of social media during digital education. They focused on adult millennial identity development of students aged between 18 and 29 in relation to Bronfenbrenner's context aspects in their interpretation. In their qualitative study, Way et al., (2008) focused on the intersection of personal and ethnic identities among forty high school students. They used Bronfenbrenner's bioecological theory to determine the course of personal and ethnic identity development of high school students from different backgrounds. This study examined the ways in which proximal processes such as family and schools as a context of identity development for high school students.

As the aforementioned studies, I used aspects of Bronfenbrenner's bioecological model to examine the perceptions of Algerian PhD students who live in the UK about their development abroad. Admitting that Bronfenbrenner's bioecological theory was originally developed to explain how the children's proximal and distal contexts can affect their development, I argue that this theory can also be successfully applied to explain adults' development within different contexts.

Conclusion

To summarise, this chapter contains a discussion of the relevant literature about some prominent theories related to international doctoral students' social, cultural and emotional experiences to explore concepts such as mobility, adjustment, identity development and negotiation. This literature review sets the context of this research study and explains the relation between the variables. The main sections of this literature review focus on exploring and explaining common theories about culture, identity development and negotiation, mobility of international students and adjustment processes. It is important to mention that there have not been many studies about the identity development and adjustment strategies of Algerian doctoral students in a culturally, socially, scholarly different contexts in the UK. Therefore, the goal of this study is to explore the different views of Algerian PhD students' experiences of identity development and adjustment strategies while studying in different universities across the UK. To make sense to the various experiences of the Algerian doctoral students in the UK, an overview of Bronfenbrenner's bioecological theory of human development in relation to the international student sojourners' experiences and identity development is provided. The overall research design and the main research methods and their importance in this study will be addressed in the following chapter.

Chapter 4: Methodology

Introduction

This research study aims at exploring the views and experiences of the Algerian international doctoral students in the UK about their identity development and adjustment strategies. This qualitative study is positioned within the interpretive approach, which aims at understanding and explaining human experience rather than searching for external causes and fundamental laws. To collect data for this research study, a combination of a questionnaire and photo-elicitation interviews were employed. The questionnaire was used to reach a large number of Algerian PhD participants across the UK, and its aim was to draw a general understanding of the views of Algerian PhD students about their identity development during studying abroad. The photo-elicitation interview was used to generate a deeper understanding of the experiences of ten of the Algerian doctoral students in the UK. It is important to note that photographs were used to elicit more information and deeper reactions to the different experiences of Algerian PhD students during the interview sessions. The generated data is analysed through different approaches to the thematic analysis process. This chapter covers in detail all the aforementioned points in addition to the different advantages and disadvantages of the chosen approaches and methods and the ways to minimise the disadvantages.

4.1 Methodological framework

The methodological framework contains a series of actions that aim at answering the research questions by analysing the data and identifying different patterns of meaning. In order to identify patterns of meaning within the data set, researchers must familiarise themselves with the data, code it, develop the themes and finally revise the themes. In this particular study, I followed these steps:

- I formulated research questions, which are conforming to the related theoretical approaches to keep the research focused on track.
- I identified and selected the research sample being the Algerian PhD students who study in the UK.

- I gathered enough information about the subject in hand by exploring previous research from experts. My research focused on areas of expertise such as identity development and acculturation literature.
- Interviews were composed in relation to the sojourn experience with consideration of the cultural and ethical aspects.
- The collected data was carefully transcribed and inspected for accuracy. Transcripts were read repeatedly before initiating the coding process.
- Analysing the data was done by moving back and forward between the whole data set and extracting codes and themes. I used temporary qualitative codes to provide a deeper understanding of the Algerian sojourners' learning experiences abroad. I attempted to connect the ideas in order to gain an understanding of the studied phenomenon. During the coding phase, all information from the transcripts were taken into consideration.
- I started writing down ideas and possible coding arrangements after scrutinising the whole set of data. Initially, many themes were identified, nevertheless, not all the initial themes were kept after the process of reviewing and selection. The retained themes were defined and named.
- Utilising some expressive examples and quotations, which effectively illustrated the points being made, findings from my research were registered through writing-up that can be found in later chapters.

4.1.1 Ethical guidelines for the interview

Throughout every phase of this qualitative study, ethical guidelines were always taken into consideration during the methodological process, especially in the way of selecting and interacting with people who participated in this research. It is necessary and crucial to be aware of ethical considerations particularly in qualitative research (Miller et al., 2012).

In all the stages of this research, the ethical guidelines of the university were respected and applied. The University Ethics Committee (UEC) granted approval to start the field work after reviewing the methodology chapter. The following actions had to be implemented and adhered to:

- An information sheet must be submitted to participants with a consent form to sign.

- Data from Interviews and transcripts should be safely stored then destroyed after 5 years when the research is done.
- Participation should be voluntary and free from coercion.

Before starting the interview sessions, all participants signed and submitted an informed consent. A brief summary of the main aims and the methodological procedures were fully explained to the participants before they agree to participate in this research. I made sure that participants were aware that they can withdraw from taking part in the interview at any time they feel uncomfortable without providing any justifications.

Participants were assured about confidentiality and anonymity. Their transcripts and voice records were stored safely in a password-protected laptop and all personal information mentioned during the interview were removed. Interviews took place in natural atmospheres, such as the university or place of residence, to minimise discomfort and increase respect and privacy.

When debriefing the participants during the interview sessions, I made sure to inform them that a summary of this research will be submitted to them when this project is complete. I did not offer the participants the opportunity to request a copy of the transcripts of the interview since no one did ask for it. Some studies suggest that returning the transcript to participants may increase the transparency and validity of the study; however, it also may be problematic at other levels (Forbat and Henderson, 2005; Shaw et al., 2010; Simpson and Quigley, 2016; Tsai et al., 2016; Thomas, 2016). For instance, participants may feel confused when seeing the written version of their testimonies and they may feel insecure if there are many corrections. These considerations were taken into account for ensuring appropriateness during the whole research process.

4.1.2 The researcher's role

In any research, especially the ones using qualitative approaches, it is important to acknowledge any possibility of potential bias. For instance, it was valuable for me to state that there may be some possible bias in my study emerging from being an Algerian PhD student studying in the UK. The term bias may imply subjective interpretations, which may alter the existing reality (Jussim, 2012; Noble and Smith, 2015). Nevertheless, participating in a reflexive activity can shift subjectivity into a positive outcome (Roulston and Shelton, 2015) in the sense that

reflecting on oneself may allow researchers to understand the participants' opinions on the different experiences of Algerian student sojourners.

Researchers reflecting on the way participants responded to their questions and on how they interpreted different parts of the transcripts is a very important aspect of qualitative research. The Algerian students appeared more formal when communicating their ideas. During the interview sessions, I felt that they were mindful of what they think and choosing what to say before answering any question. Some of the participants were enthusiastic to share some of their personal experiences in the UK and in Algeria. The way they talked about some feelings such as discomfort and anger were expressed using formal language and with respect.

In some cases, participants appeared to be repressing some of their opinions concerning experiences that they believe to be socially inappropriate or what they think to be too obvious. For instance, expressions such as “you know” and “you know what I mean” were repeatedly used by some participants. Perhaps the fact that they know that I am an Algerian student studying in the UK was one of the reasons that they may assume that I fully understand their experiences. In these cases, I had to focus on obtaining more detailed data without pushing too hard on the participants, which may create an uncomfortable environment. Furthermore, having in mind that the Algerian culture is more conservative regarding gender roles and awareness, I had to ensure that all participants felt respected at all levels.

4.1.3 Pilot study

The pilot study was useful in finding new ideas and techniques that were not taken into consideration earlier. I conducted a pilot study before the actual data collection for evaluating the usefulness of the data collection methods in answering the research questions. Another aim was to assess the quality and the relevance of the photographs and the answers for the interview questions. It also aimed at determining how easy or hard is the procedure of the photo-elicitation interviewing method in collecting data. It was carried out with three international students (2 females and one male). All the participants had been in the UK for more than six months.

I prepared a questionnaire on Google Forms, which is an online platform used for questionnaires and sent it to six participants, who are not taking part in the research project. Some of the questions were extracted from other research projects and modified to fit the aim of this study. Through the answers and the comment section at the end of the questionnaire, I

managed to clarify, simplify and rearrange some of the elements of the questionnaire to work accordingly with my research aims for answering the research questions.

After that, I have conducted interviews using the photo-elicitation method. Participants showed satisfaction on this technique in general. For instance, they mentioned that during the interview, they felt comfortable speaking about their own pictures, experiences and memories. Moreover, some of them suggested making the interviews a bit shorter since it was a tiring process for them, which I took into consideration and limited the period to 30 minutes as stated in the ethics committee comments. Limiting the time of the interviews was challenging since I dropped many questions, but that gave more time for the participants to reflect on their own pictures and minimise the researcher's interference.

The pilot study provided me with ideas and approaches that were not considered before, such as clarifying the interview structure. For instance, some of the questions in the interview were not very effective when I asked them, even though they seemed suitable when they were being formulated (Spradley, 2016). Moreover, thought-provoking questions were asked instead of questions that prompted short answers to get more details about the lived experiences. I made some changes to the instructions of taking photographs: I had to state clearly that the participants could provide pictures according to the categories provided in the instructions sheet.

Instead of conducting the interviews in my office at the University, which was shared by many other PhD researchers, I suggested that the meeting places with the participants were negotiated and dependent on the participant's preference. Some of the interviews took place within the university in quiet places. Other interviewees, who were acquaintances, invited me to their place in which the interviews were conducted with no threat to ethics of the safety or either the participants or the researcher. It was very important to establish trust and comfort with the participants by giving them freedom in choosing the time and place of the interview. According to Broom et al. (2009), a positive relationship with the respondents is a critical point for successful interviews since responses may be affected if the person is stressed or not comfortable.

During the interviews, I emphasised the importance of being objective, formal and at the same time friendly and understanding. I learned that it was very important to prepare the interviewees and create a link of comfort and trust before moving to talk about more specific and personal

information. The use of the participants' photographs may reduce the stress and intimidation of the participants. An average of 30 minutes was specified for the interviews; however, some interviews took longer simply because the participants had more to discuss.

In sum, the pilot study was beneficial in determining how the actual study would look like. I conducted a pilot study mainly for evaluating the procedures of the data collection methods and their usefulness in answering the research questions. For instance, the pilot study helped in assessing the quality and the relevance of the data generated by the photo elicitation interview method. Some changes were made on the level of the instructions for taking photographs. Concerning the questionnaire, the pilot study showed that open-ended questions provided valuable data.

4.1.4 Data transcription

All the interviews were transcribed after the data collection. The transcription of the interviews was a simple process since all the participants in the photo-elicitation interviews spoke in English with some phrases in Arabic. The recorded interviews had a clear and good sound quality from my personal smartphone. As soon as the interviews were recorded and moved to a secure computer, they were transcribed to facilitate the process of analysis. Moreover, I used NVivo software as an analytic tool for managing and analysing the data. I can argue that the data analysis was basically subjective, which allowed more engagement in the analysis process since using NVivo requires coding and developing themes and categories from the data.

Interesting data from the transcripts of the interviews in relation to the research questions were selected and categorised along with the themes, which were selected on the basis of the research questions. During the analysis process, I observed that there were pieces of information that did not have any significance in relation to the questions being asked. I had to re-read the original transcripts several times in order to re-evaluate codes and re-organise them by inserting more information and removing irrelevant parts.

The data was thoroughly scrutinised to find out comparable data among texts. Themes were selected, labelled and categorised by manually extracting them from the original texts with the help of NVivo. The next stage was putting together the findings alongside the excerpts and relating them to existing knowledge about the acculturation processes and identity development.

4.1.5 Reliability and validity in qualitative research

The notion of reliability in qualitative research is problematic (Merriam and Leahy, 2005). In the domain of science, reliability indicates that findings from a given study should be replicable and consistent. In other words, checking the truth of the findings can be done using the same objective methods to find identical results all the time (Lehner, 1998). Quantitative research is built upon the positivist paradigm, which regards the world as comprised of statistical data that can be quantified, therefore measured. Validity in quantitative research refers to whether the measurement is measuring what it is supposed to measure

On the other hand, a qualitative methodology can be based on a constructivist paradigm that generally explores phenomena in their natural contexts, in which researchers do not attempt to manoeuvre the phenomenon under study (Oliver, 2011).

The term “qualitative research” can be used as an umbrella term that includes a variety of research methods that share some aspects between them. Qualitative researchers use a naturalistic approach in studying phenomena in their social environment using methods that are more subjective than quantitative research.

Validity in qualitative studies is usually discussed in terms of three common threats to validity, which are three types of bias including respondent bias, researcher bias and reactivity (Sliverman, 1993).

Respondent bias refers to the situation where participants are not giving honest responses for any reason. For instance, they may feel that the topic is threatening to their self-esteem, or they may simply try to provide answers that they think researchers are looking for. A potential respondent bias in this study can be in relation to social and culturally sensitive situations where the female participants may feel uncomfortable to share with me as a male researcher.

Researcher bias can be very risky to the research validity and it refers to the influence of previous knowledge and assumptions of the researcher on the studied phenomenon (Patten and Newhart, 2018). A potential bias in this study can be the fact that I, as a researcher, share many qualities with the research participants such as the country of origin, the study programme, and the language, which can influence the data analysis and discussion processes.

Reflexivity refers to the role of the researcher and the influence that comes with it (Patten and Newhart, 2018). Like physical presence in the research situation and its possible influence on the quality of data from the participants. Similar to respondent bias, a potential reflexivity bias in this study can be due to my presence as a male researcher with female participants when discussing subjects that can be culturally sensitive in Algeria.

To minimise the potential influence of these three types of bias, Robson (2002) suggests six strategies to deal with threats to validity.

Prolonged involvement refers to the researcher being involved in the research situation in the participants' environment, which is likely to increase the level of trust between the researcher and participants (Smith and Noble, 2014). This, in turn, is likely to reduce the risk of respondent bias and reflexivity by generating mutual trust. However, it is likely to increase the risk of researcher bias because the relationship of the researcher and participants is likely to generate a set of common assumptions, which may be very risky.

Triangulation may refer to many things including triangulation of data collection methods, triangulation of methodology, or triangulation of theory. Triangulation is likely to minimise all kinds of threats to validity (Patton, 1999). In this research, I used a triangulation of data collection methods including a questionnaire and photo elicitation interviews. I believe that including different types of data can minimise the risks to validity by crosschecking the findings of the two methods.

Peer debriefing refers to any feedback or input from other people. This could be during events such as workshops, seminars or conferences (Kemperaj and Chavan, 2013). The received feedback may help the researcher to become more objective and can help raising awareness and targeting the limitations of the study, which is likely to minimise the researcher's bias by making the researcher becoming more objective and more aware of the ways that can improve the study. In this study, I received feedback from different sources including the supervisory team, some fellow researchers at the university, other researchers during an international conference and from the pilot study in which I piloted the two data collection methods.

Member checking refers to the practice of seeking clarification with the research participants by asking them to clarify certain aspects before jumping into conclusions (Creswell and Miller, 2000). In other words, keeping in touch with the participants concerning data clarification.

Another practice can include sending the participants their interview transcripts asking them to delete, add or change things in the transcripts. Another method is called validation interview in which the researcher conducts a second interview after an initial analysis of the first interview asking the participants about the interpretations and anything that was not clear from the first interview (Patton, 1999).

Negative case analysis involves analysing the cases of the data sets that do not match the trends of the rest of the data (Lincoln and Guba, 1995; Onwuegbuzie, and Leech, 2006). These sets of negative cases can tell more about the rest of the data by highlighting the differences from the data, and they also can highlight the similarities between the rests of the data.

Audit trail involves keeping records of all the activities involved in the research including the audio recording, the methodological decisions, the researcher diaries, and coding schemes (Creswell and Miller, 2000). This method increases the transparency of the research practices and the validity of the findings.

Using reliability to evaluate qualitative research would indicate that the research is poor in quality. Good qualitative research would reflect consistency and care in the application of research practices, which can be demonstrated through the discernibility of research practices, analysis and conclusions. It also should accept the presence of issues of partiality and limits of the research findings (Davis and Dodd, 2002).

The nature of qualitative research methods does not correlate with the statistical calculations of validity. Therefore, many researchers using qualitative methods suggested tactics and strategies to enhance the truthfulness or validity of qualitative findings (Golafshani, 2003; Leko, 2014; Trainor and Graue, 2014).

4. 2 Research design

The methodology adopted in any research should be led by the type of research problem identified. A valid research should provide a justification for the theoretical perspective that informs the choices of research methodology and methods. Moreover, rationalising (explaining) the methodology's choices can provide an understanding of the type and the characteristics of knowledge that will be obtained from research. According to Crotty (1998),

an efficient research design contains four elements: the epistemology, theoretical perspective, methodology and methods as clarified in figure 3.

Figure 3: Elements of research design (Crotty, 1998)

Crotty's model and similar models show research design as several phases that are organised in a logical framing of the research problem to the results or theories (Maxwell, 2012). This type of model is usually similar to a sequence diagram that shows a strong starting point and clear study objectives and the particular order of tasks in between. Some versions of this model are circular in the sense that earlier phases are related to later ones. This type is still linear since it is characterised by the arrangement of structures in a single direction, which is believed to be the best possible order for conducting research (Maxwell, 2008). Moreover, it tends to ignore some fundamental components such as the purpose of the research and the plans for tackling the validity of the research.

The notion of typological methodology appear in this study as the way I, as a researcher, logically planned the research design starting from epistemological considerations down to the research methods. However, I trust that an interactive approach to research design would be more effective since it highlights the relationships of the different elements of research.

4.3 Maxwell's interactive model of research design

In qualitative research, designs may be more flexible, evolving and emergent rather than fixed, structured and pre-determined in comparison to those in quantitative designs (Robson and McCartan, 2016). In its very earlier stages, qualitative research aims to explore a given phenomenon by identifying patterns, themes and models that can provide an initial understanding of a given phenomenon. For doing so, qualitative research design should be a reflexive process that is related to all research stages of development (Alvesson and Sköldbberg, 2017). The processes of collecting and analysing the data, theory development and modification, developing and framing research questions and issues around the research validity are normally related to each other and affect one another at the same time; each of the elements affects the other ones (Flick, 2018).

Research designs of qualitative studies involve interconnection and interaction between the design elements; therefore, they do not follow a fixed order of stages (Maxwell, 2012). A flexible, non-sequential approach is usually required in applied research, which means that qualitative research requires a wider and less limiting concept of design than the traditional ones listed previously (Brannen, 2017).

I believe that the interactive approach presented by Maxwell (2005) can be considered as a flexible, reflexive approach, which can still meet the criterion of systematic. This approach has two main characteristics, the elements themselves and the relationship between the elements. It is composed of five elements that focus on specific questions (Maxwell, 2012).

1. Objectives

This section focuses on defining and setting the goals of the study, in addition to the different issues that the study is intending to explain along with the intended outcomes.

2. Conceptual Framework

This section may include explanations about the choice of theories and beliefs about the studied phenomena. It may contain types of theories and beliefs that a study is built upon, for instance, the knowledge drawn from the literature, personal experience, preliminary studies, or from other sources.

3. Research Questions

This section contains what the researcher wants to understand by doing this study. This can include the questions that the researcher attempts to answer.

4. Methods

This section explains how the study is going to be conducted, research approaches, and techniques that will be used for collecting and analysing data. It can be divided into four different parts including the relationships created between the researcher and the research participants; sampling strategies that can involve the selection of contexts, research participants, the times and places of data collection and other data sources; data collection methods; and data analysis strategies and methods.

5. Validity

This section demonstrates the possible ways that the conclusions of the research could be wrong along with the alternative explanations and validity threats. In this section, researchers can address alternative explanations and validity threats and what makes the research results plausible.

Ethics are not identified as an independent component of research design, but they should be engaged with every aspect of the design (Maxwell, 2008).

The components used in this model are not different from those used in many writings about qualitative applied research design (e.g. Schwandt et al, 2007; Robson, 2017). However, this model focuses more on the relationship between the elements in the sense that they form a cohesive and interacting unit. Unlike the linear and cyclic arrangements, each component of this design is strongly related to many others as displayed in figure 4.

Figure 4: An interactive model of research design (Maxwell, 2005)

In this design, there are also other connections indicated by dashed lines that show the influence of the research goals and the methods that can be used and vice versa. Similarly, the theoretical framework will have an influence on the validity issues and vice versa.

I have chosen to use Maxwell’s model in this study as it is a flexible and non-sequential approach that can suit the qualitative applied research in general and this present research project in particular. Maxwell’s model seems to be useful in this study and similar studies since it clearly reveals and explains the major design choices and connections between its elements. Moreover, design issues that may appear within each of the components can be easily located and managed in a systematic way.

4.4 Research objectives (goals)

The term ‘goals’ is used broadly to identify motives, desires and purposes that lead to conducting research. Research goals can help researchers making better decisions about the other design components. In addition, research goals might influence the description,

interpretation and theories created along the research process. Consequently, they are essential not only when mapping, conducting and explaining the research, but also in identifying the validity issues and the sources of bias needed to be handled.

In this work, student sojourners are the students who are carrying out their studies in a foreign country for a limited period. Henceforth, the terms “international students” and “student sojourners” will be used in that sense, except if stated differently. The constraints of conducting this research during the limited time of a PhD programme and as a single researcher led me to study one case of international students in one university in Scotland.

Due to the increasing number of international students around the world, many higher education institutions are adjusting their services according to these students’ needs. For instance, during 2011/2012, the UK offered higher education services to more than 425,256 international students (Higher Education Statistics Agency, 2014). In 2012/2013, Scotland received 21.9% of the international students’ population in the UK (Tindal et al., 2013).

This research arises from my personal interest as a PhD international student in the UK and it is observed from different points of view. My interest in exploring the international students’ experiences was triggered when I was a student at the university level in Algeria where I was exposed to other international students from outside my country who became my friends. Spending some time with them, I enjoyed being exposed to their culture over three years, learning some vocabulary from their dialect and helping them get over some problems related to the language and culture. I was surprised to see some of them changed their behaviours, attitudes, and thinking, while others did not.

In 2014, more than 80 % of Algerian students went to France from a total of 20 695 students abroad (Ulrich, 2016). In the same year, the Algerian Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research granted 500 funded PhD scholarships to different UK universities over five years in an attempt to develop capacities in English across Algerian universities and to expand international partnership to English-speaking countries. Being selected to take part in this ambitious plan by the Algerian Government, I saw the opportunity of conducting this qualitative research on the Algerian PhD students’ in the UK since there is a shortage of studies on this particular context. I wanted to explore the Algerian PhD students’ understanding of their hybrid identity development in a different geographical, cultural, and historical context to see the different experiences that could affect that. Therefore, this research study is important in

expanding the knowledge about the Algerian PhD students' population in the UK and their hybrid identity development in this context.

4.5 Theoretical perspective

Epistemology is the type of relationship between what we know and how we know it (Guba and Lincoln, 1998). It provides a philosophical background to support research projects by ensuring the legitimacy and adequacy of the different kinds of obtained knowledge (Maynard, 1994). There exist several epistemologies, but this section will focus on only two approaches which are objectivism and interpretivism.

Much of the academic literature is built on the objectivist epistemology (Crotty, 1998). Researchers who build their studies on this approach assume that meaning exists apart from consciousness presuming that there is only one objective reality. The alternative epistemological approach that rejects the objectivists' viewpoint is known as constructionism. Proponents of this philosophy argue that meaning is constructed through interactions with the different realities of the world. Hodkinson (2009) argues that constructionism emphasises that social units are constructed when human beings attach meaning to their social reality. Some studies argue that language is what constructs reality, while other studies focus on how individuals interpret their acts in relation to the other individuals and the world around them. In other words, people make meaning in accordance with their behaviours and interpretations. This view considers meaning as constructed instead of already existing apart from consciousness (Crotty, 1998). According to Guba and Lincoln (1998), constructionist studies have characteristics such as relativist, transactional and subjectivist. Accepting the relativist position means that objective knowledge does not exist, in the sense that there are multiple subjective interpretations that can be applied to the real world rather than one objective truth (Hugly and Sayward, 1987). Moreover, Berlin (1989) argues that the term transactional indicates that knowledge cannot exist without interaction between elements, such as individuals, in a given context. In addition, Ratner (2008) states that subjectivist studies rely on the researchers to provide a worldview from their own perspectives.

Crotty (1998) states that the theoretical viewpoint will underlie the whole research process and it will govern the choice of the methodology and the research tools. For illustration, two qualitative perspectives will be described and compared to provide a useful guide.

4.5.1 Positivism

Positivism is the theoretical position that stresses the importance of studying the social world according to the same beliefs, methods and philosophy of natural sciences (Bryman, 2001). Different authors use positivism in distinctive styles, which make it hard to identify and outline in an accurate way. For instance, some scholars believe that positivism describes a philosophical position while others believe that it is the scientific approach that considers knowledge as reliable only if it is obtained through measurement and observation via the senses. Bryman (2001) lists five principles of positivism as an epistemological position that can be summarised as follows. First, only the phenomena that can be observed by the senses is considered as knowledge. Second, a theory is used to produce testable hypotheses that will permit explanations of laws (deductive principle). Third, knowledge can be generated through the collection of facts that constitute laws (inductive principle). Fourth, science must be conducted in an objective way. Finally, there is a well-defined difference between normative and scientific statements. According to these principles, the positivist approach highlights the cause-effect relationship and quantifiable observations that lead to generalisations. Crowther and Lancaster (2008) argue that positivist studies are usually associated with a deductive strategy, however, phenomenology philosophy espouses the inductive research approach. Bryman (2001) states that these principles imply that observation is given a better epistemological position than theory arguing that the role of research is to test theories, but it is still likely to gather observations without being influenced by a pre-existing theory.

4.5.2 Interpretivism

As an alternative epistemological stance to positivism, interpretivism is a term that contrasts with positivism and indicates that researchers interpret elements of the study rather than describing and explaining them. According to Myers (2008), researchers who follow an interpretive tradition believe that there are various realities, which are perceived through 'language, consciousness, shared meanings and instruments' that are socially constructed phenomena (p. 38). Unlike positivism, which seeks to provide an explanation of the human behaviour, interpretivism encourages to focus more on understanding those behaviours (Bryman, 2001). Collins (2010) considers interpretivism as a combination of different approaches such as social constructionism, phenomenology and hermeneutics. He adds that these approaches accept the subjectivist view, which advocates that there are multiple meanings

existing within the world (Ibid, p.38). Moreover, Crotty (1998) argues that studies based on the interpretive approach presume that people can create different realities regarding the same experience. This approach provides the researcher with a great deal of flexibility in exploring different viewpoints and experiences of different participants.

This research project will be built based on an interpretive, social constructionist viewpoint. On the one hand, I believe that human beings are shaped by culture, which is crucial to understanding and explaining human behaviours (Gifford, 2008). On the other hand, research on identity shifted from the macro level that focuses on society in general to the micro level that focuses more on individuals to reveal their constructed realities (De Fina, 2012). In other words, people experience a constant tension in understanding and meaning-making on a daily basis: from one side, the inner, micro level of meaning-making as individuals and from another side, the external, macro level as collective meanings. Such a conflict is perceived differently by diverse cultures in different places at different times.

4. 6 Conceptual framework

As more and more research are conducted, researchers consider the findings of previous studies along with the relationships observed between the variables in those studies. Generally, researchers try to understand the findings of many different projects together to better understand the field as a whole, so that they can better develop a clear understanding of the relationships presented within those studies (Wacker, 1998).

Starting from the individual studies to an understanding of the relationships in the field as a whole can lead to building a theory, or a system of ideas meant to explain some phenomena (Lewis and Ritchie, 2003). These broad theories may help in understanding the relationship that exists or might exist between more specific constructs or variables of interest for individual research projects (Davidoff et al., 2015).

Research framework can embody both the combination of both a theory and the way we use that theory to shape research designs and the expected outcomes of the study (Imenda, 2014). A framework, in general, is a descriptive explanation of a given problem that uses the concepts of interest to explain why and how specific problems exist, in addition to the expected relationships between those concepts and variables (Beaudry et al., 2016). Therefore, frameworks can help researchers to understand their own intentions and expectations when it

comes to conducting research. They also can play a role in guiding the development of research questions, research design, the selection of data collection methods and the best analytical approaches to provide answers for research questions. Researchers cannot prove frameworks regardless of whether they are conceptual or theoretical (Imenda, 2014). They can provide proof that may support and strengthen the frameworks by demonstrating the existing evidence of the relationships between the variables. This seems to be consistent with the logic of hypothesis testing in quantitative research.

Conceptual and theoretical frameworks have cyclical relationships; each type of framework is informed by and then informs the other type of framework. In practice, the difference between the conceptual and the theoretical frameworks is their scope and specificity (Imenda, 2014). Generally, a theoretical framework can be more abstract and quite broad in its scope. Theoretical frameworks typically attempt to explain the relationships between broad general ideas and constructs. In contrast, a conceptual framework can be more specific, it typically proposes an explanation for the relationships between specific concepts or the variables that researchers may use to measure the more abstract constructs of interest. Therefore, whether researchers are relying on a theoretical or a conceptual framework, they both can provide models that can help in interpreting the results and then draw conclusions about findings (Imenda, 2014).

Theoretical and conceptual frameworks are not competing against each other. They can contain complimentary ideas and structures that impose a structure for the research problem and study. All research projects have a conceptual framework guiding their design (Rocco and Plakhotnil, 2009). Researchers can be explicit about their conceptual models; however, when they write about a theoretical framework and then describe their variables and methods, their conceptual framework is automatically implied (Jabareen, 2009). In general, it is helpful for researchers to develop a construct map or a visual model of the conceptual framework as they decide the aims of their study and begin to think about the research questions. Moreover, conceptual frameworks can still be a great way to communicate researchers' intentions and this may help the committee to understand the researchers' aims so that they can provide them with the maximum amount of support for your development (Smyth, 2004).

During the last decade, studies about international students, which offer insight into their lived experiences abroad became more and more popular (Ritz, 2010; Smith and Khawaja, 2011;

Niculescu and Galalae, 2013; Chang, 2016; Heng, 2018; Jung and Kim, 2017). The scope of research on international students' experiences can be really diverse. For instance, some projects focus on the classroom contexts by providing insight to participation, interaction modes and effective learning (Abdullah et al., 2012; Ma and Wen, 2018). In addition, other studies focus on how well international students in the UK perform academically (Li et al., 2010; Glass and Westmont, 2014; Elliot et al., 2016; Nachatar Singh, 2018), while others aim at exploring International students' motivations for studying abroad (Wintre et al., 2014; Lieb, 2016; Lee, 2017).

The studies listed above offer a well-structured understanding of international students' academic life, but most of them do not address other aspects of the social experience in the host country that might impact the academic experience and their sojourn in general.

From the literature on international students' experiences, there seems to be a scarcity on the studies that employ qualitative measures when researching the lived experiences of student sojourners, as they tend to ignore the environment that frames the international experience such as globalisation trends, new technologies and political problems. Despite the wide range of research on study abroad programs, few studies have been conducted on study abroad and its relationship to identity development, and even fewer studies were conducted on North African students, especially Algerian students' cohorts. There is still a scarcity of information about how the foreign study experience affects individuals, and more qualitative studies on the contextual perspectives of student sojourners are necessary. I can argue that in this context of research, qualitative approaches can have greater contribution since they are useful to studying complex phenomena that require developing an understanding of complex situations by providing richer and diverse data (Flick, 2018). Moreover, they can examine the meaning-making processes that people within different social environments bring to their experience, which can be detected in the participants' narratives (Graci and Fivuch, 2017).

4. 7 Research questions

Research questions are the heart of Maxwell's (2004) research design and they are directly connected to all the other components of the design. In qualitative research, questions are interactive components in the research design, therefore they should not be formulated in detail before the goals and the conceptual framework are well clarified (Maxwell et al., 2015).

The research questions generally help the researcher to focus the research by relating the questions to the goals and theoretical framework. In addition, relating the research questions to the research methods and validity can guide the researcher in conducting the research. On the contrary, formulating well-detailed research questions at an early stage of the research might lead the researcher to focus on the areas of theory that are relevant to the research subject, or it may limit the researchers' focus, which can lead them to miss many important phenomena and relevant relationships.

Generally, qualitative studies use specific types of questions by which they examine specific phenomena that appear in specific contexts (Lewis, 2015). Most questions may imply an open-ended, inductive methodology to understand the connection between meanings, activities and events that the research participants are involved in (Maxwell, 2008). For instance, qualitative researchers are likely to investigate the meaning of several experiences and activities. Likewise, they can explore the relation between the context and these activities and experiences.

This research aims to explore the Algerian international students' perceptions of the impact of studying abroad on their identities, and the different adjustment strategies used during their time abroad. Investigating patterns in data about sojourn of the group, I applied and answered the following research questions:

- Question one: What are the different adjustment strategies used by Algerian PhD student sojourners to cope with the experience abroad?
- Question two: What aspects of the Algerian PhD student sojourners' identity are affected during the experience abroad and in what way?

4. 8 Research methodology

The purpose of an applied research methodology can be described as the strategy or the design that guides the researcher to choose particular methods to meet the desired consequences (Crotty, 1998). As stated earlier, choosing the epistemological philosophy can affect the choice of the theoretical perspective, in this case, it is an interpretive approach, which in turn may affect the selection of the methodology and the data collection methods (Carter and little, 2007). For instance, when a study focuses on interpreting and/or understanding a given phenomenon, the researcher is usually encouraged to employ previous knowledge and even personal experience instead of being distant from the research context. In other words, this approach

(interpretivism) can be affected by beliefs from both science and the researcher's personal interpretation of the data collected (Silverman, 2015; Willig, 2017).

One issue that researchers often face when conducting a qualitative study is pre-structuring the methods. On the one hand, structured approaches can be useful in answering questions that focus on explaining the differences between things, which guarantee the comparability of data among sources and researchers (Maxwell, 2008; Bryman, 2017). On the other hand, flexible designs appear to give greater importance to understanding the different contexts of a problem, which makes them much suitable for exploratory studies (Roller and Lavralkas, 2015). Moreover, unstructured approaches can be useful in explaining unfamiliar processes that can lead to particular conclusions, or what they call local causality (Miles et al., 2014).

According to Maxwell (2014), researchers should not fully focus on the level of pre-structuring their studies, but rather focus on the ways they are going to do it and the reasons behind their choices. For instance, researchers can utilise an open approach when collecting data, but they can use the data for confirming their hypotheses, which are based on pre-existing theories. The relationship of the researcher with the participants in the research project is inconsistent and complex and it may affect the researcher as well as other components of the research design. For example, the reciprocal impacts between the research participants, the researcher, and the encounters, which can be referred to as reflexivity, can affect the researcher's state of mind, the quality of the collected data and the ability to answer the research questions and drawing conclusions (Enosh and Ben-Ari, 2015).

4. 8.1 Sampling

In this exploratory study that aims at investigating the Algerian PhD student sojourners' identity development while living in the UK, all participants were from Algeria and they were studying at different universities in the UK. The sample was comprised of 62 respondents for the questionnaire and 10 participants for the photo-elicitation interviewing.

Purposive sampling is usually used to represent the typicality of locations, subjects and circumstances, which are systematically selected for the unique information that they will provide (Maxwell, 2014). For instance, selecting a small sample in a systematic way can provide more confidence when making conclusions about the studied population rather than using large, random, or accidental sampling variations. In addition, non-probability sampling

techniques can be valuable when researchers have insufficient time and resources. This type of sampling would be more practical when the research goal is not generating results that can be generalised applied to the whole population (Etikan et al., 2016). In this study, the chosen sample was Algerian PhD students who study in the UK. Consequently, the entire population was relatively small after fulfilling the aforementioned circumstances. Within the chosen population, I selected a representative group of participants in order to get a maximum variety of data acknowledging that findings from this research would not be generalised on the entire population.

4. 8.2 Limitations

The comparatively low number of participants that is usually associated with qualitative approaches, including thematic analysis, may indicate that the sample being unrepresentative of the target population (Denscombe, 2014). Larger sample size may provide more precise and conclusive findings that can be generalised over the whole population. I may argue that conducting fewer interviews can allow researchers to extract more details that are useful in providing a deeper understanding of any given phenomenon. The use of thematic analysis can provide great support, validity regarding the appropriateness of research tools, processes and information. Through the process of thematic analysis, researchers can ensure that the desired findings are valid when answering the research questions. The main issue I faced during the thematic analysis process is whether to consider a particular response from the data as a theme or not since there is no specific way of doing so. I had to refer to the research questions and objectives to confirm the importance of some responses and to decide their usefulness in the discussion section.

4. 9 Research methods

This study is based on the qualitative approach with a triangulation of methods including questionnaires and photo-elicitation interviews for collecting data. The mixed methods approach was defined in sociology as using more than one method for collecting data (Tashakkori and Teddlie, 2010). Nevertheless, recently, it is considered as an independent approach to social research (Flick, 2018). A mixed methods approach can be used in studies where quantitative and qualitative methods are required in relation to the same object of study (Brannen, 2017; Creswell and Clark, 2017). One of the main reasons I used multiple methods

is to extend my activities as a researcher by using more than one method in order to collect richer information about the Algerian PhD students' identity development while living abroad.

Data triangulation is very important in qualitative research since it can improve the reliability of the research findings (Denzin, 2012; Carter, et al., 2014). Triangulation is associated with using multiple methods to collect and analyse data (Flick, 2018). Different triangulation types are acknowledged to support the objectivity and reliability of the findings in research (Bureau and Anderson, 2014). There are four types of triangulation including data triangulation, which incorporates using various sources of data during a study. Sources of data can differ in time of collection, the place where the data is collected and the persons who collected the data. The second type of triangulation is the investigator triangulation where multiple researchers collect and analyse data in a study to promote reliability and credibility of the findings and to reduce potential bias. The third type of triangulation is theory triangulation that used multiple theoretical strategies for collecting and analysing data. The fourth type of triangulation is methodological triangulation, which is known as mixed-method that uses multiple methods for collecting data (Turner et al., 2017). This type of triangulation is widely used in research in which qualitative and quantitative data can be combined in one study. Researchers using methods triangulation can explore different levels of attitudes of the same situation. Triangulation of data can produce rich information and findings of a phenomenon, however, sometimes it can result in contradictory findings (Perlesz and Lindsay, 2003; O'Reilly and Parker, 2012).

Qualitative and quantitative methods should be seen as tools that may support researchers in obtaining appropriate and relevant information for specific research rather than considering them as contradictory. There are several ways of demonstrating our comprehension of different experiences and environments. Researchers may aim at answering research questions by concentrating on specific themes and categories that can organise the interview process; at the same time, the interview process may include responses and subjective interpretations that can show different versions of qualitative truths and falsities (Foucault, 1980). Qualitative research has been often questioned in terms of validity because of the multiplicity of interpretations that can be sometimes ambiguous and open-ended (Graham and Mc Dermott, 2005). Generally, researchers state that it is difficult to replicate studies, which have qualitative designs, meanwhile, quantitative approaches are popular and desired among researchers for having great validity since they offer the chance for testing and re-testing their validity (Heale and Twycross,

2015; Noble and Smith, 2015). In general, quantitative research is based on objectivist epistemology since it seeks to develop explanatory universal principles in social behaviours using statistical measures of assumptions of reality (Yilmaz, 2013).

In this study, the term method signifies the style of data collection including a questionnaire, and photo elicitation interviews, as well as the methods of analysis, including thematic analysis of the Algerian PhD students' narratives. Sometimes, the methods used for collecting data may imply specific techniques of analysis (Alexander et al., 2008). For example, surveys are usually compatible with statistical analysis, but in different cases, the data collection method does not imply the analysis technique. For example, the generated data from an interview can be analysed via thematic coding or with narrative analysis techniques (Silverman, 2016). This may suggest that research methods can be mixed at different phases of the study.

When researchers decide to triangulate methods at the data collection phase, two or more data types are expected to be generated (e.g. Data from surveys, interviews and observation). Qualitative methods like interviews, focus groups, visual methods and documentary analysis can be mixed without any of the quantitative methods (Alexander et al., 2008). For example, Bagnoli (2004) designed a participatory project that used multiple methods to research the identities of young people from Italy and England, in which research participants were considered as co-researchers and wrote weekly identity narratives. They provided the researcher with some of their favoured photos of themselves and participated in two open-ended interviews. Similarly, in this present study, mixing methods appear to stimulate more reflexivity and enthusiasm for the research participants by guiding the research project. I argue that the use of multiple methods in collecting data for this study has widened the area of research on Algerian PhD students' identity development abroad by permitting me as the researcher to access information that might have been more challenging to get without using multiple methods.

Using a mixed methods approach in this research study has many advantages, but it also comes with its own challenges. Using multiple methods in this research project took more effort, work and time. For example, each method should be undertaken correctly and separately since every method has its own requirements. The online questionnaire's aim was to present a general understanding of Algerian PhD students of their experiences of development abroad. The online questionnaire was distributed among 120 Algerian PhD students across two Facebook groups of Algerian PhD students in the UK. The link to the questionnaire contains an

information sheet and a consent form to sign before answering the question and returning it. The questionnaire data was collected and analysed after 10 days from the date of distribution. Only 62 people have responded, which make the response rate around 51.6%. All 62 respondents have signed the consent form attached to the questionnaire.

After an initial analysis of the questionnaire's data, I started the photo elicitation interviews with 10 Algerian PhD students. Findings from the questionnaire have informed questions of the interviews in order to get more detailed data about some aspects from the Algerian PhD students' experiences. This process of collecting and managing different types of data, analysing them and presenting the results was challenging since the results of every method used must be combined and integrated in a coherent way (Alexander et al., 2008). Another challenge that I faced as an international PhD student is the word count when writing the thesis. Reporting the results of one research method requires writing in sufficient depth to transmit the meaning; therefore, the more methods are used, the more complex it can get, which would necessitate increased word count (Salehi and Golafshani, 2010; Creswell and Clark, 2017).

In becoming more aware of the different variations of methodology, I realised that qualitative methods can be more suitable in exploring acculturation processes and cross-cultural interaction research. Even though previous studies appear to be beneficial in exploring an extensive range of variables related to identity and acculturation of international PhD students, I believe that methods that involve exploring personal experiences and providing detailed information about the lived experiences would be more useful in relation to this study's aim.

In this research study, the use of the questionnaire alone may be restricted when exploring the subjective experiences of Algerian PhD students, which can be complex and can comprise emotions, relationships, and social interactions. Therefore, the questionnaire was used to collect some broad data of the Algerian PhD student population in the UK about their identity development, whereas photo-elicitation interviews were used as a complementing method to provide a deep understanding of the phenomenon. The combination of these two methods appears to be appropriate in investigating cognitive and emotional aspects during different experiences of the Algerian PhD students in the UK. Using data from the questionnaire in informing and guiding the photo-elicitation interviews allowed me to be more focused and understanding in relation to the phenomenon being explored.

Utilising both quantitative and qualitative approaches in my research was more valuable in collecting data since some people may prefer expressing their views emotions using other ways of communication such as indirect communication or writing. One of the most important reasons I used a qualitative paradigm is to make use of the sensitive and detailed methods to explore the different experiences and attitudes of the Algerian PhD students in the UK, which may help in creating a clearer image about their lived experiences, challenges and attitudes.

In conclusion, I used a flexible design for this study that examines the Algerian PhD students' perceptions about whether their experiences of studying in the UK have affected their identities, in addition to the reasons that made an impact on their social and academic lives abroad. I have chosen to use methods triangulation, which according to Bagnoli (2018) is a way of increasing the reliability and validity of the findings. Since the present research project is a qualitative study, which aimed to explore different perspectives of several individuals about their experiences abroad in relation to adjustment and generating in-depth data about sojourn experiences and hybrid identity development, I believe that a combination of quantitative and qualitative traditions and techniques including a questionnaire and photo-elicitation interviews, which can generate broad and rich data is needed in order to meet the specific needs of such research circumstances.

4. 10 Questionnaires and surveys

Many Scholars argue that surveys can generate different kinds of data that range from attitudes, values, personal experiences and behaviours (Robson and Mc-Cartan, 2016; Bryman, 2017; Brace, 2018). Surveys can generate data from a particular population using postal questionnaires and online surveys such as e-mails, or survey websites (Brace, 2018).

Some researchers have strong views about the importance as well as the limitations of using questionnaires as data collection tools. On the one hand, Robson and Mc-Cartan (2016) argue that all types of surveys generate information that, in one way or another, are affected by some of the characteristics of the participants, such as personality, memory and motivation. Moreover, survey methods are unable to precisely describe the respondents' beliefs and attitudes (ibid, p. 248). For postal questionnaires, in particular, McGuirk and O'Neill (2016) state that this tool can be criticised as it usually has a low response rate. In addition, it is difficult to determine whether the research sample represents the general population or not (Patten, 2016;

Krosnick, 2017). Moreover, ambiguities, misunderstandings and dishonesty of the participants are usually difficult to be detected (Robson and Mc-Cartan, 2016; Brace, 2018).

On the other hand, when it comes to the study of attitudes, motives and beliefs, surveys are proved to be a simple method that goes directly to the point. Questionnaires are believed to be an applicable tool for collecting data from populations with significant numbers, and findings from that data can be generalizable (Robson and Mc Cartan, 2016). In addition, many researchers argue that questionnaires are tremendously useful for gathering large amounts of information without spending so much effort or time and they assure the anonymity of the participants (Patten, 2016; Robson and Mc Cartan, 2016; Brace, 2018; Krosnick, 2017).

In this research, I started collecting the data using a website-based questionnaire as a secondary method. I believe that designing the surveys on websites permits a great degree of flexibility and creativity.

Similar to other survey methods, online questionnaires can also face many challenges including security issues, computer literacy, internet access and other technical errors (Smyth et al., 2004; Hesse-Biber and Griffin, 2012). Another challenge of this tool is the uniformity of the questionnaires since the appearance might be affected by different aspects such as the screen size, operating systems, the web browser, and internet speed. For instance, many researchers reported high rates of non-response as well as non-completion of surveys because of the excessive length of the questionnaire or its layout and presentation (Smyth et al., 2004; Denscombe, 2009; Farrell and Peterson, 2010; Dillman, 2011).

Although there are many disadvantages for using the web-based questionnaires (Bell et al., 2018), yet I believe that their advantages make them a worthy technique for data collection. They appear to be very functional in covering large sample sizes across wide geographical areas with a very limited effect on the cost (Karpf, 2012). In addition, typical data collection can take a short period including the follow-up contact that can increase the response rate (Kaplowitz et al., 2004; Ferrell and Peterson, 2010). Moreover, I found out that web-based surveys can offer a high degree of flexibility in design by integrating automated skip patterns that can decrease the confusion of the respondents (Dillman, 2011). Furthermore, visual aids such as diagrams, pictures and videos can be easily designed and included in the questionnaires (Smyth et al., 2004).

4. 11 Photo-elicitation interviews (PEI)

The visual aspect can always be present in our personal life, conversations, and even in academic work (Pink, 2007). It can be linked to different identities, narratives, cultures, history, time, space, place, reality and truth (Pink, 2015). Therefore, ethnographic research is likewise possible to be associated with visual technologies through images, viewpoints and experiences. Photo-elicitation interviewing (PEI) is a qualitative research method that I used in which participants took photographs, which I used them during interview sessions to elicit and discuss the participants' different experiences. It is not a new method in social sciences; it originated from visual sociology, along with many methods such as photo-essays and documentary film (Harper, 2002).

The debate about whether or not including the visual aspect of the anthropological research evolved during the 1960s (Pink, 2006). Initially, the integration of photographs as a research method was made by Collier (1957) who was a member of a research team at Cornell University, Canada. Their project was to examine the effects of different aspects of the technological and economic changes on the communities' changing mental health, in the Maritime Provinces. The research team have found difficulties in exploring different aspects of the phenomenon using conventional data collection methods such as surveys and interviews, which made them try a new creative way of interviewing by using photographs. Collier and Collier (1986) highlighted the usefulness of the visual aspect in sharpening the memories of participants during interviews. For instance, Collier (1957) concluded that the use of the visual aspect during the interviews has decreased the amount of confusion between interviewers and interviewees and it helped in stimulating the participants' memory and emotional statements about their life. After publishing several works using photo interviewing, Collier and Collier (1986) became a major reference in visual anthropology and sociology. During that period, some social scientists criticised the visual method of collecting data of being subjective, unmethodical and non-demonstrative (Pink, 2013).

The use of visual methods, such as photo-elicitation interviews, in qualitative research is becoming more and more popular among social scientists (Reid et al., 2018). Photographs can be considered as a method to reveal how participants and researchers construct the meaning of lived experiences (Torre and Murphy, 2015; McCloy et al., 2014; Langmann and Pick, 2018). In addition to analysing the photos, researchers that use PEI can analyse the participants'

reactions to the photos in order to reveal their values and perceptions (Hillman et al., 2018; Jarret and Coba-Rodriguez, 2018; McGraw et al., 2018). Moreover, many researchers agree that the use of PEI acknowledges the participants as partners in research as they engage in the data collection and interpretation with their ideas and viewpoints (Harley and Langdon, 2018; Reid et al., 2018).

Several researchers use PEI in action research to explore how people can identify, represent and enhance their community through specific photographic techniques (e.g.; Baxter et al., 2015; Vannini et al., 2015; Sawyer et al., 2018). Moreover, using visual methods can enable participants to generate critical knowledge and deep reflections through the discussion of their photographs (Bell, 2016; Gray et al., 2018; Libenberg, 2018; Wilhoit, 2019).

Visual methods have also been used in educational settings as a valuable pedagogical tool (Torre and Murphy, 2015; Hamilton, 2016; Latz et al, 2016; Mount, 2018). For instance, using PEI in the classroom setting can encourage more reflection and interaction from the students and it can provide teachers with a better understanding of the various difficulties faced by the students (Rogers, 2016; Danker et al., 2016). Furthermore, the process of visual research methods exposes the students to various experiences and viewpoints, which make them more self-reflective (Brand et al., 2016; Mount, 2018 Stupans et al., 2019).

4. 11.1 The process of photo-elicitation interview (PEI)

The fundamental idea of the PEI method is implementing photos in the process of an interview (Biag, 2014; Banks and Zeitlyn, 2015; Sanoff, 2016; Allen, 2017). Studies using the PEI vary in the sampling techniques, data collection resources, how photos are used during the interview and the way photos are analysed (Torre and Murphy, 2015). A general process of PEI starts first with selecting a research topic, then identifying and selecting the research participants. The third step is taking pictures or asking participants to take pictures following some instructions that guide them. The fourth step is using the collected photos to control and enrich data generated from interviews. The final step is analysing data and reporting findings (Torre and Murphy, 2015).

4. 11.1.1 Sampling in photo elicitation interview

The sampling technique selected is a fundamental element to any research project. According to the literature, PEI studies employ the different sampling methods used in qualitative research. For instance, Corrigan-Doyle et al., (2016) use convenience sampling in their study exploring the home as a system for happiness and sustainability. Snowball sampling is another method used by Elkins and Shimek (2016) in their study assessing citizenship, ethical behaviour and other factors on campus. Moreover, Moes (2017) explores the different identities of various groups of people in relation to the political and geographical understandings of Europe through photo-elicitation interviews by using the maximum variation sampling method. In this exploratory study, I used purposive sampling to investigate the Algerian PhD student sojourners' identity development while living in the UK. The sample comprises of 62 respondents for the questionnaire and ten (10) participants for the photo-elicitation interviewing.

4. 11.1.2 Taking pictures

Unlike the conventional approach PEI where the researchers are the ones who take and select pictures, current approaches to PEI, including Auto-driven interview, allow the participants to be active members in the research project (Ford et al., 2017; Jones, 2018). In other cases, researchers might ask the participants to select photos from historical archives (e.g. Torre and Murphy, 2015; Gordon and Kurzwelly, 2018), or from social media (e.g. Hood and Reid, 2018; Laws et al., 2018), and Maps (e.g. Moore-Cherry et al., 2015).

I advised the participants to provide photographs according to the following categories emphasising that all the photographs will only be used during the interview and none of them will be reproduced for educational or any purposes other than the interview sessions.

- a. Photos of daily routines.
- e. Photos of weekends.
- b. Photos of social and cultural activities.
- c. Photos of academic activities.

In this study, I decided to give the participants the freedom to take or select photos that will be used during the interview sessions. I instructed them to provide photographs that they own on social media, phone or camera. I also stated that the pictures that they provide for the interview will be viewed only by the researcher and will be stored in a password-protected system to be used during the interview session. As stated in the ethics forms and approved by the ethics committee, I did not include the photographs in the analysis and discussion of the findings to avoid potential consent issues.

4.11.1.3 Collecting photos

Since it is an auto driven interview, I set some criteria for the research participants to follow when they take photographs. For instance, I advised the participants to take pictures that represent their experiences and/or emotions in different contexts (Bates et al., 2017; Armstrong-James et al., 2018).

4.11.1.4 Interview and photo manipulation

After the pictures were taken and sent to me through email before the interview sessions, I tried to integrate them into the interviewing process. For example, I went through all the pictures and selected some specific photographs shown at the beginning of an interview session (e.g. Pachmayer and Andereck, 2017; Palmer and Furler, 2018). In some cases, the researcher may ask the participants to categorise or to select the pictures that influenced them the most (e.g. Pitterson, et al., 2016; Boucher, 2018), which I found very effective at the beginning of the interview sessions to break the ice and engage the participants. Other researchers have asked the participants to produce written narratives about the selected photos (e.g. Byrne et al., 2016), which I thought might be unnecessary, since the participants in this study were asked to describe the photos and state the reason why they selected them.

4.11.1.5 Understanding photos

Many researchers believe that photos can help knowing how the photographer and/or viewers understand the world and construct meaning, but they use different ways for viewing photos. For instance, some scholars view photographs as a visual record of different events and as a mean of observation (Carins et al., 2016; Parsons and Pettinger, 2017; Meyer and Youngs, 2017). Other researchers argue that photographs are the result of many subjective choices made

by the photographer (Byrne et al., 2016; Zappavigna, 2016; Svensson, 2017). Photographs can produce multiple interpretations, which can be related to the personal experiences of viewers and the contexts of photos (Shohel, 2012; Lobinger, 2015). Studies using the PEI method tend to use qualitative methods of analysis, yet researchers diverge in their analytical design to whether including photos in the analysis of the transcripts of interviews or not. Other researchers prefer to analyse photos in addition to interview transcripts to a better and deeper understanding of the phenomenon they examine. Moreover, photos can be considered as communication tools that contain several symbolic characteristics that can be analysed to reveal the psychological state of the photographer using a process called photo-interviewing (Hung, 2018; Langmann and Pick, 2018). Researchers tend to analyse the symbolic characteristics such as the background, the foreground, what is in the pictures and what is not in the pictures (Wilhoit, 2019). Other researchers analyse the symbolic representation by grouping the photos to identify patterns between participants (Langmann and Pick, 2018; Musselman et al., 2018; Ndione and Remy, 2018). In this study, I considered the photographs as a reference point, which were used in the interview process rather than an independent objective image of reality (Pyyr, 2015; King et al., 2017; Miller, 2018), mainly because of the large amount and variety of data generated by the various methods in this research.

4.11.2 Advantages

In social research, there may be cases where there is a power imbalance between researchers and research participants. Generally, researchers are seen as experts in their fields whereas participants are considered as objects of study (Torry and Murphey, 2015). In contrast, recent studies, including this one, report that using PEI can decrease power imbalance between researchers and participants by focusing on the participants' experiences and knowledge and giving them the freedom to take and select photos for the research (O'Brien, 2013; Boucher, 2018; Reid et al., 2018; Richardson and Thompson, 2018; Walton, 2017). Moreover, discussion between two or more people about the meaning of photographs creates a sense of collaboration between them (Pitterson et al., 2016; Bedi and Webb, 2017; Healy and Fitzgibbon, 2018; Hollinrake et al., 2019).

Studies using PEI generate additional participants' data that can help researchers in understanding the different perspectives of participants (Leonard and McKnight, 2015; Pachmayer and Andereck, 2017; Patricia et al., 2017; Mills et al., 2018). Participants can

provide deeper reflections when talking about photos that triggering their memories (Dockett et al., 2017; Bornnioli et al., 2018; Gray et al., 2018). Moreover, other researchers argue that photos can highlight important ideas and topics that the participants want to bring into light (Leonard and McKnight, 2015). For example, topics, such as sexuality (Joy and Numer, 2017; Bowling et al., 2018), neighbourhoods (Hanson et al., 2016; Sawyer et al., 2018) and chemotherapy (Bates et al., 2017; Pini et al., 2019). Furthermore, visual data can increase the validity and reliability of research by triangulating it with the data generated by interviews and/or observation (Boucher, 2018).

Another advantage of using PEI in this present study is building rapport with research participants as research partners during interviews, which is proven to reduce anxiety and produce richer data (Pachmayer and Andereck, 2017; Patrici et al., 2017). The familiarity of participants with the photo materials understudy may reduce the awkwardness of interviews (Mullen et al., 2016; Biswas and Gerrard, 2018). This is confirmed by many studies, which reported that using PEI can help participants feeling more comfortable and less of an object of study since it can shift the focus from the interviewee to the photos (Pachmayer and Andereck, 2017; Gautam et al., 2018; Rodriguez et al., 2018; Willig, 2017).

4.11.3 Ethical issues with visual research

In this section, I will present some of the ethical issues that arise related to consent, confidentiality and anonymity. I will also provide some examples of the ways in which these issues can be handled.

Any research project should contain ethical principles that govern the data collection phase and protect researchers and participants, and this research study is no exception. Good visual research must guarantee protection to researchers and to the institutions employing them requires obtaining consent that clarifies the different purposes for which photos are going to be used and issues of copyright to the research participants (Miller, 2015; Pink, 2015). Issues of copyright emerge if the researchers decide to include the photos taken by participants in publications (Healy and Fitzgibbon, 2018). Shohel (2012) argues that it is the researcher's responsibility to raise the participants' awareness of how their photographs are going to be used. To deal with this issue, I provided the research participants with a consent form and an information sheet that clarifies the purpose of their participation stating that the photographs will only be used during the interview sessions and will not be disseminated. Such photographs

cannot be disseminated even if they come with a signed written consent that provides copyright to the researcher. In such a complex situation, researchers must be cautious when deciding to use photos that may identify some individuals and put them at risk or harm or moral criticism (Wiles et al., 2011). Choosing not to include the photographs in the analysis and discussion of the finding in this study was to prevent another potential consent problem when participants take photographs that identify non-participants who did not agree to take part of the research project or who may not know the different purposes of using these photos (Rose, 2007; Asiedu et al., 2018; Edmondson et al., 2018).

4.11.4 Anonymity and confidentiality

Another central issue in visual research is keeping anonymity and privacy in relation to visual materials, which can be a problematic dilemma. Many scholars emphasise that the researcher must anticipate future issues associated with the use of the collected visual data of individuals, institutions and communities in the different publications (Gubrium and Harper, 2016; Bell et al., 2018). It is equally important for researchers to understand the social, political and cultural contexts in which the visual data will be presented (Pink, 2013). To address these ethical issues, some researchers prefer to use the photographs by having the people identified in the pictures to sign a consent form (Ruiz-Casares and Thompson, 2014; Harley and Langdon, 2018; Miller, 2018). Other researchers use specific software to modify the photos by obscuring facial features or by blocking out eyes and faces (Allen, 2015; Mok et al., 2014).

The case for places is similar to individuals since many studies include photos of locations as well as of people (Banks and Zeitlyn, 2015; Jarrett and Coba-Rodriguez, 2018). Even if alternative names are given to locations, it is still possible to locate them by simply checking the study settings (Wiles et al., 2011).

Researchers who collaborate with research participants aim to empower them by allowing them representing themselves in the photographs and commenting on them before publication or presentation (Azzarito, 2016). It is important that implications such as anonymisation and identification need to be carefully studied and discussed with research participants (Torres and Warr, 2016; Vaughan, 2016). For achieving these aims, researchers must assure to identify and explain to the participants the different implications of using photographs in various publications (Smith et al., 2018).

Using the photo-elicitation interview in research, researchers tend to describe the generated photographs with verbal narratives, but no further analysis is done on the images. Images can be hard to analyse since they can mean different things to different people depending on the context (Graneheim et al., 2017). Moreover, analysing photographs only may misrepresent the participants and their stories in relation to the photographs such as the context and the process and the reason behind taking certain pictures (Pachmayer and Andereck, 2017).

4.12 Analysis

The main aim of this research is exploring the different acculturative experiences and their effects on Algerian PhD student sojourners' identity development in the UK. In this section, I review the methodology used to investigate and analyse these qualitative variables using thematic analysis, which aims at identifying, analysing and interpreting patterns of meanings and themes (Braun et al., 2016). The analysis of the data in this research was mainly guided by the research questions and Bronfenbrenner's model of development as a theoretical framework (Alvesson and Sköldbberg, 2017). Deductive thematic analysis principles were used to answer the following research questions:

Question one: What are the different adjustment strategies used by Algerian PhD student sojourners to cope with the experience abroad?

Question two: What aspects of the Algerian PhD student sojourners' identity are affected during the experience abroad and in what way?

4.12.1 Thematic analysis

Choosing a qualitative methodology in this research is guided by the need to illustrate the Algerian PhD student sojourners' experiences that can be challenging to understand using quantitative approaches. In order to exploring the development of a hybrid identity of Algerian PhD students while living in the UK, it was important to understand their social background, so that they can express their views and viewpoints of the different experiences as they see them. The main focus of this work is to explore the Algerian PhD students' acculturation processes and identity development through analysing their narratives and attitudes. I suggest that thematic analysis can serve as a useful tool to illuminate and explain the different processes of social construction. This qualitative method of thematic analysis is based on creating codes

and themes from the data. The deductive approach starts with ideas from the framework and related theories and uses the data to confirm or disprove them (Mayer, 2015). The used process of a deductive approach emphasises the research goal and is guided by the research questions and the theoretical framework used in the research. One main step of the deductive thematic analysis is known as coding; it is the selection of certain aspects of the data rather than considering the whole set. The process of thematic analysis focus on examining analytically the narratives by dividing the text into smaller units called codes before assembling them into categories that share the same themes (Sparker, 2007; Sandelowski and Leeman, 2012; Vismoradi et al., 2016; Flick, 2018).

Thematic analysis has been acknowledged as a method in its own basis (Braun and Clarke, 2014). This method can be used in identifying, analysing and reporting different themes extracted from qualitative data sets. This would indicate that researchers can include their own interpretation of the research topic that enables them to organise and describe the data in great details to improve their understanding of the studied phenomenon. The notion of labelling the emerging themes can be ambiguous and sometimes incorrectly oversimplifying the process of thematic analysis by ignoring the active role of identifying and organising the ideas into codes and themes, which are the ways in which researchers interact with the data to find answers to their research questions (Braun and Clarke, 2014).

I have chosen to use a deductive thematic analysis to answer the previously asked questions. I believe that understanding complex processes like identity formation, negotiation and development in relation to the lived experiences abroad. This method of analysis is widely used within the field of psychology and other fields, but there is no clear agreement on how it is acknowledged (e.g. Smith et al., 2017; Edmondson et al., 2018; Musselman et al., 2018; Sawyer et al., 2018). The term thematic refers to themes, which can be defined as patterns in the data that can identify and organise different observations, which may interpret aspects of the studied phenomenon (Terry et al., 2017). Both implicit and explicit ideas in the data can be considered during the process of analysis (Vaismoradi et al., 2013). Researchers can rely on previous theoretical framework when generating themes, which is known as deductive analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2014).

In this research, I did analyse the data from the photo-elicitation interviews aiming for answering the aforementioned research questions, but at the same time, I did not neglect other

forms of data, which I thought could be important. This approach allowed me to look at the data in a holistic way rather than just providing answers to the research questions.

4.12.2 Thematic analysis process

It is common among qualitative methods that data collection and data analysis take part in a simultaneous time, which gives more depth to the data analysis process (Vaismoradi *et al.*, 2013). Nevertheless, in this research project, all data were collected before starting the analysis process.

In this study, the used process of thematic analysis in this research study can be demonstrated in table 3.

Table 3: The process of thematic analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2006)

Phase	Description
1. Familiarising with data	Transcribing data, reading and rereading the data, noting down initial ideas.
2. Generating initial codes	Coding interesting features of the data systematically across the entire data set, collating data relevant to each code.
3. Searching for themes	Collating codes into potential themes, gathering all data relevant to each potential theme.
4. Reviewing themes	Checking if the themes work in relation to the coded extracts and the entire data set, generating a thematic map.
5. Defining and naming themes	Ongoing analysis for refining the specifics of each theme and the overall story that the analysis tells, generating clear definitions and names for each theme.
6. Producing the report	The final opportunity for analysis. Selection of vivid, compelling extract examples, final analysis of selected extracts, relating back of the analysis to the research questions and literature, producing a report of the analysis.

Phase 1: Familiarising with data

A good way for doing that is via the process of transcribing the data. Some researchers argue that data transcription should be considered essential in the process of data analysis (Bird, 2005; Clarke and Braun, 2013; Gale et al., 2013; Terry et al., 2017). Throughout this stage, I devoted

close attention to data transcription since it may enhance the interpretative skills needed to analyse the data (Kings et al., 2018). This step of getting familiarised with the data is a crucial one in both approaches, deductive or inductive and it must be done in a thorough manner. After this, data must be transcribed, which is another way to be more familiar with the data. The transcripts must be accurate to their source of origin and must keep the same original meaning of the provided information.

Phase 2: Generating initial codes

After having a good idea of what the data is about, I started identifying units of analysis. It might be useful to break the data into useful chunks such as individual words, phrases, sentences, paragraphs. Any meaningful chunk of data can be considered as a valid code (Boyatzis, 1998). The process of coding depends on whether the researcher is using an inductive approach, where themes are established from the data, or a deductive approach, as in the case of this study, where I used previously generated themes from the used theoretical framework (Braun and Clarke, 2006). The data was analysed with some specific goals attempting to answer the research questions that guide the coding process.

Coding can be done manually, by using highlighters and writing notes on the text analysed, or with the help of computer software (Leech and Onwuegbuzie, 2007). In this study, the coding process was done using a computer programme NVivo, which helped in facilitating the whole process and resulted in saving more time. The traditional way of organising and analysing the qualitative data is usually time-consuming and requires intensive workforce. In order to reduce that effort, it is important that researchers make use of computer software such as NVivo so that they would work “more methodically, more thoroughly, and more attentively” (Bazeley and Jackson, 2013).

Phase 3: Searching for themes

After coding the entire dataset, a long list of codes is identified. Through the generated codes, themes are created and arranged, then codes will be organised according to the themes. At this stage, I had to analyse and sort all the various codes into potential themes by using visual representations, which was beneficial in exploring relationships between codes, themes and the different levels of themes (Braun and Clarke, 2006). At the end of this stage, a collection of several themes and sub-themes is gathered.

Phase 4: Reviewing themes

At this stage, some themes might be discarded for the lack of supporting data, while other separate themes might be collapsed to form a new theme. For reviewing and refining themes, I started the reviewing process at the level of the coded data transcripts by checking the coherence of the ideas in each theme (Braun et al., 2014). Some themes needed reorganising or recreating since they did not appear to be coherent. I then formed a thematic map including all the candidate themes that appear to fit together. At the second level of this stage, I checked the validity of individual themes in relation to the whole data (Boyatzis, 1998). At the end of this phase, I developed a good understanding of the established themes, the relationships among the themes and the relationship between the themes and data.

Phase 5: Defining and naming themes

In this phase, I was able to identify the aspects that constitute each theme in addition to identifying each theme as well as the relationship among themes. This was done by writing a detailed analysis about each individual theme and its relationship with the data and the research questions (Vaismoradi et al., 2013). At the end of this stage, I was able to assign working titles and names to the themes in the final analysis.

Phase 6: Producing the report

At this stage, I formed the report of the analysis which contains a description of the themes within the data with supporting examples such as quotes from interviews. In addition, I constructed analytic narratives from the themes, sub-themes and codes.

It is worth noticing that at every stage of the thematic analysis process, data needs to be evaluated within its original context and following the research aims and questions. At the end of this stage, the final version of coding should appear as similar as possible the initial set of the data, which demands a continuous reviewing and changes during the analysis (Howitt and Cramer, 2007; Braun and Clarke, 2006).

4.12.3 Advantages of thematic analysis

Using the thematic analysis in this research study has several advantages such as the ease and flexibility of this process. Thematic analysis is considered as a flexible method since it can be

compatible with different paradigms, such as participatory research, essentialist and constructionist paradigms and can produce detailed and complex results (Braun et al., 2013).

This type of analysis is popular for analysing large data sets providing a general analysis and providing a comprehensive description of the analysis process. Through identifying patterns and themes from the data, this method can be useful in providing insights from the data as well as providing similarities and differences within the data (Braun and Clarke, 2006; Javadi and Zarea, 2016). As for early career researchers with no experience of qualitative research, thematic analysis can be a relatively easy and quick method to learn and do. For instance, it can summarise the most important features of data, which can provide an opportunity for researchers to highlight similarities and differences across the data set. Moreover, it permits researchers to make social as well as psychological interpretations of data, which can lead to unexpected results and visions. Finally, it may be useful for producing qualitative analyses suited to informing policy development.

4.12.4 Disadvantages of thematic analysis

Flexibility can be seen as both an advantage and a disadvantage since dealing with a broad range of data can be considered as an advantage but sometimes it might be hard to control all the aspects of data, which makes it hard to focus on the research aspects (Braun and Clarke, 2006). Another disadvantage for thematic analysis is that it has a more of a descriptive nature that it needs to be combined with a theoretical framework that promotes the analytical nature of analysis (Holloway and Todres, 2003; Braun and Clarke, 2006).

4.12.5 Trustworthiness

Even though studies using a qualitative approach became more popular in the past few decades (Borochowitz, 2005), qualitative methods have not been accepted in some fields. Qualitative studies that are built on the post-modern approach stress the relationship between the researcher and the participants that result in the co-construction of reality and meaning (Guillemin and Gillam, 2004). Regardless of the differences between the above-mentioned approaches, many researchers argue that qualitative studies must ensure that findings should be trustworthy via applying some procedures for assessing the quality of the work (Lincoln and Guba, 1985; Creswell, 1998; Creswell and Miller, 2000; Connelly, 2016; Padgett, 2016; Smith and McGannon, 2018).

Unlike in quantitative research, rigour in qualitative research does not mean a set of standards and procedures that limit its flexibility, it is rather increasing the ethical responsibility of the researcher in reflecting thoughts, feelings and experiences of the participants (Gambrill, 1995; Cope, 2014). Moreover, researchers are encouraged to be transparent in reporting complications during the data collection by providing possible explanations (Levitt et al., 2018).

In this study, describing the research findings in an authentic way that reflects the participants' description was used to overcome some threats to trustworthiness such as bias and reactivity (Padgett, 1998; Noble and Smith, 2015). For instance, during data collection, I had to encourage the participants to be frank in their responses since there are no wrong answers by debriefing them before the data collection takes place. In addition, I made sure that participants must be aware of their right to leave the research or to withdraw their consent at any time. During the data analysis, I made sure to read the transcripts several times before interpreting them. After producing the themes, I had to discuss them with my supervisor to minimise the researcher bias during the data interpretation. Another strategy that I implemented to ensure the trustworthiness of this study's findings is the inclusion of the participants own words in the discussion of the findings.

4.12.6 Reflexivity

Qualitative methodologies acknowledge that the researcher's background knowledge and beliefs may impact the research process and results. For instance, Medico and Santiago-Delefosse (2014) argue that meaning construction in qualitative research is a cooperative process that considers both experiences of the participants and those of the researcher. In order to understand the participants' viewpoints about their own experiences and successfully interpret them, I had to use the process reflexivity in which I acknowledge my different beliefs and biases (Probst, 2015; Raheim et al., 2016). Accept the fact that I may be influencing the research process and interpretation of data can limit my influence as a researcher by acknowledging the existence of such influence since it is impossible to eliminate (Goldstein, 2017; Stenner et al., 2017). Moreover, reflexive practices are believed to reinforce the transparency and trustworthiness of qualitative research (Roose et al., 2015; Tuval-Mashiach, 2017; Welch, 2017).

Conclusion

The purpose of this qualitative study is to explore the various views and experiences of the Algerian international doctoral students in the UK concerning identity development and adjustment strategies. Data from the questionnaire was used to provide initial information, which later was used to inform the interview questions. The visual data from the photographs provided during the interview sessions was only used to help the participants feeling comfortable during the interview. I believe that the use of a questionnaire and photo-elicitation interviews to generate data is best suited to this study since the combination of the two methods allows overcoming the disadvantages of each method by reaching a large number of participants and generating more detailed information about the phenomenon. The use of thematic analysis process provided a great deal of flexibility when dealing with a complex phenomenon such as identity development abroad. The qualitative approach may have many disadvantages, but the implementation of strategies such as researcher reflexivity and addressing issues such as researcher bias aimed to minimise their impact on the quality of this study.

Chapter 5: Findings

Introduction

This study aims at exploring the views of Algerian doctoral students about their identity development and the different strategies they used to cope with the different cultural, social and scholar contexts in the UK. In this chapter, I will present the results of my research after analysing data from an open-ended question from 62 respondents on an online survey and ten (10) interviews. The analysis process would reflect the aims of the research, exploring the Algerian PhD students' perceptions about identity and the relation between their experience abroad and identity development. The use of NVivo was beneficial in organising the large amounts of textual data from the open-ended question and the transcribed answers from the interview sessions. Finding then are organised into themes, which will be presented and supported with extracts cited from the responses later in this chapter.

5.1 Emerging themes from the open-ended question and the photo elicitation interviews (PEI)

Thematic analysis is defined as a search for themes that appear to be important to the description of the studied phenomenon (Daly et al., 1997). The process of identifying themes starts by thoroughly reading and re-reading the dataset (Braun and Clarke, 2014). Patterns within the data are recognised and the themes are then analysed according to the chosen method of analysis.

In this research, I used a deductive approach based on the research questions and the literature review.

This section introduces interpretations of Algerian PhD student sojourners' data which was generated from an open-ended question from the questionnaire and from photo elicitation interviews. Their views are necessary to draw insights into their hybrid identity development during their sojourn and their acculturative experiences during the time they spent in the UK. The data was critically interpreted by using deductive thematic analysis, which aim at organising the data into themes and connecting the most significant ones to the research questions. For instance, when ideas are shared and discussed by several respondents, I believe that it is worth to be explored and backed up by examples from the data. Additionally, unusual

or unexpected ideas might appear from the data and including them in the analysis could have a positive impact on the research quality.

The selected examples illustrate the occurring codes and themes from the data and help understanding and answering the research questions. The analysis of the participants' responses was guided by a mixed process of deductive and inductive thematic analysis and by the research questions. Other significant themes emerging from the data were also explored and exposed. I used NVivo software during the data analysis process, which relieved me of the burden that comes along with manual coding of the textual data. I ended up collapsing some potential themes together into a distinctive and coherent set of themes and then moved to the next stage where I reviewed the themes in relation to the entire data set. I read all the data to make sure that the themes cover the entire data set and that they are relevant in relation to my research questions. Each theme was supported with quotations from the participants that are most representative of the research findings. This gives voice to the participants while reinforcing the transparency of the research.

I used examples from the open-ended question, which is the only form of data from the questionnaire, and interviews. The examples from the interviews are the ones with names in brackets, while examples from the open-ended question are the ones in italics with no names at the end.

The findings have been classified into these following themes, which are represented as the following:

- **Feeling frustrated.** I examined the data from the questionnaire and interviews in relation to the participants' reactions to cultural differences and the feelings associated with that.
 - **Feeling like a stranger.**
 - **These are my best buddies.**
- **Becoming a better version of myself.** I looked into the participants' responses in relation to their experiences in the UK. : In this theme, I analysed the instances where the Algerian PhD students expressed their satisfaction with life in the UK.
 - **Feeling more open.**
 - **Religion and identity negotiation.**

- **Feeling more comfortable**
- **Feeling powerful and autonomous.**
- **My life as an academic:** I analysed the Algerian PhD students' responses in relation to the different academic contexts. All participants referred to their positive and negative experiences related to academic life in the UK, and the relationship with staff and supervisors.
 - **The PhD life is very hard for me.**
 - **Engaging in academic activities.**
 - **My relationship with supervisors, staff and academics.**

5.1.1 Feeling frustrated

Several participants from the photo elicitation interviews referred to some of the interactions they had with the host nationals where they had strong emotions. Annoyance, frustration and vulnerability were significant when they were talking about some pictures of their experiences in the UK.

Being around the town or in the student accommodation, even in the university, many participants felt annoyed how host nationals or other international students looked at them and interacted with them. For instance, female participants who wear hijab stated that they felt annoyed in different settings around their place of residence:

When I firstly arrived here, there was not that much Muslim or veiled girls, especially in the university. Some people find it weird, I can tell from their eyes how they look at me. Some of them just tried to avoid me. (Selma)

Similarly, one participant described her first day at the student accommodation where she used to live:

It was my first day in my new accommodation and people started to look at me in a weird way because I was wearing my veil and I am Muslim and it's the same moment of terrorist attacks in Paris. (Ahlam)

Being in Scotland for the first time, Sara had a hard time adapting to the new culture and especially to the English language:

In this country or at university, I feel frustrated and hesitated to introduce myself because I don't know those people, I don't know those lecturers. In addition, I have a problem with the English language since it is not my first language. Sometimes, I am afraid of making mistakes in front of the audience...

(Sara)

Nadia is another participant who talked about her feeling of frustration because she could not understand host nationals using Scottish accent when interacting with her:

The Scottish accent is very hard to understand, and I do have some Scottish friends, at the very first days I couldn't understand anything, I just reply by yes.

(Nadia)

From a linguistic point of view, participants had a general understanding of the English language; however, they did not have much knowledge about the Scottish accent upon first arriving to Scotland.

Participants demonstrated that language is a fundamental aspect of culture and identity. In the context of this study, Algerian PhD student sojourners revealed that they studied different languages including Arabic, Berber, French, and English. However, they also mentioned that this experience abroad was their first time ever to live in a foreign country and that they faced several issues related to language use either within academia or their social life. This division created interesting data despite the difficulty to generate a common theme due to the different responses. For example, Algerian PhD students in the UK may tend consider English as a way to communicate with the world. For instance, Ali states: *“I always introduce myself as a PhD student in English language, because the more knowledgeable you are the more people will try to approach you in a good way thus they know who you are”*. However, when being with members from the home culture, they tend to use their mother tongue as a strategy for preserving their Algerian cultural identity in a multicultural environment. For example, Nadia stated: *“I believe that the fact that I cannot speak my native language at all is annoying sometimes. Because I feel the need to use as it makes feel close to who I am.”*

This linguistic environmental shift was very noticeable to them, as they were still learning how to successfully establish communication and understanding the Scottish accent. The proximal processes that took place during this time included the process of “acquiring new knowledge

and know-how” and the process of “engaging in... intellectual... activities that become increasingly complex over time” (Bronfenbrenner, 2000, p. 130).

Selma expressed how stressed they were at the beginning of their journey. Feeling unable to fulfil simple daily activities made them feel very less of themselves and their capabilities.

Everything was different, people, cars, busses, the speech. I was like “what am I doing here, I can’t speak that English. I felt that I’m not qualified to live here.
(Selma)

Similarly, Nadia did not understand how different shops in Scotland are. She faced some difficulties to find halal meat near the area where she lives and she had to travel to a different area. “For example, buying meat, I need to eat only halal meat, so I need to travel more than 10 kilometers to get it”. The different exosystems of transportation and shops in Algeria were very different from those in Scotland, which caused frustrations.

Findings from this study also show that some of the female participants have expressed that they experienced some incidences based on religious discrimination during their sojourn. For instance, one of the participants experienced an instance of discrimination when she first came to her new accommodation. She stated that she had some unpleasant encounters with other individuals within her place of residence.

People started to look at me in a weird way because I was wearing my veil and I am Muslim and it’s the same moment of terrorist attacks in Paris. So, I got that people were afraid from me because I am a Muslim and I was afraid from interacting with them.
(Ahlam)

Another participant, Latifa, who had some experiences of unfriendliness in her area of residence, on the streets and in her everyday navigation in the city. For instance,

...in shops, sometimes, the cashiers act normally with other people like: thank you darling... do you need a bag? But with me I feel that they use different language: Hi... do you have a bag? Yes/no it’s not like a normal conversation like this.
(Latifa)

5.1.1.1 Feeling like a stranger

Bronfenbrenner defines macrosystems as “...carriers of information and ideology that... endow meaning and motivation...” (Bronfenbrenner, 1977, p. 515). Up until their sojourn to the UK, Algerian PhD students were immersed in a cultural environment that has certain ideologies and

information, which suddenly changed after they moved to a new cultural environment that fostered ideologies and information different than their home macrosystems.

Some of the responses referred to the emotional state of the Algerian PhD students while living in the UK. Some of the experiences were positive like meeting new people, learning about the culture and developing oneself as this female participant noted:

Being in a multicultural environment and knowing about other cultures helped me to develop a sense of flexibility in interaction with people from different cultural backgrounds, speaking different languages.

Other experiences were considered negative such as missing family and struggling to adapt to the new context. For instance, several responses contained examples of feeling as strangers, a female participant explained:

I think that living with complete strangers coming from different places of the world is one. Being a researcher and being among highly skilled people and professionals is another one. Being a stranger in the UK is three. You might notice that all the aspects I mentioned revolve around the idea of being a stranger, which I think was very important to me and allowed me to discover things about my identity that I did not realise I had before coming to the UK.

Many participants stated that they experienced frustration during the transition process. For instance, a male respondent mentioned instances when he felt not fitting in when emphasising on the shift from belonging to the racial and religious majority in the home country to a minority living in a small community and how that shift affected their self-confidence and cultural awareness at the same time:

I hated that because I looked different I was treated differently and then realized that this is how it is going to be and I was ok with it. Before living in the UK, I never thought that I belong to a minority or seen myself as not being the norm.

Many respondents expressed their feeling of confusion concerning different contexts including the academic context as this female participant noted:

Sometimes you find yourself that you are not in the same level as those who are... already studied for the undergraduate or for the masters here, so you work all the time to achieve that level that they already have. They were like working on five years while I was working for five years for a degree purpose not for learning purpose.

Another important aspect that the Algerian PhD students emphasised is spaces where intercultural interactions happened. For example, most of the interactions happened within universities' offices, or student accommodations, which may indicate a limited interaction with host nationals and other international students. Some answers indicated isolation from interacting with the environment of the host country as this participant explained:

Being independent and responsible for everything is a positive effect. However, I have less contact with people around me as I'm all the time studying and there isn't much time to have friends.

Several participants affirmed that religion plays a great role in their lives before and during the sojourn. Religious activities are an important aspect for Algerian families and individuals, since religious practice and perspectives are taught and deep-rooted from a young age and it can be seen in the different aspects of a Muslim individual's life (Fellag, 2014). For Algerian PhD students in the UK, practising religion can function as an "identity maintenance system" (Gollnick, 2005, P. 114) by giving them a sense of belonging to a larger community that has a common purpose. However, that sense of belonging to a given community can magnify the tendencies to view people from other communities as different and as the other. For instance, some of the participants talked about establishing clear boundaries between their home culture and the host culture, which they consider as different. For example, a female participant explained her position towards Christmas celebrations: "*I am not showing hostility or dislike to that celebration, I respect them. I know this is not my culture, it's their culture and I won't show any hostility towards that*". Similarly, a male participant believes that there is a clear cut between home culture and host culture as he explained: "*It's good to respect other people and to know about them. But my culture is here, and their culture is there*".

Another participant described her views of the new culture as different and inappropriate, when she first arrived in the UK. She stated that she was shocked from people's behaviours during weekends as she viewed their behaviours as inappropriate according to her home culture and religion:

During the weekends, when I go home at night from the library, I see people drunk and dancing in the street, I was very shocked at the beginning. I was judging them without knowing them.

The shift in the context of living for the Algerian PhD students affected the proximal processes on the familial, institutional, social and cultural contexts. Some participants reported that they felt as strangers in the sense that they lost most of their familiar references and found themselves feeling alone in a different country. The most impactful changes were related to the temporary loss of the usual proximal processes operating within microsystems including familiar people like family members and peers and places where they used to live. On a higher level (macrosystem), changes can appear in the cultural context and the language of communication.

For most of the Algerian PhD students in this study, proximal processes within environments had great influence on their development. For instance, interactions that did not happen within the participants' mesosystem 'student accommodation and peers', 'university and peers' caused hardships for some of the participants.

Moreover, sudden changes in the social environment and culture can be seen on all levels, where Algerian participants live and study. The sudden changes did not allow participants to easily navigate through their lives within the new context. Being unable to handle the simplest activities such as shopping for groceries and attending to university and even crossing roads safely caused severe emotional distress and unstable identity development. Furthermore, using only English for communication on a daily basis affected some of the Algerian PhD students negatively and caused them to feel lonely and anxious during the first times.

5.1.1.2 These are my best buddies

In the photographs provided for the photo-elicitation interviewing, almost all pictures contained the participants themselves with other people whom they referred to as friends. When the pictures contained co-national fellows, participants spoke more and deeply about the experiences they share together with them. In some cases, participants stated that the people in the pictures, who are co-nationals, are their best friends. For instance, Selma talked about her Algerian friend that she provided her with social support since the first day of their sojourns to the UK:

Taking a picture here in Glasgow when I went for shopping with my friends. My friend in this picture is no longer here, she left now. I like her so much and I had the best days with her. She made my life different like we spent a nice because we live far apart from our families and doing a PhD is not that easy task to do and you have ups and downs and she was always supporting me.

(Selma)

Similarly, Ali talked about catching up with an old friend by visiting him in London, and how that experience brought him joy and acted as a social support:

That picture was taken in the British Museum, I remember that I went to see my friend in London... at that day, he showed me many places that I didn't know about before; we had a good time. That makes me feel like having your friend, we were friends back home and the way we were hanging out in London and stuff like that eating Algerian food, it makes you feel like you're back home.

(Ali)

Sara, on Halloween night, stated that it is not usual for her to go out to such events; however, being with her Algerian friend made her feel more comfortable to do so:

This picture was more than four months ago, it was a kind of feast, which people of the UK celebrate it. This is me with my friend from Algeria as well as other people... At first, I felt a bit frustrated because I'm not used to do so. At the same time, I was comfortable because I wasn't alone since my friends came with me.

(Sara)

Other students shared pictures where they were doing activities organised by the university's international office to create spaces for interaction between students from different countries. For example, Houda stated: "I started going to trips organised by the university. I spent some good time with my friends". Similarly, Latifa mentioned an event just for females organised by the University in which she joined her Algerian friends:

...yes, this picture is from a party called the Arabian tea party. It has been organised by the Muslim society yeah, I went with my Algerian friends and we decided to dress up Algerian traditional clothes.

(Latifa)

Notably, other participants provided pictures of themselves with a group of friends from their student accommodation as part of their social interaction with others. Having friends from different cultural backgrounds, mutual social support and experience social recreational activities. For instance, Nora described her experience in the student accommodation where she and other international students interact and learn about their cultures through music and dance:

Even for example where I live in the accommodation, sometimes we do parties in the kitchen, we play traditional songs or songs that represent culture for each country like our dance, our music. (Nora)

Ali also talked about travelling with friends as an extracurricular activity to cope with his study stress:

I was with my best buddies; that was in last week in Loch Lomond, we rented a car. That's what I usually do when I'm not in a mood for study, I run out from study and go and have fun and discover Scotland. (Ali)

In the case of all the Algerian PhD students in this study, travelling to the UK was such an emotionally difficult experience because it was a major transition without any supportive microsystem that could support them when engaging in increasingly complex and new experiences. Usually, micro systems such as 'family' and 'friends' hold strong emotional attachments and provide emotional support when it is needed. The limited interaction of these proximal processes during the sojourn was clearly a source of distress for them during the first weeks.

Living away from family and friends who still live in Algeria, participants started interacting more often with peers who share similar interests and engaging in activities with them. It appeared that participants felt less stressed when engaging in new experiences as long as they are with someone they trust as best friends.

The participants' best friends were the same sex and approximately the same age, but most importantly they were the ones who shared and supported the participants' social identity. For instance, the participants' best friends are people from home society or from the new society who affirm the participants' social identity as members of a certain group such as Algerian, Muslim, international PhD student, etc.

5.1.2 Becoming a better version of myself

For a few months, Algerian PhD students in this study have been acquiring new knowledge about the culture, as well as the language. Both of these forms of knowledge were intellectual efforts that continued to reveal more complexities as participants continued acquiring them.

Many participants from the open-ended questionnaire mentioned different skills they developed during their experience abroad, which helped them adjusting successfully with their new environment. Most of them mentioned that they developed their language and academic knowledge, social interaction and personal traits including resilience, cultural awareness, independence and responsibility.

A number of respondents stated that they developed some coping strategies and awareness of the host country's cultures that may have helped them in overcoming the frustrations of transition between cultures and adjusting to the host culture (Wu et al., 2015).

On the personal level, gaining a sense of autonomy was a common response among most of the female participants as this participant illustrated that *“being abroad helped me to become more independent. I learnt to manage my money, manage my time and become more organised”*. In fact, female participants wrote about feeling more power in being independent and in making their own decisions in comparison to women's state in the home country as this participant explained: *“when I came (to the UK) I realised that all the roles that the society gave to me or to other women back home or my city or my family as cultural roles or... because of men power”*. Another participant added: *“I am here in the UK and there is nothing that differs between men and women I feel like I have more power and equality”*.

In addition, they mentioned that being a PhD researcher boosted Algerian PhD students' self-confidence in both countries, which gave them a sense of achievement. For example, a male participant stated: *“Going back to Algeria, and getting your PhD from a foreign country, I think we... I got more chances to get a good job and a good life with that... Yeah”*. Another female participant shared the same viewpoint: *“So being in here doing a PhD gave more power, especially in the way of thinking. I feel that I am not thinking the way I was in Algeria”*.

Moreover, most of the participants mentioned their raised awareness as a positive consequence of their sojourn abroad. They explained how the living abroad experience made them learn about their own identities, attitudes and cultures as explained by this female respondent:

Growing up in religiously bounded culture makes individuals less open to others or at least know very little about them. Living in a country where there are people from different nationalities, cultures, religions, ethnic groups and linguistic backgrounds has shaped to very large extent my identity. I feel that I am now more aware and tolerant when I am in cultural encounters that are different than mine and somehow contradict with my values and beliefs. Additionally, I consider that my understanding to myself and the other is being built and it is developing, so that now I can travel to anywhere without having the feeling of stranger.

One of the major goals of living abroad is *learning about the other cultures*, which is a common idea shared by most of the participants in this study. Many of the participants mentioned that they learned about different cultures through interaction with the others, which had a positive impact on the participants' language fluency and social support.

The chance of living in the UK taught me how to be inter-culturally competent in accepting other's cultures and never judge or consider non- Muslims people as bad people. [...] In fact, studying in the UK helped me to raise my awareness when talking to professors in a professional way, it also gave me the opportunity to build good friendship with many friends from different countries and know about their culture and respect their religion.

The use of different languages might indicate that the Algerian PhD students exhibited a complex identity in which they see themselves as cosmopolitan individuals that can communicate and accept the various cultures. Most of the participants stated that they can speak several languages including Tamazight, Arabic, French and English. For instance, several interviewees indicated that the ability to communicate using several languages gave them the opportunity to interact with different people in different situations, which helped them building a stronger sense of satisfaction. For instance, Nadia talked about the importance of the English language in the communication process and as a way of developing an awareness of the other peoples' cultures when she was talking about the different encounters she had during her sojourn: *"These encounters helped me to develop, not just my English but also my awareness towards other cultures"*. Similarly, Selma mentioned an encounter with French people who needed her

assistance: *“When I met French people, at work, who needed help. I just switch directly from English to French (smiling) it’s good”.*

Participants in this study talked about PERSON resources including their mastery of many languages, which they considered an advantage that can help them develop interaction and social functioning. Mastering languages gave Algerians an opportunity to express themselves with a wider variety of people from different linguistic and cultural backgrounds. In fact, being able to communicate with a wide variety of people helped Algerian PhD students widening their circle of contacts, which reflected positively on their psychological well-being and social functioning in the new societal context. However, other participants expressed that not being able to use mother tongue can be frustrating sometimes.

Studying abroad for a PhD is milestone in the process of participants’ empowerment since it enables them to respond to the challenges, to confront their traditional roles and change their lives. Living in foreign country away from the different influences of strong traditional forces, where men are considered to be decision makers or providers. The less systematic interaction with the home culture macrosystem elements the less impact they have on the Algerian PhD students’ identity development in the UK. In this sense, less restrictions from home society means more freedom for participants in this study to express themselves and to do whatever they like.

For some participants, studying abroad at a doctoral level entails learning to freely make decisions in all aspects of their lives from thoughts and actions. Participants’ responses emphasised on the newly developed disposition characteristics such as power, independence and cultural awareness. Moreover, focusing on achieving their goals and having open interactions with different people in different places over a period of time has benefitted the Algerian participants in shifting their attention towards developing themselves.

The unique cultural exosystem in the UK, which promotes more individualistic attitudes has influenced and shaped how Algerian doctoral students’ social and personal processes work within the new environment. This exosystem was a positive structure for development by influencing how microsystems and mesosystems interact and develop. For instance, after interacting with the new environment and experiencing cultural differences through different cultural situations, Algerian doctoral students developed new senses of power and freedom in comparison to their previous experiences in their home societies. One of the sources of power

stressed in the participants' responses was PhD education. Most of the female participants believed that a PhD degree from the UK would give them more power to overcome gender inequality in their home societies. This served as a motivating factor that encourages them to overcome the difficulties related to their social and academic life.

5.1.2.1 Feeling more open

Openness towards other cultures in this context was reported by different participants after interacting with new people from their new environment. In Algerian society, there are very few people from other countries; it is unlikely to interact with people from different countries and cultures.

In the case of Algerian PhD students in the UK, being able to use English has helped the Algerian PhD students interacting with a wide variety of people and learning about cultural differences and similarities and learning to accept different viewpoints.

The proximal process of having complex and positive interactions with peers from different cultural backgrounds that took place in the student accommodation has affected the participants' views about the microsystems of being 'international students' and 'significant others'. For instance, many participants stated that they could navigate through interactions without constraints across cultures.

Now I feel I am more open. Now I can take part in a conversation with a native speaker and express myself in a free way. [...] I can say that I am more developed. I feel more comfortable and accepting the culture around me. I am accepting more people yeah; I am more open. (Selma)

One of [my friends] comes every time to my room, sometimes she finds me praying and she asks about that, but she never say something as I used to say about others. She respects my religion and learned to do the same. (Nadia)

I felt like I was in a small box, I wasn't open-minded, I didn't know the meaning of life now I'm more open yeah... I am seeing from another vision other aspects of life. [...] I feel more open to people, especially [when using] English, which

is an international language. So, this is the most powerful language that really helped me to know more people here. (Nora)

Another participant described an interaction with a homosexual man that she met at the university:

I didn't have problems because I was open, curious and respectful and I know my limits and how to respect others. (Ahlam)

Developing Person characteristics Resources including Emotional maturity and cultural awareness, curiosity, respect and acceptance. Moreover, becoming self-aware of their own beliefs and values and learning about other cultures and worldviews during interaction with different people gave the Algerian PhD students a sense of satisfaction with general and specific areas of their life in the UK.

5.1.2.2 Religion and identity negotiation

The most marked observation to emerge from the data comparison was the strong association of religion with the Algerian PhD students' identity abroad. In this study, most of the participants consider their faith as an important dimension of their identity formation. They addressed the increasing importance of the religious aspect of their identity as they lived abroad. In addition, they felt that their religion is a way of expressing and maintaining one's identity rather than representing ethnicity or nationality. For example, Latifa expressed how wearing the hijab was a part of her Muslim identity and how speaking about it with others would make it more accepted and understood. She reported instances where she had many conversations about the reasons she thinks women, like herself, and are wearing hijab:

In a party, I knew new friends and other people. There were some Italian girls and they asked us as Algerians, why we wear this (hijab) yeah and I had to explain to them that. (Latifa)

She also shared a story of her when she to a concert of religious music:

it was my dream to attend a concert to anybody (laughter) and Sami Yousef came to Glasgow last year and I like the kind of music he sings (soufi music) it is a type of music the expresses devotion to god and it even enhance the ... physical and the spiritual aspects of the listener... (Latifa)

Sara, who lives in a student accommodation with other people from different nationalities, explained that she wanted to share some information about Ramadan and her home culture practices:

I like showing people my culture or what do I celebrate. I put a time table for Ramadan in my kitchen, Muslims do celebrate Ramadan. (Sara)

Ali, talked about an example of negotiating identity during sojourn, as the influences of home culture from one side and participating in social activities with friends from another:

I don't tend to let my Algerian culture affect me here because sometimes you cannot... how to say it... you are in a foreign country so you need to cope with the life here. Going to pub doesn't mean yeah I have to drink or something, I just like to go with friends but that doesn't mean drinking or doing stuff, which are not part of our culture. And yes, there are things that do back home and still doing here, like going to the mosque and stuff like that. (Ali)

Religion and identity in the Algerian context go hand in hand. It makes a big part of most of the Algerian population since birth. The majority of Algerian people are used to practise religious activities on a daily basis, weekly basis and in some cases on a monthly basis like Ramadan. Religion was present on the familial context, institutional and societal contexts. According to Bronfenbrenner, consistent interaction with person, a place, or a symbol would make a great impact on the persons' development. Sudden changes in the context of living (including both micro and macro levels) resulted in affecting negatively the psychological wellbeing of the Algerian participants.

Some participants talked about how keeping practicing religious activities has a great importance to how they feel about themselves. On the societal context, social identity/ being part of a social/ religious group that can be made of various cultures and nationalities can offer social support. Some participants talked about having consistent interactions within places like the mosque and how that helped them expressing their Muslim identity being as part of the Muslim community in the UK. However, identity negotiation might appear when demand characteristics of Muslim identity in the may interfere with other interactions with different people in different contexts. For instance, a possible space for negotiation could be when Muslim Algerian PhD students interact with others during social events that might include activities that are not accepted according to the religious beliefs and rules such as drinking

alcohol, music and mixing with the other gender. As a solution to this dilemma, some participants created a third space where they engage in activities and interact with other people yet stay faithful to their Muslim identity.

5.1.2.3 Feeling more comfortable (PEI)

In regards to Algerian PhD students' feelings, the improvement of the social environment for them led to develop feelings of confidence. Most of the participants in the photo-elicitation interviewing talked about their experience abroad and referred to their new context in different ways. Ali explained how living in a student accommodation enriched his experience by exposing him to more people.

I have chosen to live in a student accommodation because there are many international people coming from all over the world. For example, Erasmus students come for four months then go and other students come then go and I have the chance to knowing them and their different cultures. Even the way like... being in the accommodation with international people means you are always speaking in English, that's a good thing. (Ali)

Nadia talked about her observations about the different people she interacted with in the UK and reflected on her own behaviours and values:

English helped me to know so many people who became my best friends and that helped to improve my English skills and to make successful conversations with them. I live in a student accommodation, I try to socialise with people from different cultures and countries and I realised that everyone has his own religion and I need to respect it. (Nadia)

As a reaction to the positive interaction with the host nationals or with other international students, at university or at the students' accommodation, some participants explained that they started accepting the new culture. For instance,

I do meet people from different cultures and they've got different backgrounds. This is something really amazing, it gives me the opportunity to discover and to acquire new things new knowledge. (Nora)

I felt like something started to change here. I feel more comfortable and accepting the culture around me. I am accepting more people yeah, I am more open... (Selma)

These positive feelings of confidence due to an expansion of the social environment led the Algeria PhD students to interact more within their accommodation. Some of the participants spoke about feeling overwhelmed when they first stayed in the students' accommodation, which is typically filled with people from around the world and usually English is the only way to communicate with them. However, after a period of time, some participants overcame their frustration and started making good progress in both academic and social lives. Becoming more familiar with their environment, they started interacting with people, objects and symbols from their new environment. Moreover, being able to use personal characteristics like the English Language helped the participants during different social interactions within their new environment.

The students' accommodation exosystem of being a place where people from different nationalities and cultural groups live together has influenced the Algerian doctoral students' social processes. For instance, the motivation to become friends with other international students and becoming more comfortable in the new environment drove them to interact more and to become more comfortable to use English when interacting.

5.1.2.4 Feeling powerful and autonomous

Being autonomous was one of the various changes highlighted during the interviews. Many participants had used terminology such as “becoming independent” and “free”. Taking care of oneself in a foreign country after spending a lifetime depending on family for everyday needs is one thing shared between most of the participants in this research. A female participant expressed that her experience in the UK had a great impact on her at several levels as she stated: “*my experience in the UK changed my perception and conception about who I am. My perception about culture. Self-awareness, individuality, independency and autonomy*”. Nadia, during her interview, explained that being a doctoral student in the UK boosted her feeling of autonomy:

I feel as a very strong woman, because seeking knowledge in one of the UK's universities makes me more mature and develops my self-independence. When I was in Algeria, I used to depend on my parents. My father is and always been responsible for us, but when I came here, I learned how to be self-independent and how to do everything by myself, otherwise, no one will do it for me.
(Nadia)

Many of the female participants have referred to some of their experiences in the UK as empowering ones. Some of them talked about the authoritarian regime in the Algerian society that is characterised by male dominance, in an attempt to raise more awareness of the women's rights in the Algerian society. For instance, they expressed their new-found social freedom as being responsible and free to decide for themselves to make social, political, and individual choices within the new society in the UK. Ahlam explained her view towards the women's situation by giving an example of her family:

I grew up in a family that men have the decision to do, they decide instead of us not we decide ourselves. It's the same thing I think for almost all the women back home. (Ahlam)

Nora is another participant who expressed a similar feeling towards home society as limiting women's freedom using social norms and religion as examples:

Going out at night is totally new, I'm not used to it in Algeria, but here it's like something normal for them. Maybe it has to do with our culture or religion or about safety, it's not safe. I feel like I'm free to do whatever I want in here, it's not the same at all. (Nora)

Similarly, Latifa referred to the limited freedom of socialising with the opposite sex in their home society arguing that traditions do not allow such thing:

To be a woman or a female I can't really be sociable in the society because of the traditions and so on. (Latifa)

Sara, expressed her concern in relation to power imbalance between men and women:

Most of men in Algeria think that they are better, and females are not equal, they do not have the same rights. (Sara)

Nadia talked about how male-dominant society limited her freedom as she grew up, which was upsetting for her:

When I was a child, I used to have a small bike, but I stopped when I started my secondary school because it is not the same as here. It's a matter of society, because people, especially men, when they see a girl riding a bike is something not normal at all. (Nadia)

Ahlam, on the other hand, referred to the limited freedom of women on social media. For instance, she shared her experience of not being able to post her own pictures on social media.

When I was in Algeria, I wasn't brave enough to put my picture as a profile picture, or to post my pictures; others too. But when I came to the UK and started interacting with people and they saw that if you have a real-life identity and you are a person that exists in real life and the virtual world is another world. (Ahlam)

Generally, it is accepted that people who are studying for a PhD are expected to be talented in terms of their academic performance and achievements; therefore, receiving scholarships. All the participants in this study have been selected for a scholarship to study at PhD level after successfully completing undergraduate and master's degree – at the top of their classes in different Algerian Universities. Moreover, students were selected after successfully passing an exam at the national level to be eligible for this scholarship to the UK. It must be highlighted that most of the participants emphasised their previous experience had increased their perception of self-pride and efficiency. However, Feelings of power and autonomy during the sojourn in the new environment can be related to the newly found freedom in relation to the familial and social contexts back in Algerian societies. Female Algerian PhD students, who might have experienced gender inequalities in Algerian societies found themselves able to do and to be whoever they want in a society that supports individualism and freedom of thought and action. Authoritative figures, which acted as stressors that exist on different levels like familial, structural and societal contexts in Algeria had a limited impact on the Algerian PhD students in the UK. Participants experienced more autonomy in their daily lives from taking care of their health and wellness and organising their daily routine to fit their personal goals, which gave them more responsibility and freedom. They introduced new element in their person characteristics including resources like power and freedom. This situation gave them more emotional stability and self-confidence.

5.1.3 My life as an academic

The academic experiences shared by the participants in this study can be summarised into three general themes: Engaging in academic activities, my relationship with supervisors, staff and academics, and The PhD life is very hard for me. Each theme contains ideas expressed by participants from the photo-elicitation interviews and also from the questionnaire.

5.1.3.1 *The PhD life is very hard for me*

Some participants stated that one of the issues that faced them at the beginning of their PhD programme was that research is difficult for them being international students compared to other host nationals.

The PhD life is very hard, especially at the beginning... it's not only for me; it can be for everyone especially for overseas students. The different culture, system and university can make very hard. (Morad)

Similarly, Ahlam raises an important issue she faced, which is the difficulty of balancing academic and social life. She talked about how being an international student in a new cultural and academic cultures can affect her academic performance and that should be addressed more by the University.

I am an international student abroad, so I have an intercultural, cultural experience, which is new for me, plus the academic experience is completely new for me. I think it is a bit ignored that they don't provide that balance between the two they emphasis on the academic side (part) of it of my journey, not the other part, which include the cultural one. (Ahlam)

Another major issue reported by students was making the balance between their social lives and their study time. One participant discussed her experience doing pre-sessional courses and how that experience wasn't as beneficial as she expected. She felt that she had spent more time preparing for the IELTS and contacting universities compared with the time spent on her social life.

I was doing my pre-sessional course, but our focus was getting (having), secure a placement in universities and having the IELTS, so we didn't have time to go and visit other places in the UK. We were spending most of the time in Kent. (Ahlam)

Remarkably, participants express a strong negative relationship between academic identity and their social one abroad. As the findings from her interview show, Latifa appear to be less involved in extracurricular activities to maximise her academic outcomes:

Though the PhD life erm, Socio cultural adjustment restricted me a bit, because I want to develop my academic identity rather than the social one, because you know it's a PhD and you need to keep isolated from people and

just reading books and stuff of the study. Maybe I couldn't make the balance between the social identity and the academic one. (Latifa)

International students have to learn a whole new macrosystem due to the educational and cultural differences that exist with university systems in the UK, which are vital to understand and succeed academically. In the beginning of their sojourn, participants experienced a sense of loss and frustration to the unfamiliarity of the new academic environment and talked about how challenging their academic life was.

5.1.3.2 Engaging in academic activities

From the analysis, I highlighted three subthemes related to academic activities including pre-sessional courses, academic research activities and extracurricular activities. Several participants shared pictures about their academic activities explaining their learning experiences and the different activities on campus. For instance: Ali talked about a picture of him during the 3 minutes thesis competition. He was feeling proud of that achievement, which in turn cultivate his academic identity as a researcher in both academic and non-academic contexts. Another aspect that Ali mentioned is his engagement in extracurricular activities and their effects in boosting self-confidence and the overall satisfaction of his journey.

The second picture was last year, it was taken during the preparation for the three minutes thesis competition. It was good for me like one of the things that you feel here as an international student is developing your knowledge and that was one of the best moments for me to present my work to a non-specialised audience and to let them know about my topic in three minutes. I didn't know that I actually could present my work in a good way so by the end I won the best presentation for the audience and that makes me feel proud of myself and my work. (Ali)

Latifa talked about her experience as a teacher of Arabic at the university. She presented a photograph about her during a class that she was giving at the university, which amplified her academic identity by identifying herself as an associate lecturer, as well as her cultural identity associated with Arabic language.

Here is me giving Arabic class because I'm an associate lecturer, delivering Arabic classes for beginners at the UWS yes ...erm. My Arabic get stronger why? Because teaching beginners sometimes is challenging because there are things that I learned in my childhood, so I had to come back and revise many

things because you know, our language is so difficult... to see foreigners learn my language, I feel proud to see them doing progress each session I teach them yeah. (Latifa)

Participants emphasised their engagement in different academic activities within a context that supported the participants' academic identity. They talked about being able to navigate through the new academic culture successfully by using their knowledge about the new cultural context and developing personal dispositions such as organisation, independence and openness. Furthermore, effective functioning at an institutional level lead to boosting the participants' self-confidence, psychological wellbeing and satisfaction over the whole experience.

5.1.3.3 My relationship with Supervisors, staff and other academics

Another aspect of the academic adjustment is the relationship of the participants with their supervisory teams and other academics and staff at their university or abroad. Some of the participants referred to their relationship with staff and academics and how they managed to overcome cultural differences between the academic settings in Algeria and in the UK. For example, Ahlam provided a detailed account of her first contact with other host nationals and international academics and how comfortable she felt when interacting with them:

When I came to the UK, I got in touch with academics, who made a difference. The first thing that they taught us is we don't use names (titles, or honorifics) like doctor, or professor to communicate with them, but we have to use their first name and that's it. That gives you the insight that there is no barrier between the teacher and the student, so you start seeing yourself like you can achieve what they achieved. (Ahlam)

Similarly, Nora talked about the good relationship with their supervisors at the university and how that nurtured their academic identity and acted as a social support. For instance, Nora talked about her positive relationship with her supervisory team and university staff as a way to boost her self-confidence within academic contexts as she explained:

The shift from being in Algeria, which is a developing country then directly towards the UK in one of the best ranking universities in the UK, I mean the School of Education. I wanted to say that the relationship in here, they are friendly and are really helpful. This is what helped me to being more confident. So, I feel people want to know more about me and what I am doing my

research, they really do respect people, which is like totally the opposite in Algeria. (Nora)

Ali also talked about the importance of the good relationship with his supervisory team in enhancing his experience within academic settings:

I have a very good relationship with either my supervisory team or with any of the staff in the school of education. I found it very important to have such good relationships in terms of academic experience yeah. (Ali)

Latifa brought an important aspect of her view on academic identity, which is her perception of power balance between students and staff in the UK and the importance of spaces for informal and social interaction in boosting her sense of belonging to the university community.

Here you feel you are equal with everyone, either the professor or the dean of the school or anyone else. But in Algeria NO. You are a student, you need to...just studying and studying and that's it. Here they even organise parties for students, trips for students to let that stress go over and so on. Yeah. I think the life of students here is much much better than in Algeria. (Latifa)

Selma brought a personal experience explaining her development as an international PhD student and her supervisor's support that had a positive influence on her academic writing and her well-being in general.

As a student in here, (Scotland) everything you do is important and has a value. My first pieces of writing were very bad, but my supervisor liked it. Now I feel that there is a difference in my style of writing. Even if there are plenty of mistakes a lot of things that I need to work on they never make you down. (Selma)

The academic support that international students receive at university can be a very crucial component of the students' academic success. The type of support that the Algerian PhD students in this study have received within the new academic environment made them feel as equal, appreciated and valued members of the academic community.

Participants' proximal processes surrounding them were powerful systems. From their responses, it was evident that complex and positive interactions the supervisory teams had a major development effect on the participants' views about the microsystem of being an 'international student' and 'a doctoral student'. This proximal process served boost to their self-

confidence, psychological well-being and gave them more motivation to achieve greater intellectual development.

Conclusion

In this chapter, I analysed the data from the open-ended question from the questionnaire and the textual data from the photo-elicitation interview using thematic analysis. Analysis shows the different interpretations of Algerian PhD student sojourners about their acculturative experiences in the UK. The data was critically interpreted by using deductive thematic analysis, which aims at organising the data into themes and connecting the most significant ones to the research questions and to Bronfenbrenner's' bioecological model of development.

The sudden changes in the contexts did not allow participants to easily navigate through their lives within the new environment. This made them feel like they are unable to handle the simplest activities and caused severe emotional distress. However after few weeks, they felt less stressed when they are with someone they trust as best friends. In addition, having complex and positive interactions with peers, supervisors and staff inside the university and outside it affected Algerian doctoral students' development of new senses of power and freedom and motivating them to overcome the difficulties related to their academic and social lives.

Female Algerian PhD students, who might have experienced gender inequalities in Algerian societies experienced feelings of power and autonomy during the sojourn in the new environment can be related to the newly found freedom in relation to the traditional familial and social contexts back in Algerian societies.

Participants emphasised their engagement in different academic activities within a context that supported the participants' academic identity despite the difficulties they faced at the beginning of their sojourn. The type of support that the Algerian PhD students in this study have received within the new academic environment made them feel as equal, appreciated and valued members of the academic community.

Chapter 6: Discussion

Introduction

The key findings from the data are related to the Algerian doctoral students' expressing feelings of emotional frustration and anxiety on the first few weeks of their study sojourn. In addition, findings also highlight their positive emotions of settling in and their different social networks within the new environment. Moreover, data show a part of the Algerian doctoral students' life and identity as academics by casting the light on the different academic activities, relationships and challenges they face during their studies. Findings also highlight the importance of language and religion in the process of identity negotiation in addition to the positive identity changes from being exposed to new experiences and cultures in the UK as perceived by the Algerian PhD students. This chapter focuses on the discussion of the findings, which are discussed in relation to the research questions, the theoretical implications and the research literature. The research questions are answered and limitations of the study and future research directions are addressed later in this chapter.

6.1 Considerations

Before discussing the results from the data, it is important to position myself, the researcher, in the context of this study. The qualitative researcher's role is like a reporter who records parts of everyday life and as an artist who presents the results of research in an unusual way for the audience (Bergin and Garfield, 2013; Springer et al., 2018). In this research, my aim is to be that qualitative researcher. I am also aware that acknowledging me as the researcher will have its own effect on this study, which will be addressed later in the conclusion chapter.

To begin with, there is still a debate about qualitative research and its focus on the function and importance of the reflexivity of the researcher (Etherington, 2004; Reid et al., 2018). Generally, it is believed that data collection and analysis processes cannot be shaped in isolation from the personal involvement of the researcher. During the research, the participants were involved in a reflection on their personal experiences and identities, with me as an interviewer who has an interest in exploring the topic. In fact, I am the only audience to whom the participants present themselves in terms of this research. Also, acknowledging me as a researcher will have, in some ways, influenced what the participants provided, which is known as "interviewer effect" (Schaeffer et al., 2016). To reduce this impact of the interviewer, during the data collection

phase, I employed the photo-elicitation interviewing method to bridge the power gap between me as a researcher and research participants. In addition, a reflexive process was used throughout the research stages: at the conception of this study, the research design, interviews, the thematic analysis and the discussion. Reflexivity is believed to help researchers in exploring the various ways in which their engagement has an impact on different stages of the study (Haynes, 2012; Xerri, 2017). The inclusion of a reflexive process is believed to increase the rigour of the research process by improving data reliability. Reflexivity can be a tool that promotes understanding of the studied phenomenon by acknowledging the relation between and influence of, the researcher and participants.

The discussion of the results is in relation to the following research questions:

6.2 Question one: What are the different adjustment strategies used by Algerian PhD student sojourners to cope with the experience abroad?

Our findings show that the Algerian PhD students use different adjustment strategies, namely academic, personal and social ones, to cope with living abroad.

6.2.1 Academic adjustment

Most of the participants referred to their educational experience as students in Algeria and compared it to the UK. Generally, they reflected on many problems they faced within the Algerian education system including the lack of students' voice, traditional teaching methods, the huge communication gap between students and teachers and the impact of these problems on their academic life in the UK.

Findings from this study also report the different academic issues that participants faced during their first few months. Participants in the present study reported that, at the beginning of their PhD programme, they faced many difficulties such as unfamiliarity with the academic culture and time management.

Remarkably, most of the participants expressed a strong negative correlation between academic identity and their social one. For instance, Algerian Doctoral students showed that they were focused on working on their own PhD projects and less interested in other academic and non-academic activities inside and outside the academic establishments. Focusing on just writing a PhD thesis can negatively affect the doctoral students' wellbeing and make them feel loneliness

since they usually interact only with supervisors for more than three years with little interaction during other workshops and seminars (Cotterall, 2013; Hunter and Devine, 2016).

Most of the participants seemed to have some difficulties at the beginning of their PhD programmes, which is common among other doctoral students (Kamler and Thomson, 2014). Algerian PhD students stated that they had some difficulty in adjusting to the new academic culture, especially in academic writing, and other necessary skills for a PhD such as critical thinking (Brodin, 2016). With regard to the difficulties faced at the beginning of their PhD degree, some participants indicated that their level of writing was not good enough, but with the help and support from their supervisors, they felt a gradual, steady development of their academic style which made them feel more accepted in the new academic culture. This positive relationship between staff from the host academic institutions and Algerian doctoral students can provide context for negotiating identity and developing a strong doctoral identity (Holley, 2011).

Most of the participants seemed satisfied with their relationships with supervisors and had no problems with communication. Literature shows that misunderstanding and communication problems may appear between students and supervisors due to the lack of English proficiency (Adrian-Taylor et al., 2007; Devos et al., 2016; Cornér et al., 2017). However in this context, Algerian PhD students did not report any issues in terms of interaction with supervisors or staff at universities.

Some of them spoke about the PhD pre-session course that they attended prior to their PhD programme, which appears to have been a great advantage in developing the students' openness towards the new academic culture and proficiency of English language before starting the PhD process (Meng et al., 2017). Spending time to get used to the cultural, social and academic contexts of the host country before the official start of the PhD programme appears to be beneficial in this context, yet further research is required to provide fuller evidence of this.

6.2.2 Sociocultural adjustment

Linking this study's findings to Bronfenbrenner's bioecological theory (2005) I was able to understand some factors, dimensions and processes that influence one's experience of studying abroad by using the original framework but in a more fluid and adaptable way in which culture is conceptualised as the context in which microsystems and other systems exist and interact

between one another. Understanding the process of identity negotiation would prepare student sojourners for the changes that may occur during their experiences abroad. Although study abroad programmes usually consider formal academic settings, participants generally report learning from cultural and social situations (Heine, 2015; Wu et al., 2015).

During their sojourn, taking part in intercultural interaction may result in instances of conflict that necessitate identity negotiation (Berry, 2005). Reflecting on some experiences during their sojourn, Algerian doctoral students commented extensively on the changes in their personal aspect of identity. This was a common theme of conversation in all the interview sessions; all the participants mentioned some life-changing developments in their views on the world and in their behaviours. All the participants went through some intense emotional experiences at the beginning of their journey as they tried to adjust to both the sociocultural environment and to the academic one.

In this study, many participants' statements that they felt "frustrated" and "like strangers" might indicate struggling with emotional insecurity, which led them to reflect on their belief systems and assumptions by negotiating their original identity and developing a hybrid one. For instance, the shift of the between two culturally different environments may leave students emphasising racial and religious belonging when living in the UK and how that shift affected their self-confidence and cultural awareness at the same time:

I hated that because I looked different I was treated differently and then realized that this is how it is going to be and I was ok with it. Before living in the UK, I never thought that I belong to a minority or seen myself as not being the norm.

The experience of overcoming the negative feeling and adapting to the new cultural and social contexts considered as a process of becoming a better version of oneself instead of a complete change in the Algerian PhD students' identity. For instance, learning about the other cultures through interacting with them had a positive impact on some participants' language fluency and social support.

The chance of living in the UK taught me how to be inter-culturally competent in accepting other's cultures and never judge or consider non- Muslims people as bad people. [...] In fact, studying in the UK helped me to raise my awareness when talking to professors in a

professional way, it also gave me the opportunity to build good friendship with many friends from different countries and know about their culture and respect their religion.

When sojourners move to another culture to live for a period, they often experience a transformation in the way they see the world to cope with stress and anxiety (Ting-Toomey and Dorjee, 2018). Usually, when individuals face an experience that cannot be fully understood using their own perspective, the experience is rejected or the perspective changes to accept the experience. Most of the participants had a mono-national perspective, which had been shifted to a multinational perspective by becoming accommodated with the new environment. This evidence points to the effectiveness of the study abroad programme on developing intercultural awareness.

Taken together, findings from this research suggest that the individuals during the sojourn use different strategies to conceptualise different identities when interacting with others in different contexts in the host culture. Adjustment to the new context comprises reactions to the context by observing, rationalising and most importantly interacting with others. Many participants in this study interacted more with co-nationals who have similar bioecological systems, similar cultures, religion, or language. This supports previous findings from Gu and Schweisfurth (2015) who state that most international students form cultural relations with others who are similar to themselves. However, interacting with the host national and other PhD students appears through some of the participants' responses as a useful strategy in broadening their perspectives and impacting the way they live and think (McLeod et al., 2015).

The analysis of data proposes that the new microsystems of most of the Algerian sojourners include some people from the old micro system in addition to the new people and places in the new context, which are in a constant interaction with the individual, that might include roommates, neighbours, supervisors, people from the same country or who have similar culture or language, and places like the student accommodation, university, or the mosque in the host country. Further analysis of the narratives from the participants showed that the student accommodation and university are the places where most of the participants' interactions happened. Many of the participants reported that they were living together, or close to one another, at same student accommodation, or the same town. They talked about the different activities they did together, such as different gatherings, national and religious celebrations.

Living in a student accommodation, the participants stated that it is a better way to increasing communication skills with both co-nationals and international students. These findings suggest that the participants received more social support (Yang et al., 2018) when living in student accommodation with students who share the same experiences and who can understand their struggles and support each other through their time together (Wilcox et al., 2005; Rahat and Ilhan, 2016; Taha and Cox, 2016; Lindvig, 2018).

In conclusion, most of the participants experienced changes in their cultural identity perspectives, especially when they were anxious or when their values are challenged or because of the sudden shift of contexts, social networks and cultures. Despite the challenges faced by the students, they managed to adjust to these changes using different strategies such as keeping in touch with old social networks, creatively using common areas like student accommodations and university for social support and networking. Despite the weak interaction with local communities, some participants associated it with their self-efficacy gains that can be acquired along their PhD programme that lasts three/four years, which gives international PhD students an advantage compared to short term programmes.

6.3 Question two: What aspects of the Algerian PhD student sojourners' identity are affected during the experience abroad and in what way?

Algerian doctoral students appear to negotiate identity and develop hybrid identities whenever they are faced with novelty in the new cultural contexts (Comănaru et al., 2017). Findings suggest that students who successfully navigate their experiences abroad usually show higher self-esteem, lower signs of depression and prosocial behaviour (Ward et al., 2011; Nguyen and Benet-Martínez, 2012; Hong et al., 2016).

6.3.1 Personal identity

Despite the different social, cultural and academic challenges that they may face, the Algerian PhD student sojourners managed to cope with the context shift and progress by focusing on elements from their micro systems including their personal identity aspects, such as autonomy, self-confidence, and internal motivation, in addition to sources of social support like family, old and new friends from Algerian and friends from the host country, to accomplish their goals.

A large part of the data focused on Algerian identity development during their doctoral experiences. For instance, being autonomous was one of the various changes highlighted during their sojourn experiences. Many participants had used terminology such as “becoming independent” and “feeling free” to describe their feeling of maturation. Taking control of oneself in a foreign country after spending a life time depending on family for everyday needs and gaining a sense of autonomy was a common response among most of the female participants as this participant illustrated: “*being abroad helped me to become more independent. I learnt to manage my money, manage my time and become more organised*”. The fact that more female participants emphasised on articulating their feeling more power in being independent and in making their own decision in comparison to women’s state Algeria is really important. That raises the question of the social status of women in Algeria and how does that affect them at many levels. I can argue that experiencing a level of responsibility towards their personal wellbeing and their learning process, which they did not have before, would enhance their sense of achievement and self-worth.

6.3.2 Academic identity

It must be highlighted that most of the participants emphasised this previous experience that increased their sense of belonging to the academic community. However, many participants raised different issues, such as being an international student in a different cultural context, the difficulty of balancing the academic and social life, time management and being subject to religious discrimination, which made them feel the PhD life is hard for them.

Concerning their academic lives, a number of participants talked about their life as academics including engaging in academic activities, their relationships with supervisors and academics, and their academic issues. The increased self-confidence of the participants during their study abroad can be viewed as a positive development of their hybrid identity as international students and active researchers and academics. Many participants reported that they felt more independent and comfortable in their research environment where they appeared to be more proactive in their research-related activities and how that is an essential part of academic life. Such findings provide considerable insight into the effectiveness of study abroad in raising the students’ academic identity.

Findings from this research also advocate that interacting with other doctoral students can influence identity development (Foot et al, 2014). Building good relationships with supervisors

and different academics had a positive influence on the Algerian PhD students' doctoral identity and gave them a sense of membership within the university academic setting. Similarly, experiencing feelings of being supported as students inside the academic settings and outside the academic establishments, can also encourage academic identity as students in the UK. (Taylor and Coia, 2009).

6.3.3 Culture and religious identity

One of the most marked observations to emerge from the data comparison was the strong link between religion and personal identity in the Algerian doctoral students' perceptions. In this study, most of the participants consider their faith as an important dimension of identity. They addressed the increasing importance of the religious aspect of their self-image as they lived abroad as a strategy to gain a sense of personal and collective social support from that membership (Luhtanen and Crocker, 1992; Sedikides and Brewer, 2015; Coleman and Collins, 2017). According to Gollnick (2005) religion can be used as a source of support and stability for identity. Moreover, in the context of this study, religion was considered as a way of expressing one's identity as a number of female participants spoke about the symbolic role of wearing hijab in their process of identity formation. They also expressed how wearing the hijab was a part of their Muslim identity and how speaking about it with others would make it more accepted and understood.

In relation to the theoretical framework, Bronfenbrenner's bioecological model considers religion as one of the elements that can influence the development of child/individual and it is usually situated within the Exosystem. However, in the context of Algerian individuals, religion became one of the most important components of their hybrid identity. Participants in this research show a strong connection with Islamic religion since they were exposed to it at different levels including family, society, and culture in general. Findings also suggest that religious values have influenced and are still influencing the Algerian sojourners' lives abroad especially through some transnational practices such as praying, fasting, going to the mosque and wearing the veil as part of their heritage, which they are proud of. However, some participants, from my perspective, are in the process of negotiating the different components of their cultural and religious identities. Performing such religious and cultural activities in a group is a way to gain support and to connect with people who share the same cultural background.

Although some participants consider themselves as a minority in a foreign environment, others saw an opportunity of developing a strong, independent Muslim identity in the UK. By embracing qualities such as openness, independence and empowerment when living abroad for the period of their studies. In fact, most of the female participants experienced ways of negotiating their cultural and religious identities abroad and expressed feelings of anger towards the limited role of women in the Algerian society in comparison to the UK. Participants may perceive the idea of becoming different from their original social group as threatening and the fear of not belonging their original social group can discourage them from adopting values from new contexts.

6.4 Implications for host universities

Due to the small number of participants in this study, the findings cannot be generalised. However, they offer a number of implications to improve the experiences of international students at UK universities.

University staff should be aware that there are a variety of factors affecting the student sojourners' experience of studying abroad. Some factors were identified in this study but still many more, which need to be cautiously treated with the aim of maximising the student sojourners' benefits during their study abroad.

First, host universities could provide more informal contexts for learning to allow international students to reflect more on their actions, values and beliefs. For instance, host universities can create more occasions that can serve as bridges for engaging both international students and local ones to address the sense of isolation and loneliness.

Addressing the unfamiliarity of the academic setting, host universities can organise inductions for PhD students to manage their expectations of studying in different academic, social and cultural contexts. Findings also suggest that universities can provide learning and teaching materials, which are related to the students' major disciplines.

Language is another issue discussed by the participants that host universities can enhance by providing more opportunities for developing the students' language skills. International PhD students for whom English is not their first language can benefit from language workshops for Academic English, writing sessions and informal discussion sessions.

Attitudes towards studying abroad seem to be an interesting point among international students, influencing their experience in a new context. This could be an intriguing factor worth investigating to provide a deeper knowledge about the motivations leading the students to take part in an international journey for studying abroad.

Findings also indicated that the pre-sessional programme for international students played an important role in providing them with the necessary skills to start their PhD research. In line with this, host universities should provide postgraduate preparation programmes in helping international students to develop the necessary language skills and to provide them with an opportunity to experience the academic culture prior to their programmes.

6.5 Implications for Algerian international students

Findings from this research study indicate that most of the participants' interactions with international students were during formal activities organised by the host university or the student accommodation. Students are encouraged to engage within the academic culture in the host universities as well as other universities in the UK by attending different conferences, workshops and other academic activities. Students are partly responsible for familiarising themselves with the British academic culture, which can maximise their learning ability and communication skills. I think that the university resources for social support are essential, but I could argue that it is preferable for students not to rely completely on them and, rather, to find their own formal and informal resources of learning. In this study, only a few students were more creative in finding different ways to interact with others, like kitchen parties and short road trips with international friends.

6.6 Limitations of the study

6.6.1 Researcher bias

The researcher is also an Algerian studying in Scotland. This may have facilitated the understanding of the different feelings of the participants and the analysis of data. However, this may also have brought some potential bias in the interpretation of the data, mainly because of the personal challenges and the researcher's lived experiences abroad, which may have prevented him from objectively seeing the experiences of his fellow Algerian students. In an attempt to reduce the effect of bias on the interpretation of the data behind the photographs, I asked the participants to select, organise and describe their photographs in an order, which they

preferred. This exercise proved to be beneficial in creating an environment of balanced powers by giving the interviewees the freedom of selecting their photographs and talking of them in an order they thought to be important to them.

6.6.2 Time restriction

Due to the time restrictions related to the study context (research conducted as a PhD thesis project) I could only involve students in the data collection phase. I would recommend involving different bodies, such as international offices in host universities and home universities, in different stages of the research project, such as developing research questions and strategy development.

6.6.3 Sampling

First, this was an exploratory study with the typical disadvantages on the qualitative approach, as stated previously. My study was restricted to Algerian PhD students in the UK. The sample was comprised of 62 participants for the questionnaire and 10 participants for the Photo-elicitation interviewing. All participants were from Algeria and they were studying in the UK. It is suggested that recruiting participants from one country would increase the sample homogeneity. However, recruiting participants from different countries would increase the validity of data.

6.6.4 English language

Lastly, I used English as the language of communication in the photo-elicitation interviewing sessions, though some participants mentioned, during the interview sessions, that they feel uncomfortable using English in their interactions. This is why it is preferable to suggest to the participants to choose which language of communication they prefer using during interview sessions. This would allow all participants to talk in the way they are most comfortable. This would also establish a higher level of cultural sensitivity to the study.

6.7 Future research directions

More research should be conducted to improve the understanding of the student sojourners' experiences when studying in other English-speaking countries such as Australia, Canada, the USA, or any other countries. Future research also should focus on different parameters related

to the experiences of international PhD students' motives, goals and development during their stay overseas using different methodologies and theories.

Most of the people now are using social media in different scenarios, which create a relationship between technology and users. Social media users create profiles and connect with other people creating an environment with a tremendous amount of diverse information sources such as photos, videos, voice messages and texts. I believe that this context would inspire future studies on international students' experiences by providing many opportunities to analyse processes of constructing identities from and by social media platforms. It would cast light on the different adjustment strategies of various groups from the events they attend and the stories they share on social media.

After returning home with new emotions, new passions, or even confusion from the different experiences abroad, I believe that it is worth investigating the processes of re-entry into the home country and professional reintegration. Moreover, considering the personal and emotional aspects of the re-entry process and their effect on the professional development of returning PhD students would also be worthy of research.

6.8 Conclusion

This study investigated the Algerian PhD student sojourners' perceptions of the impact of studying abroad on their hybrid identity development. The level and depth of hybridity could not be said to be uniform and varied from individual to individual. However, it was these individual stories that the research aimed to surface rather than to theorise at the general level. It looked at Algerian international doctoral students' challenges, learning experiences and adjustment strategies during their sojourn. Pursuing a PhD programme can be a complex process on its own; however, undertaking it in a foreign country makes the adjustment to the academic system not just more difficult, but also necessitates adjusting to new cultural and social contexts. The method of photo-elicitation interviewing was used as an attempt to enable the research participants to represent themselves and their lived experiences by photographing the world as they see it. Ten Algerian PhD students were recruited as research participants. They experienced academic adjustment in different domains such as academic issues, university resources and academic activities. They also shared their sociocultural adjustment strategies, which can be outlined into three general themes: feeling frustrated, becoming a better version of myself and my life as an academic. In this study, participants expressed different views about

the relationship between environmental factors and their identity development. I used Bronfenbrenner's model of bioecological systems as a framework to organise and interpret the data from this project.

At the Macro system level, participants shared their view on the society and culture of the host country as well as their home country. On the one hand, living in a new society may have caused some participants to experience negative feelings related to culture shock, while others stated that they had some difficulties when they could not overcome some of the home culture influences, which acted as barriers in interaction with others. On the other hand, experiencing life in a different culture raised the awareness of some participants towards the other cultures and enabled them to learn about different cultures, including their own, and to develop more interaction skills.

At the Exosystem, participants stated some of the external factors and influences that affected their development journey either directly or indirectly. For example, most of the Algerian PhD students mentioned different support sources as enablers, including financial support from the Algerian government, social support and facilities by the local university and different communities. At the same level, other participants stated several barriers at the institutional level including the lack of academic support, the inadequacy of research activities and academic writing difficulties.

Interpersonal relationships played a very important role in the Algerian PhD students' hybrid identity development and are presented in the mesosystem. For instance, keeping contact with the families, while living abroad, could provide sojourners with emotional support; however, support from families was not enough in most of the cases. Making new social networks is another way to compensate for the need for social support. At the mesosystem level, connections between contexts and Microsystems appear to have a great impact on how individuals build identity; therefore, new relationships made in the host country could have influenced the Algerian sojourners identity development. Conversely, studying at a PhD level can be challenging for many people in terms of social interaction. Many participants stated several issues including the lack of interaction and support, homesickness, and isolation, which they believe is due to the long hours they spend on their research projects and away from other social events.

At the microsystem level, which is the closest to the person and it represents the immediate environment; participants stated a mixture of old and new elements such as family, old and new friends, the University, accommodation, the mosque etc. Navigating successfully through the new environment and integrating new microsystems into the bioecological model can have a positive impact on the sojourners self-confidence and motivation, while preserving old microsystems such as family, friends and religion, may have provided them with the necessary psychological and spiritual support during the shift between contexts.

Religion is considered as an important element in many Algerian societies. Likewise, it appears to be an important element of many of the participants' lives while studying abroad. In fact, many participants stated that Islam is a fundamental part of their daily life activities, and they highlighted the interconnectedness between their belief systems, the ways they perceive and present themselves and social relationships. For instance, the practice of wearing headscarf for Muslim females can be related to different aspects such as gender, culture and agency. In most of the cases, religious beliefs and cultural expectations made a significant influence on the sojourners preferences for taking part in different activities within the new environment, in the sense that they only participated in activities that are compatible with their Islamic beliefs.

All in all, the experience of the Algerian PhD students studying abroad involved a short-term loss of the social networks and social support sources, which resulted in a lack of social connectedness and distress. The unfamiliarity with the new cultural contexts forced the Algerian student sojourners to make extra efforts to adapt to the new social context as their familiar social groups are absent. Despite the challenges rooted within the academic, social and cultural contexts of study abroad, Algerian PhD students who prefer engaging in complex and positive social interactions managed to cope with the transformation and showed evidence of maturation, accomplishment and overall satisfaction of their experience in the UK. Addressing the adjustment issues in relation to the academic context, findings suggest that the type of support that the participants received from different proximal processes, including positive interactions with their supervisors and staff within the university, made them feel equal, appreciated, and valued members of academic community in the UK.

Interestingly, most of the female participants reported that they found more freedom and autonomy in the UK in contrast to the traditional familial and social contexts in Algeria. Developing a new academic identity as doctoral students gave them more power to stand against

gender inequality and traditional social roles in Algerian societies. Finally, Findings showed that interaction within different contexts can promote intercultural learning and awareness of self and others. Based on these findings, I can challenge the structure of Bronfenbrenner's bioecological model conception of culture as a separate context situated in the macro system of individuals and, instead, culture in the context of this study was introduced as an integral part that can influence the proximal processes and the behaviours of the group under study.

6.9 Reflections as a researcher

Before travelling to study abroad, I was one of the few students who was looking forward to studying abroad. I knew I was going the hard way when I was writing different research proposals and application forms. For a young adult who has never been abroad before, it was not an easy thing to do.

Throughout my PhD journey, I noticed the different changes in my ways of thinking, attitudes and identity that have developed in the last couple of years and progressively understanding the meanings of saying such as "doing, being and becoming" (Wilcock, 2002). As an evolving researcher, I often find myself travelling back and forth through time from the past events to the future potentialities hoping to integrate them into the present moment. This feels new to me as I progress through the different stages of research, however, this experience looks familiar and even predictable for more experienced researchers. I noticed my progression from being a student to a researcher and explored my own narrative as a new researcher.

My international journey started at a University in the south-east of England, where I met many people who are different than me. During my stay there, I found my identity because I got many questions about my background like what is like the foreign policy of Algeria? What about women's and gay rights? Is everyone Muslim there? I felt like I had to defend a lot of things I was not even aware of myself, being from a society where things are considered as the norms. I felt I had to learn about my own culture to explain many things about it, which made more aware of my identity. Moreover, I received a lot of personal questions, sometimes offending questions, but that made me realise that I had to formulate my opinions in a very clear way, which I enjoyed.

Throughout my doctoral study in Scotland, I made many friends, I went to different places and adventures, explored different local foods (haggis) and cultural activities (dancing Ceilidh).

From all these experiences I learned that studying abroad is not just about studying, it is more about living abroad; experiential learning. Reflecting on my experience abroad, I always ask myself whether I did challenge myself enough, or did I get away from my comfort zone? I know that academia is a great source for learning and building knowledge, but I found that most of the time, real learning happens away from academic settings. Friends who do not look like me and who have different opinions about life were a great source of learning and of support in Scotland.

Keeping a digital photo/video diary that contains many of my experiences helped me in reflecting on my own experiences. For instance, I found it useful for capturing memories especially remembering the various occasions I have been through and recording the experiences I had in my life.

In addition, looking back to my photos with the presence of friends and reflecting on the experiences helped me discovering many aspects of myself. I found it useful in remembering thoughts, intentions and feelings when taking those pictures, which allowed me to discover myself on a deeper level.

Looking back at pictures from the past allowed me to see the different changes I have made in my life and to think about the growing process while living abroad. I was inspired to use this as a data collection method where participants can express themselves using their personal photos as a way of reflecting on their lived experiences abroad and how that affected their identity. Discovering identities is a task that requires a great deal of self-reflection and memory, which may take a longer time in talk only interviews. I used photo-elicitation interviews since it is believed to stimulate people to talk about what they know, think, experience and remember, which makes it a productive research strategy. At the beginning of the data collection phase, I found it difficult in terms of providing guidance and encouragement to the participants to talk about their pictures. However, several participants expressed they felt less pressure when talking about the pictures that make the photo-elicitation interview more dynamic and more relaxing than talk alone ones.

Throughout this study, I have found profound pleasure using the photo-elicitation interview method. I think it is due to my interest in photographs, which can provide time travel to the captured past events. My interest in this method can be also due to the sense of collaboration

between the researcher and participants when discussing the meaning, memories and events of the pictures.

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Appendices

Appendix A

Online Questionnaire

Identity questionnaire

I invite you to take part in this survey exploring the Algerian students' perceptions about identity definition and its varieties. I would appreciate knowing your thoughts and opinions about such a complex concept in order to provide a better understanding of your background and experience. This survey should only take 10 - 15 minutes to complete. Be assured that all the answers you provide will be kept confidential.

*Required

Participant Information sheet

University of the West of Scotland
School of Education

Participant Information sheet (Questionnaire)

Title of the research: The experience of student sojourners and identity development while studying abroad.

Name of the researcher: Ahmed Ghodbane

Introduction

You are being invited to take part in my research study. Before making any decision whether you would participate or not, please take time to read and understand the purpose and requirements of this research.

You have been invited to this research for the following reasons:

- You are an adult,
- You originate from Algeria and are funded by the Algerian government for doing your PhD.
- You started your PhD in a UK institution, and
- You are staying in the UK for at least three years.

What is the purpose of the study?

This qualitative study aims at exploring the students' perceptions on the impact of studying abroad on their identities. It is an exploratory study that seeks to understand the international students' experience of studying abroad from the students' viewpoint, and how this experience affects their identity development.

What will you do in this research project?

If you are willing to participate in this research, you will be asked to complete an online questionnaire about your views on identity and its varieties. This will take between 10 and 15 minutes to complete.

Do you have to take a part?

Participation in this research is entirely voluntary; it is up to you to decide to participate in this research or not. If you choose to take part, you will be provided with this information sheet, in addition to a consent form to sign and return. You can always withdraw from this research at any time and without giving any explanation up to the point when the data analysis will start.

What are the potential risks to you in taking part?

There will be no risks to you in taking part in this research project since data will be confidential. A unique ID will be used to ensure identification of a particular questionnaire within the sample, but will neither contain participants' names nor initials. In addition, in any publications based on the questionnaire data, results will be reported as descriptive summaries of the sample and not on an individual level, hence it will be impossible to infer participants' identities.

Data will be stored on the laptop from the university which is protected by a password and using the University's network login. Copies of the processed electronic files with personal information deleted or disguised, will be kept on the university Laptop and on the researchers Drive Cloud, which both are password protected at the login and individual file level. Data will be destroyed 3 years after conclusion of the project.

If you are happy to get involved in the project, you will be asked to sign a consent form to confirm this.

If you have any questions/concerns, during or after the investigation, please contact:

Professor Donald Gillies
Dean of the School of Education
University of the West of Scotland
Ayr Campus
AYR KA8 0SX
Room: 3.023

Researcher Contact Details:
Ahmed Ghodbane
School of Education
University of the West of Scotland
Paisley Campus
Scotland, United Kingdom

CONSENT FORM (QUESTIONNAIRE)

Please tick box

1. **1- I confirm that I have read and understood the information sheet for the above study and have had the opportunity to ask questions. ***

Tick all that apply.

Option 1

2. **2- I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time before data analysis has commenced, without giving reason. ***

Tick all that apply.

Option 1

3. **3- The procedures concerning confidentiality have been clearly clarified (e.g. use of names, codes, anonymization of data, etc.) to me. ***

Tick all that apply.

Option 1

4. **4- I understand that the research team are the only ones who will have access to data collected. ***

Tick all that apply.

Option 1

I- General information

5. **Age ***

6. **Gender ***

Mark only one oval.

Male

Female

Prefer not to say

Other: _____

10. **Please add any comment about identity which is important for you but not covered in this questionnaire:**

Thank you

Thank you for participating in this project. If you have any queries about this form or about the project or your participation in it, please do not hesitate to contact Ahmed Ghodbane at:

Appendix B

Instructions for taking photographs

For the interview, our focus is on learning more about “who you are” and the experiences that have shaped the way you think, act, and see yourself in the world and in relation to others. To do this effectively we will use pictures that you own or collect from other public sources such as social media, phone or camera. These pictures may be in any form – self-portraits, graphic images, pictures of friends, family, homes, colleagues, projects, favourite places, etc. There are no right or wrong pictures.

The pictures that you provide for the interview will be held confidential and viewed only by the research team of this study and will be stored in a password-protected system.

You can provide photographs according to the following categories:

- a. Photos of your daily routines.
- e. Photos of your weekends.
- b. Photos of your social and cultural activities.
- c. Photos your academic activities.

All the photographs will only be used during the interview and none of them will be reproduced for educational and/or non-commercial purposes, in reports, presentations, publications, websites and exhibitions connected to the research project.

Appendix: C

School of Education

Participant Information sheet (PEI)

Title of the research: The experience of student sojourners and identity development while studying abroad.

Name of the researcher: Ahmed Ghodbane

Introduction

You are being invited to take part in my research study. Before making any decision whether you would participate or not, please take time to read and understand the purpose and requirements of this research.

You have been invited to this research for the following reasons:

- You are an adult,
- You originate from Algeria and are funded by the Algerian government for doing your PhD.
- You started your PhD in a UK institution, and
- You are staying in the UK for at least three years.

What is the purpose of the study?

This qualitative study aims at exploring the students' perceptions on the impact of studying abroad on their identities. It is an exploratory study that seeks to understand the international students' experience of studying abroad from the students' viewpoint, and how this experience affects their identity development.

What will you do in this research project?

If you are willing to participate in this research, you will be asked to take photographs, or to choose photographs from your own galleries, that represent who you are by showing aspects of your experience abroad that you think they affected your identity. You may provide as many photographs as you wish. After two weeks, an interview session will be held either by a Skype call or face to face to talk about your experience and the photos. The interview will take around 30 minutes.

Do you have to take a part?

Participation in this research is entirely voluntary; it is up to you to decide to participate in this research or not. If you choose to take part, you will be provided with this information sheet, in addition to a consent form to sign and return. You can always withdraw from this research at any time and without giving any explanation, up to the point when the data analysis will start.

What are the potential risks to you in taking part?

There will be no risks to you in taking part in this research project. Respondents who do not wish to reveal their identity will be allocated pseudonyms in any discussion of interview data. Furthermore, any information which

may reveal their identity (for example, the mentioning a particular address or place of work by the respondent), will be excluded from public discussion. Moreover, data will be stored on the laptop from the university which is protected by a password and using the University's network login. Copies of the processed electronic files with personal information deleted or disguised, will be kept on the university Laptop and on the researchers Drive Cloud, which both are password protected at the login and individual file level. Data will be destroyed 3 years after conclusion of the project.

If you are happy to get involved in the project, you will be asked to sign a consent form to confirm this.

If you have any questions/concerns, during or after the investigation, please contact:

Professor Donald Gillies
Dean of the School of Education
University of the West of Scotland
Ayr Campus
AYR KA8 0SX

Researcher Contact Details:
Ahmed Ghodbane
School of Education
University of the West of Scotland
Paisley Campus
Scotland, United Kingdom

CONSENT FORM (PEI)

Title of the project: The experience of student sojourners and identity development while studying abroad.

Name of the researcher: Ahmed Ghodbane

Email:

Phone number:

Please tick box

- | | |
|--|--------------------------|
| 1- I confirm that I have read and understood the information sheet for the above study and have had the opportunity to ask questions. | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| 2- I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time before data analysis has commenced, without giving reason. | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| 3- The procedures concerning confidentiality have been clearly clarified (e.g. use of names, codes, anonymization of data, etc.) to me. | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| 4- I understand that the research team are the only ones who will have access to data collected. | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| 5- I agree to the interview / focus group / consultation being audio recorded. | <input type="checkbox"/> |

Name of Participant	Date	Signature
Ahmed Ghodbane	18-04-2017	<i>Ahmed Ghodbane</i>
Name of Researcher	Date	Signature

Thank you for participating in our project. If you have any queries about this form or about the project or your participation in it, please do not hesitate to contact Ahmed Ghodbane at:

Appendix D

Interview protocol:

Opening

Hi, my name is Ahmed, I would like to ask you some questions about studying abroad for a PhD degree and how does that affect you on personal social and professional levels.

I hope to use these information to provide a better understanding of the Algerian international students' experience abroad and their perceptions about identity development.

The interview would take less than an hour, is that okay with you?

I emphasise that there are no right or wrong answers for the questions. In addition every information will be confidential. During the interview, I will be making some notes, and if you are okay with it, I will record this interview mainly for academic purposes.

Body

Tell me about yourself, who are you? and how do you see yourself?

How do you introduce yourself when speaking with people from different countries?

Do you think that the physical appearance is important to how you see yourself?

How is that?

Do you think your home identity differ from your abroad identity?

What is similar and what is different?

What changes might you notice in your identity over time (with the change of context?)

Are you still in contact with people from Algeria?

How often?

Did you make new friends here?

Where did you meet them? Where are they from?

What do you do during weekends?

Do you think other people may have a role in shaping your identity? Example family, friends, others etc.

Can you give examples?

Do you think living in a different culture can affect your identity?

Why?

Do you think that you are going to feel the same when you go back to Algeria?

How do you feel about doing a PhD in Scotland?

Closing.

I appreciate the time you took for this interview. Is there anything else you think would be helpful for me to know more about you and your experience abroad? (Maintain Rapport)

I should have all the information I need. Would it be alright to call you at home if I have any more questions? Thanks again. I look forward to meeting you again. (Action to be taken).

Appendix E

Coding process

Coding data from Questionnaire: Open ended question

In few sentences, can you list some of the aspects that you believe your experience abroad has affected in your identity:		
1- I feel more confident and responsible	F: Confidence, responsibility,	Sentiments
2- I have found the real me when being in the UK, in fact being out of the box enable you to do a fair self-evaluation I have found a supportive and welcoming environment when appearance is no more than a choice or a destiny in comparison with home society I become more independent in a sense that I can freely express my thoughts my dreams and enact them	F: I found the real me, Self-evaluation, Supportive, welcoming environment. Comparison with home society, Appearances are not important. Freedom of thoughts, more independence.	Self-reflection Environment. Sentiments
3- I believe that my interaction with people from a variety of cultural and linguistic backgrounds has affected my identity. Public discourse about my ethnic and religious background has changed the way I see myself. In addition, the way university labels us and treats us both in campus and in accommodation has had an effect. As for the language, I believe this has widened the horizons of my identity.	F: Interaction, public discourse about ethnic and religious backgrounds (self-reflection), University, in campus, accommodation language	Interaction Religious, ethnic backgrounds Environment Language
4- Being friend with individuals from different cultures, English Lifestyle affected fairly my identity too and English language itself.	F: Interaction, friendship culture, lifestyle, language	Friendship
5- My experience abroad has showed me that I am part of a global community that I can affect and be affected by meeting diverse nationals/	M: part of a Global community Affect and being affected by Interaction	Belonging Feelings
6- If my experience of living abroad (as a researcher) has affected my identity in any way, then it has certainly made me question who I really am (or was).	F: researcher, Self-reflection questioning the self	(empowerment) Self-awareness
7- Being abroad has affected my identity to a great extent with regards to the academic abilities. It also affected my way of thinking and how do I see life differently in a good way.	M: Academic abilities, different perspectives	Skills
8- I could say that may stay in the UK affects to some extent different aspects of my identity. For instance. My way of thinking has been totally changed.	F: Way of thinking totally changed	Self-awareness
9- Growing up in religiously bounded ulture makes individuals less open to others or at least know very little about them. Living in a country where there are people from different nationalities, cultures, religions, ethnic groups and linguistic backgrounds has shaped to very large extent my identity. I feel that I am now more aware and tolerant when I am in cultural encounters that are different than mine and somehow contradict with my values and beliefs. Additionally, I consider that	F: Religion bounded cultures, self-reflection (religious society) less open to others, Host country, multi cultures ethnicities, languages Awareness of self and others, tolerance of difference of values and beliefs, Self-confidence.	Negative sentiment (religious bounded community) Environment (host) Awareness Sentiments Belonging

<p>my understanding to myself and the other is being built and it is developing, so that now I can travel to anywhere without having the feeling of stranger. The only thing that I think and most of people around me have noticed that in me is that I am still sticking to my cultural values and behaving like an Algerian. This thing really makes me feel safe in the way that I still have the feeling of belongingness to a some point on Earth that is my home land. I also feel balanced between accepting the other and being myself as I cannot deprive myself from a set of beliefs and values that grew up with me and at the same time I cannot reject the other.</p> <p>In sum, my experience abroad has developed my maturity while being by a socially and culturally different setting.</p> <p>Thank you and good luck :)</p>	<p>Sticking to the cultural values and behaviours Sense of belonging, safety, balance. Home culture vs Accepting the others</p>	<p>struggle</p>
<p>10- It made me realise that, once at a certain age, the individual's identity does not change in a different environment.</p>	<p>F: Identity does not change</p>	<p>F: Identity does not change</p>
<p>11- The chance of living in the UK taught me how to be inter-culturally competent in accepting other's cultures and never judge or consider non- Muslims people as bad people. Thus, it helped me to reduce stereotype or even belittle people who are not from Algeria.</p> <p>This experience helped me to be an open minded person towards all the other foreign cultures I faced in my life. In fact, studying in the UK helped me to raise my awareness when talking to professors in a professional way, it also gave me the opportunity to build good friendship with many friends from different countries and know about their culture and respect their religion.</p>	<p>F: Interaction with others, Interculturally competent Non-Muslims academic development, Self-reflection (having stereotypes), Awareness, Friendship, tolerance of difference (culture, religion)</p>	<p>Interaction Sentiment skills Self-awareness Awareness of the others</p>
<p>12- My perception and conception about who I am. My perception about culture. Self-awareness, individuality, independency and autonomy, relationships, nationality.</p>	<p>F: Perception of the self, and culture, Self-consciousness</p>	<p>Awareness of the others Self-awareness</p>
<p>13- Being in a multicultural environment and knowing about other cultures helped me to develop a sense of flexibility in interaction with people from different cultural backgrounds, speaking different languages.</p>	<p>F: Interaction with the other, multi-cultural setting, Flexibility</p>	<p>Interaction Skills</p>
<p>14- My experience abroad has not affected my identity; however, I do feel like I am growing a little more irritated by the bureaucratic practices back home. Whether that is an identity parameter or not is for you to judge.</p>	<p>M: identity not affected Irritation from bureaucratic practices</p>	
<p>15- Living abroad has affected my identity in the following aspects: self-esteem, self-knowledge, self-awareness, flexibility, self-expression through a foreign language and more importantly languages use.</p>	<p>M: Self-consciousness, Flexibility, foreign language use</p>	<p>Self-awareness Skills Development</p>
<p>16- Answering the 'small talk' common questions of where you come from, the accent you have, the level of education, and some other external appearances that challenge people's preconceived knowledge, is a constant reminder of my identity(es). Living abroad and interacting with people from all over the world contribute to my own questioning of who I am, and how I want to be identified. I developed a sense of self-</p>	<p>F: answering the small talk questions Origin, education level, accent are reminders of identity, interaction, self-consciousness developed Awareness of different identities.</p>	<p>Positive sentiment Self-awareness Skills Multiple identity</p>

consciousness that I did not systematically have while in Algeria. Now, I introduce myself and live as an African, Arab, Multilingual, Muslim, Women, Activist, Researcher, Teacher, Sister, Lover, Friend, Daughter of my parents, financially independent adult, and hardworking individual, passionate about gender equality and social entrepreneurship, business minded, and intercultural communicator, professional when needed, and socially approachable. The order can vary and my different identities become more visible depending on when/where/with whom/ and why. My readings for the sake of my research have contributed a lot in constructing and deconstructing my perception of the Self and the Other. My political and literary references as well.	empowerment, layers of identity The contribution of research subject, political references in the construction of the self.	Empowerment
17- Added more confusion to the concept	M: confused	
18- May be exposure to international and diverse people. The fact that internationalize my views as well as my identity	F: interaction with the other	Interaction
19- My contribution in academic activities such as presentations and giving my voice in English. Meeting new people. Living far from my family.	F: Academic setting, voice, Language use , New people maturity far from Family	Environment Empowerment Language Interaction
20- the way I dress up, the way I walk, the way I think	M: Visible culture, thinking	Visible culture
21- Positively, I added features of some values to my identity as I collectively experienced and as I accepted diversity.	M: identity as flexible, diversity , collective experience	identity as flexible awareness of the other
22- I don't think that my identity has been affected by been abroad, but the way I think in terms of research like my critical thinking skills are what seems to be improving.	M: Identity not affected, Improvement, research, critical thinking skills	Identity not affected Academic abilities
23- I think that I became more aware of my identity when I moved to the UK. I started to compare my prior knowledge, beliefs, and culture (which I believe shape one's identity) with those in this new community, and I became more attached to what I stand for. Difference is key, I think!	F: Self-consciousness Consciousness of other (comparison) Attachment to the own ideas	Self-awareness awareness of the other Sentiment
24- What has in a way affected my identity is the way others perceive me. I believe it is all linked to the image we construct about ourselves and others. It could get shaken if other individuals in the society for instance think less of you. However, this does not mean that people will lose their identities and hide behind a mask just to be accepted among a certain group that might have different ideologies than theirs.	F: Others' perceptions Image construction (self and others), Collective self. Awareness of self and others Losing identity	Others' views Awareness of the others Self-awareness Collective self
25- - The study abroad experience reinforced my national identity - it assisted in building a sense of belonging to my home country and the host country as well.	F: National identity, Belonging to both sides	National identity Sense of Belonging
26- well, I really enjoyed my experience abroad, I experienced different things that helped me to move on and develop my skills and I think this affected my identity in different ways too such as, how to act and react to many things around, I realised that I am more involved in social work and activities and I care more about other cultures and always trying to grab what suits me from other people's cultures, also I learned how to express	F: reacting, Experience that improved the Skills, social work contribution, Caring about other cultures Benefit from other cultures Self-expression.	Skills Awareness of others

	myself in different ways, and how to control myself in different situations.		
27-	I can think of my: Mode of interaction Bulk of knowledge Personal habits Language	F: Interaction, academic knowledge, habits, language.	Interaction Skills Language
28-	After being abroad I feel that I have developed a more social identity than before. I did not think before that I needed people around me but it became clear to me that it is essential to have a social life. Being abroad helped me develop a more religious identity and it drove me to think clearly about my principles in life and how to work by them so as to not get affected by others.	F: Social identity interaction, More social identity than before (in the past, or in algeria) religious identity, My Principles Not to get affected by others	Interaction Self-awareness Religion Contradiction
29-	Being far away from my home country as well as my family made me to some extent a more independent, self-reliance and responsible for my own life.	F: Far from home Independence, responsibility My own life.	Environment Sentiments
30-	Cherish my cultural belongings and respect others	F: Belonging, respecting others	Sense of belonging
31-	Being independent and responsible for everything is a positive effect. However, I have less contact with people around me as I'm all the time studying and there isn't much time to have friends.	F: Independence, responsibility, Less contact with people Studying all time Less time for making friends	Sentiments - Interaction - Friends + study
32-	Since coming the UK, I became more open to get to know people from different backgrounds. As a female, I believe I became more feminist.	F: Openness, female, Beliefs, feminist	Sentiments Empowerment
33-	through this experience I do appreciate more who I am, to where I belong and the beliefs I hold, which I did not recognize before or I was not aware of.	F: Self-appreciation, belonging, beliefs, awareness	Self-awareness Sense of belonging Beliefs
34-	I have been always an independent, mature person in my family at very young age. My experience abroad have shown my family that I am capable of taking care of myself. I felt good about that; it gave them relief because I am the youngest member in the family (they never thought I can do it). Also, I never had the opportunity to study far away from home; I studied at local university where I lived with family. I learned to appreciate even more what I have, and been raised to "my religion and country". I have grown both academically and socially during my first 6 months in the UK (Pre-sessional Courses) and I will surely do even more when I start in October my PhD. The past six months showed me how strong I have been, and how venerable I can get; I never knew the lines between those two; "HELL!" I never acknowledged the last. But, I realised that a part of being strong is being venerable sometimes.	F: independent, mature family, lived with family, Youngest member, Studied at a local university Appreciate religion and country Growing up academically and socially Being strong, and vulnerable	Sentiments Attachment Negative sentiment Religion Skills Sentiments
35-	Perhaps all of the effects relate to my personality but not identity.	F: Identity not affected Personality	Identity not affected
36-	My identity was not affected at all	F: identity not affected	Identity not affected
37-	Being in a foreign country gave me the opportunity to discover who I am, my views towards the world has changed through the interaction that occurs with different people from all over the world. Regarding the educational setting, I do believe that I became more confident	F: Discover who I am. Interaction with the other changed my views towards the world. More confidence and comfortable with difference	Self-awareness Interaction New views Sentiments Abilities (academic)

about taking different risks and dealing with different tasks. Being able to work collaboratively with others and think more critically. Thus, the environment has affected my identity positively.	More skills (collaboration, critical thinking) Different environment	Environment
38- Self-evaluation is a unique thing for me. I have also acquired loneliness as opposed to social life back home	M: Loneliness abroad	Sentiments
39- Highlighting my original values against the new one and compare them	M: Self-awareness, comparing own values with new values.	Self-awareness Awareness of the others
40- Since I travelled to different countries, (Arabic countries, Islamic countries and European countries), I came to sum up that nothing can affect my identity because it's who I am. If wherever I go I got influence then at the end who I will be????? Therefore, remaining your language, customs, behaviours, the way you dress that all can prove that you have an identity. As you can have only one name and one face to distinguish you from other, you can have only one identity to be different.	M: Travelling Identity not affected Same language, same dress, same behaviours, same name, same face. Being different than others.	Identity not affected Similar context Self-awareness
41- I became less careful about the others as I needed to save my efforts to myself. More open about what I think regardless of what others would think. Less judgmental and more flexible with situations and people stands.	F: Self-reflection, Becoming less judgemental, More flexible,	Self-awareness Sentiments
42- The interaction with people with different cultural and intellectual backgrounds The ability to look outside the box and accept other's perspectives and orientations in life The ability of openness to multiple options in life	F: Interaction with the others Accepting the others' perspectives, Openness	Interaction Awareness of the other Sentiment
43- Being abroad has slightly affected who I am, how I think and most importantly how I behave and react.	F: Behaviour , thinking	Skills
44- Being a resilient person helped me survive in a new country on my own.	F: Self-awareness, Survive a new country	Self-awareness Negative sentiment
45- My experience abroad helped to have very strong personality and to overcome all my points of weaknesses and it helped to be an independent person and not to rely on any one but myself	F: Strong personality, independence	Sentiments
46- I believe that the fact that I cannot speak my native language at all is annoying sometimes. Because I feel the need to use as it makes feel close to who I am. The fact of knowing other cultures, life styles, ways of thinking and their view on the world makes me realize deeply the sense of my personal identity.	F: Not being able to speak the native language is annoying Connectedness to home self-awareness through the awareness of others	Negative sentiment Attachment Self-awareness Awareness of the others
47- I am still loyal to my Islamic and Algerian identity. The experience abroad makes me aware of the coexistence between me and other identities. I appreciate the idea to keep peace and tolerance by encouraging international identity. When one was asked to identify himself, he replied: 'my blood is red' because he knew that talking about his identity might seem offensive.	M: Loyalty to national and religious belonging. Coexisting of different identities Self-reflection peace, tolerance International identity Blood is red	Attachment Multiple identities Religion Sentiments
48- I believe that my experience abroad helped me in acknowledging how flexible (my) identity can be i.e. I think that one can have many identities at once. For instance, the way you deal with fellow Algerians isn't the same as you deal with	M: Flexible identity, awareness Multiple identity Modes of interaction differ	Multiple identity Interaction

	foreigners. In other words, you can possess many identities at once.		
49-	Language/ culture/ religion/personal principles and believes/ physical appearance and the way of dressing	F:	
50-	I think that living with complete strangers coming from different places of the world is one. Being a researcher and being among highly skilled people and professionals is another one. Being a stranger in the UK is three. You might notice that all the aspects I mentioned revolve around the idea of being a stranger, which I think was very important to me and allowed me to discover things about my identity that I did not realise I had before coming to the UK. Being in the UK is a self-discovery journey to me and a reshaping of my identity.	F: Living with strangers, A part of a different community Being a stranger Self-reflection Reshaping identity	Self-awareness Sentiments negative
51-	* my behaviour has changed * the way of speaking (not using one language while speaking with my family members, for example)	F: Behaviour Language use Family	Interaction Attachment
52-	My point of view that I Should see my life with it changed after living abroad even if it was for just five months, my lifestyle and perspectives changed . I became more addicted to adventures and experiencing new cultures. The way I think now changed drastically as a woman, I feel free for the first time from any traditional social uptight ideas and I feel as if I gained a new personality: a new me	F: Life style, experiencing new cultures woman Freedom Social uptight ideas (self-reflection) New personality	Awareness of the others Sentiments Self-awareness
53-	I believe that being abroad helped me to become more independent. I learnt to manage my money, manage my time and become more organised. Additionally, I care less about people's appearance and dressing I become interested in personalities. Finally, I learned to overcome all my problems alone either psychological or physical. To sum up, my identity has been affected, and in a positive way.	F: Independence, finance, time, organisation, (skills) Problem solving	Sentiment Skills
54-	I became a more hardworking person. I have learned to level-up my goals. I changed my views about people from different ethnic or religious groups, and learned that the only thing that matters is the knowledge that I come out with at the end of my experience.	F: Hard working Goals setting Different views	Self-awareness Awareness of others
55-	I personally believe that it is through the other that I can understand who I am. Getting to know many people from different backgrounds allowed me to find ways to work things out and negotiate my identity depending on the people I am with as well as on the context.	F: Understand the self through others Interaction, Negotiate identity	Self-awareness interaction Awareness of others
56-	Living abroad raised my awareness about the concept of identity in general and my own identity in particular. It made me realize the importance of the religious dimension in my identity.	F: Awareness Religion	Self-awareness Religion
57-	I have become more organized, independent in the sense I have become responsible of myself and responsible for all what I do. Honestly, studying abroad was of great importance for me. I learnt several positive stuffs and this never mean I throw my identity or my religion. But in sense of academic life and social life, i have	F: Skills, organisation, independence responsible Keeping my identity and religion Better Academic Nation	Skills Sentiments Religion Attachment

	become a better person without forgetting my Algerian identity.		
58-	Sense of responsibility/ Patriotism	F: Responsibly, nation	Sentiment, nation
59-	Being more opened to people with different identities and being more understanding. Being more aware of my own identity and not taking things for granted.	F: Openness, understanding Self-awareness	Sentiment Self-awareness
60-	I believe that my experience abroad has strengthened my identity as an Algerian person. Ever since I realized my sense of self, I, admittedly, was never into Algerian music nor was I ever a fan of Algerian food or traditional clothing. Surprisingly, staying for a few months in the UK accentuated my "Algerian" identity. I started to enjoy listening to Algerian music (Malouf), and, now, I would not trade the Algerian traditional food for the world. Age wise, seeing how age is by no means a restriction to how the British live their lives, I somewhat enjoyed turning 24 after fearing that for ages before being to the UK.	F: more national, Enjoying traditional, Music, food , clothing Age, not a restriction in the host culture Host culture life style vs home culture	Attachment Nation Visible culture Different perspective Self-awareness Awareness of others
61-	I started to be more conscious about my identity to start with. I realized how different I am concerning physical appearance which was not that important in my country. I started to think that my identity in the UK is reduced to how I look. People themselves didn't effect my identity per se but my perception of my identity. I started to think more about my identity and ethnicity, considered myself different and belonging to a minority. It wasn't easy firstly but I got used to it. Again living abroad helped my think and be more aware of my identity, didn't change much about it though. I hated that because I looked different I was treated differently and then realized that this is how it is going to be and I was ok with it. Before living in the UK, I never thought that I belong to a minority or seen myself as not being the norm (different)	M: self-conscious Difference (physical) Home vs host country Different perception of the self Ethnicity, Minority Identity didn't change much I hated that I looked different, and treated differently	Self-awareness Negative sentiment Awareness of others Ethnicity Negative sentiment Difference
62-	Several elements has affected my identity while living abroad. The most important thing is being open to other cultures not only the British culture, but also a variety of cultures from different countries. Being a researcher in the UK has transformed my academic thinking which was locally oriented to be more open to international academic life. Religion, gender, and the way I dress also play a significant role in shaping my identity; in other words, being accepted in a western society as a Muslim girl who wears AL hijab has reinforced my self-esteem.	F: openness to other cultures Being a researcher, international academic life. Religion, gender and dressing Muslim girl Western society Reinforcement of self esteem	Awareness of Others Empowerment Interaction Religion Gender Skills
63-	What I could say about this situation is that my identity has not changed since I was abroad, but I can suggest some aspect that may influence me: - cosmopolitan context - way of thinking and organizing - behaving and functioning within a society.	M: identity not changed Skills, Thinking organizing Behaviours	Identity not changed Skills

Appendix F

Coding process

Coding data from the Photo elicitation interview

Academic identity

Amanda: I believe that I am here temporarily as a student sojourner, and my last destination will be in Algeria.	Student sojourner
Ahlam: I am an international student abroad so I have an intercultural, cultural experience, which is new for me, plus the academic experience is completely new for me. As a PhD student you live in isolation so if you don't find those ways of interaction, you will never find them. So the university should work on balance.	International student PhD student
Ali: I always introduce myself as a PhD student in English language, because the more knowledgeable you are the more people will try to approach you in a good way thus they know who you are. It was good for me like one of the things that you feel here as an international student is developing your knowledge	PhD student, International student
Latifa: I am a PhD student eee and I was among the best student in Algeria and I've got a scholarship to study in the UK so I'm so lucky	PhD student
Morad: I am a PhD student in the UWS. I am from Algeria, and if I have the chance to speak about something in particular about Algeria	PhD student
Nora: when I meet some people I just talk to them in a normal way, but when I say what I am doing (I am doing a PhD) they just, like there is a reaction you know something different and you can feel it you can feel it from people's speech and the way they talk to you.	PhD student

Ahlam: In Algeria, as a student, you are not that... the students are not appreciated. You study... most of the student study for a degree, especially like myself. I came from an interior city and our university is so small. So, the main aim for a student is to study for a degree, and finish that degree and find a job.	Perceptions of being a student in Algeria.	Education system in Algeria
Ali: There are many differences between studying here and back home. One of the things that we have got chances to develop ourselves in terms of research. Back home, you are always limited, you need to do extra work and there's not that support and motivation environment. Here you find yourself... it all depends on you, whether you are ready to work hard, you have everything you need just to work hard.	Being a student in the UK Lack of Support Research	Education system in the UK

<p>Ali: Back home, there are many limitations and many potential problems in terms of research in general. So you find it very difficult to cope with the environment in general, but here, it depends on your hard work. You have everything around you, either from the supervisors, from university, there is all the motivation that the researcher needs.</p>	<p>The environment does not support research</p>	<p>Education system in Algeria</p>
<p>Latifa: There is a huge difference, yes. Here in the UK or in Scotland, being a student can give you more opportunities. They respect the things you are doing as a student. The least thing that they do discount for students. This is the least thing that they offer you as a student.</p>	<p>Being a student in the UK More opportunities respect Students are well supported in the UK</p>	<p>Education system in the UK</p>
<p>Latifa: But in Algeria... No. here as a student for example in a conference, if you raise your hand to ask questions before I don't know, someone like a lecturer or a professor, they will give the chance before him. But in Algeria...No they will ignore you as far as he raised his hand</p>	<p>Lack of Power Lack of Voice</p>	<p>Education system in Algeria</p>
<p>Here you feel you are equal with everyone, either the professor or the dean of the school or anyone else. But in Algeria NO. You are a student, you need to kill yourself just studying and studying and that's it. Here they even organise parties for students, trips for students to let that stress go over and so on. Yeah. I think the life of students here is much much better than in Algeria.</p>	<p>Being a student in the UK Equal to every one</p>	<p>Education system in the UK</p>
<p>Nadia: When I did interviews with teachers and students from universities in the west of Algeria. Most of the teachers studied in the UK and they aspire for something new, they seek to rise their students' motivation towards learning and teaching the English as a foreign language. Maybe the reason is because in the west, people are more open minded and modern, even in their culture because in Algeria there are different regions. In the east, they are so preservative... I think that they care more about social norms and rules, whereas in the west, they are open minded. For instance, a colleague of mine from a university in the west, created a freebie club with his friends. One of its aims is to make the students interculturally competent, to accept and respect the others. Teachers motivate and help them to do this, but in the east, teachers, I think they just work for getting money. Hopefully, I will make a change.</p>	<p>Perception of the difference between the universities in Algeria. The west of Algeria, open minded Other students initiative to interact within their university</p>	<p>Education system in Algeria</p>
<p>Nora: I have never been exposed to this. I didn't know even what critical thinking means, because we weren't taught to have reflective thinking. In Algeria for example, in the classroom, we didn't have the opportunity to express ourselves to have our own voice. We were always controlled by the teachers, they are just delivering knowledge, but they don't like to know more about us as individuals, as learners.</p>	<p>Critical thinking Lack of opportunities in the Algerian schools Students-teachers power gap is large.</p>	<p>Education system in Algeria</p>

Academic adjustment

<p>Ahlam I was doing my pre sessional course but our focus was getting (having), secure a placement in universities and having the IELTS, so we didn't have time to go and visit other places in the UK. We were spending most of the time in Kent.</p>	<p>Pre sessional courses</p>	<p>Academic support and facilities</p>
<p>Ahlam This picture is with the Professor Adrian Holliday from Canterbury Christ Church University, he was one of the programme leaders during my pre-sessional course. This person, I can say that I didn't appreciate what he was offering for me during our class, not totally appreciate but I didn't realise what he was doing at that time. His main course was about academic research, interculturality, paradigms, especially paradigms, at that moment it was so boring to learn about them, but during my study now, when I started researching about research paradigms I just remember those sessions that I missed, that I wasn't 100% focussing on.</p>	<p>The relationship with academics and its impact on her academic performance.</p>	<p>Relationship with staff and academics</p>
<p>Ahlam when I started my PhD in my current university, the academic identity is very emphasised as a post graduate student, but sometimes they neglect that I am an international student that my experiences before doing a post graduate is different from those who already studied in the system of the country of the UK or in Scotland.</p>	<p>Culture shock Academic setting</p>	<p>Down side of the academic life</p>
<p>Ahlam Sometimes you find yourself that you are not in the same level as those who are... already studied for the undergraduate or for the masters here, so you work all the time to achieve that level that they already have. They were like working on five years while I was working for five years for a degree purpose not for learning purpose.</p>	<p>Comparing to others Negative sentiment</p>	<p>Down side of the academic life</p>
<p>Ali: The second picture was last year, it was taken during the preparation for the three minutes thesis competition. It was good for me like one of the things that you feel here as an international student is developing your knowledge, and that was one of the best moments for me to present my work to a non-specialised audience and to let them know about my topic in three minutes. I didn't know that I actually could present my work in a good way so by the end I won the best presentation for the audience and that makes me feel proud of myself and my work.</p>	<p>Academic life Competition Positive feeling of achievement</p>	<p>Personal development</p>
<p>There are many differences between studying here and back home. One of the things that we have got chances to develop ourselves in terms of research.</p>	<p>Development in terms of research</p>	<p>Down side of the academic life</p>
<p>Back home, you are always limited, you need to do extra work and there's not that support and motivation environment. Here you find yourself... it all depends on you, whether you are ready to work hard, you have everything you need just to work hard. Back home, there are many limitations and many potential problems in terms or research in general. So you find it very difficult to cope with the environment in general, but here, it depends on your hard work. You have everything around you, either from the supervisors, from university, there is all the motivation that the researcher needs.</p>	<p>academic support environment independence and facilities</p>	<p>Academic support and facilities</p>
<p>I have a very good relationship with either my supervisory team or with any of the staff in the school of education. I found it very important to have such good relationships in terms of academic experience yeah.</p>	<p>The relationship with the staff at the university</p>	<p>Relationship with staff and academics</p>

Nadia: I feel I am a very strong woman, because seeking knowledge... masters or a PhD in one of the UK's universities makes me more mature and develops my self-independence.	Being an academic as form of empowerment	Personal development
Nadia: The supervisors are very kind. For the materials, sometimes I order book or online, electronic books that I cannot find but there is the Sconul card I registered in Glasgow university, if there is nothing here I can go and pick books from there, or just ask the librarian to order it for me.	academic facilities supervisor	Academic support and facilities
Nadia: There is one thing that I don't like, there's no chance for PhD students to work at university. Being an international student, we need to work. And the best thing for PhD student to developing themselves as academics or teachers, or a future doctor is to teach. Unfortunately, we don't have the chance to work at the university.	What the university might offer in the future.	Academic support and facilities
Nora: The shift from being in Algeria, which is a developing country then directly towards the UK in one of the best ranking universities in the UK, I mean the School of Education. I wanted to say that the relationship in here, they are friendly and are really helpful. This is what helped me to being more confident. So I feel people want to know more about me, and what I am doing my research, they really do respect people, which is like totally the opposite in Algeria.	The good relationship with staff at the university and its impact on the participant performance	Relationship with staff and academics
Nora: Another picture... for example this one at the university. I was presenting my research for an audience... em as you know, I'm doing a PhD and I need to present my research. This is something new as well for me. I was studying for 5 years in Algeria, I was exposed to English for 5 years at university but I never had the opportunity to do a presentation for an audience, I feel really ashamed of this. But in here I found more opportunities to develop academically.	Engagement in the academic life Presenting the research for audience The past experience as a student in Algeria More opportunities	Academic support and facilities
Selma: As a student in here, (Scotland) everything you do is important and has a value. My first pieces of writing were very bad, but my supervisor liked it. Now I feel that there is a difference in my style of writing. Even if there are plenty of mistakes a lot of things that I need to work on they never make you down. But in Algeria, they have a lack of communication they don't try to advice in a nice way. They don't try to make you think positively. But here is totally different because everything you do is good, not really good but they give you self-confidence to make things better.	Feeling positive about the relationship with the supervisor Support and help from the supervisor to overcome the issues related to the research.	Relationship with staff and academics
Sara: My supervisor, he is so nice, and even other lecturers and staff members, all of them are nice and they are very helpful people. I found myself very happy and comfortable in this university.	The relationship with the supervisor and its positive impact on the academic life.	Relationship with staff and academics

Ethnic and cultural identities

Ahlam: When I came here to the UK and people start to ask me questions... I was like, I shouldn't say I am an Arab. Yes I learned Arabic as a native language but I'm not an Arab, I am an Amazigh. I am from the native people of Algeria, so I have to show that and talk about it proudly.	Ethnic representation issue	Ethnic identity
It was my first day in my new accommodation, and people started to look at me in a weird way because I was wearing my veil and I am Muslim and it's the same moment of terrorist attacks in Paris. So I got that people were afraid from me because I am a Muslim, and I was afraid from interacting with them but I was courage enough to find solutions and try to do that.	Wearing the veil Muslim woman	Religious identity

I was like, why I am afraid that I am a Muslim. If it is something that I was born with, something that I decided to be at some point in my life, so why I am afraid of it. So I decided to join the interfaith vigil and take a part in it, and express my identity as a Muslim girl.	Religious affiliation Being proud of oneself as Muslim	Religious identity
“Moving to another picture... this picture is from me, one day I decided that I will put the tattoos that old women in my city have, just artificial ones, not real ones, why? Because when you meet people who don’t know any... who didn’t meet any person from Algeria before, they start questioning what do you have in Algeria?”	Representation of ethnicity, Empowerment	Ethnic identity
“This is my first time, I was proud to put this picture on the social media... it’s not modern; It shows the style of Amazigh women in the old times (past). So, everyone was talking like why you have tattoos. All women back home had tattoos because it was a symbol of beauty.”	The use of social media as a tool of representation and empowerment.	Ethnic identity
Morad: In this picture, I was performing my Friday’s pray in a mosque in Glasgow and I liked the Arabic and Islamic design of the door. I missed the adhan (call for prayers) because here I don’t hear it except with my phone. As if I am losing a part of my identity as a Muslim.	Religious practice Religious identity	Religious identity
Nora: But I do feel really proud about being Kabyle, because we are still sticking to our identity... yeah. Other people in other wilayas, regions, they are thinking that we are racist. When I introduce myself, I always say that I am Kabyle, not just Algerian. Most of people perceive Algeria as an Arab country and that makes me sad, because we’ve got a diversity. We’ve got different cultures, different languages...	Ethnic affiliation Representation of ethnicity	Ethnic identity
Nadia: As a Muslim myself (hesitating) I was stereotyping people without knowing them, I had an essentialist point of view. It is really hard to maintain this religion abroad, because, you know as you are living here, everything is normal for you, and you are free to do whatever you want; there are no family rules. I find it very hard.	Religious affiliation Culture shock Hard to maintain religion in the host society. (wearing hijab)	Religious identity
Nadia: I am Shaouia... I am Berber but I don’t... because my father and mother don’t speak the language inside the house I just understand it. But here in Scotland, they present their culture, even in the roads by wearing the kilts and playing the bag pipes. In England they don’t do such things.	Representation of ethnicity	Ethnic identity
Latifa: in Islam, the girl when she grow(s) up, there are some physical changes show up on her body so she might attract men so it’s better to cover her hair and pay attention on her clothes. In our religion women have a role in the society. I don’t like the way women are treated in Algeria.	Perceptions why women wear hijab. Religious practice Negative sentiment about how women are treated in home society.	Religious identity
Actually, Algeria is classified to be Arab country, but me myself I’m Berber okay? My mum is Berber, and my father is the same. But I don’t know, I don’t speak any of the Berber languages.	Ethnic identity struggle.	Ethnic identity
Selma: I am very proud of my background, so I am originally Berber, but there is no classification for you (laughter) unfortunately.	Positive feeling about her original Ethnicity	Ethnic identity

Home culture and society

Ahlam:		
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When I talked about representation of the Algerian girls and talking about my experience, the society limits you, limit your identity and who you are, limit your role in the society, and putting boundaries in everything.	The limited freedom and voice of women in home society.	Limited freedom and voice of women in home society Home society pressure
Ahlam: I grew up in a family that men have the decision to do, they decide instead of us not we decide ourselves. It's the same thing I think for almost all the women back home, especially in the east of Algeria or in my city.	Gender inequality within the family	Limited freedom and voice of women in home society Home society pressure
Ahlam: When I talked about representation of the Algerian girls and talking about my experience, the society limits you, limit your identity and who you are, limit your role in the society, and putting boundaries in everything.	The limited voice of women in home society.	Limited freedom and voice of women in home society Home society pressure
When I was in Algeria, I wasn't brave enough to put my picture as a profile picture, or to post my pictures; others too. But when I came to the UK and started interacting with people, and they saw that if you have a real life identity and you are a person that exists in real life and the virtual world is another world.	Limited freedom on Social media and the online identity.	Limited freedom and voice of women in home society Home society pressure
Amanda: It would really bothers me that being a female in Algeria, is that people and society are expecting from you to grow up, to be honest all time, to be perfect all time, to get married, to have children and that's it. So these are the parameters to be recognised as female, and it's really bothering me you know.	Negative feeling about the Women's social role in home society	Gender identity Home society pressure
Amanda: I used to sing when I was a child, But my parents were against that, so I stopped.	Family pressure, The limited freedom of women in home society.	Limited freedom and voice of women in home society Home society pressure
Ali: Back home in Algeria, being a male... we do have that kind of discrimination, not in a bad way but... like being a male, there are things that a male needs to do and the same for females. For me, being a male, there are many things that I need to do, like in university, the way you speak, the way you behave, the way you walk. Everything matters being a male in Algeria. Even within the family, there are things, you are the male you need to do them. For example, there are things like at night probably going out to get something, I am the one who must go, not my sister because I am the male. As a male you find that there are many things that you are responsible for	Social role In the Academic context Social role within the family Responsibility	Male point of view about home society
I do believe that one of the main reasons is culture I think. Something that our grandfathers used to do, and our parents as well, and then it came to us. We kind of trying to live the same way as our parents, but sometimes it doesn't work for us as the new generations, especially for us who came here abroad in a foreign country and when we go back home, we find it very difficult sometimes to cope with things, even going back for just a month, and there are things like, why we are still doing such things.	Social roles are based social norms and traditions. Cultural adjustment Questioning the self	
Morad: Having this scholarship, as if the government trusts you to build yourself and be more knowledgeable and share the knowledge with other people back home.	Power exercised by the government.	scholarship
Latifa: Maybe I got more respect because I'm wearing [the hijab] yes. But as I told you, there are other things that are missed like em to be a woman or a female I can't really be sociable in the society because of the traditions and so on.	The limited freedom and voice of women in home society.	Limited freedom and voice of women in home society Home society pressure

I felt so so comfortable just because I took off the hijab.		
Houda As women, we were rarely used to post pictures. For me, it doesn't happen at all to put my pictures or to post them on social media. I had only few pictures, and I made sure that I am the one who took them and I want to keep them personal.	The limited voice of women in home society, and on social media.	Limited freedom and voice of women in home society Home society pressure
Nadia: When I was a child, I used to have a small bike, but I stopped when I started my secondary school because it is not the same as here. It's a matter of society, because people, especially men, when they see a girl riding a bike is something not normal at all. I feel bad because I fancy riding bikes but I cannot ride it in Algeria until I came here in Canterbury and Scotland.	The limited freedom of women in home society.	Limited freedom and voice of women in home society Home society pressure
Nora In Algeria for example, in the classroom, we didn't have the opportunity to express ourselves to have our own voice. We were always controlled by the teachers, they are just delivering knowledge, but they don't like to know more about us as individuals, as learners.	The limited voice of students in Algeria classrooms.	Limited freedom and voice of women in home society Home society pressure
Nora: In Algeria, for example the way of dressing, I cannot dress what I want, even if I don't wear veil but I always need to look to the others how they will see me in the society because I am supposed to respect some rules.	Limited freedom in dressing due to social norms.	The limited freedom and voice of women in home society. Home society pressure
Going out at night is totally new, I'm not used to it in Algeria, but here it like something normal for them. Maybe it has to do with our culture or religion or about safety, it's not safe	The limited freedom of women in home society	Limited freedom and voice of women in home society
Houda: As women, we were rarely used to post pictures. For me, it doesn't happen at all to put my pictures or to post them on social media.	Limited freedom in representing oneself on social media platforms.	Home society pressure
Latifa: In Algeria, especially in my home town in the east of Algeria we are a bit conservative so women are not allowed to attend concerts.	Conservative society in the east of Algeria	The limited freedom and voice of women in home society.
Selma: Most of men in Algeria think that they are better and females are not equal, they do not have the same rights.	Gender equality issue.	The limited freedom and voice of women in home society.
This is very important, communication, this is the lack that we have in Algeria, lack of communication. They just give you orders and you need to obey without discussing, and this is wrong.	Power issue	The limited freedom and voice of women in home society.

Language and Identity

DATA	CODES
Ahlam: The first thing that people ask you is that how many languages you speak? The first thing is good because you show that you are a multilingual person. The second is that you have been in touch with many cultures, and even if we talk about French, it is related to Algeria's colonisation during 132 years, and this period is enough for a culture to have roots in the place. The French people when they came, they came with the language and with the culture and all of that. But if I consider French as a language of colonisation; I will never learn. But if I consider it as a language that will open me doors for communication with others. Be open to other languages and cultures as well.	Advantages of being a multilingual person abroad.
I grew up with my family, it is Amazigh family it is Shaoui family. Both my parents speak Sahoui, but with us, they speak Arabic. My father was so proud of	Language and ethnicity

Arabic. I do understand the Tamazight language (shaoui) I speak it sometimes but not fluently.	
I speak Tamazight, Arabic, French, I'm not a big fan of French, I was among the best students of French language but when I started learning English they just decided, no English anymore, because my father was a French teacher but I decided to learn English and no more French. So I believe that I have an upper intermediate level in French and English.	Language and empowerment (having a voice within the family)
Ali I do speak my mother tongue, French, and English. It depends on the group you are with, most of the time here in Scotland I only use English when I am in an international group I tend to use English. But sometimes when im with my Algerian colleagues and we are the only ones, then we use Arabic or our slang.	Being a multilingual person abroad.
For me for example, speaking English and the way reached my level of English and the way I speak. I feel myself, yes I did achieve something, especially when I speak with people and they tell you about your English how good it is. It gives some feeling of achievement and pride at the same time.	Positive sentiment when using the English in communication.
We all know that Berber languages, and many international people ask me the question why don't you speak them. It makes me feel ashamed, I think that Tamazight language is a language that any Algerian should study and know. It is a shame that only some parts in Algeria do speak it and many others don't. We don't have Tamazight in our schools. Some people know the history and they ask about Tamazight.	Negative sentiment of not being able to use Tamazight (National language)
Houda: If I speak about passed events about Algeria or events in Algeria I use Algerian Arabic. If I speak about academic subjects or with international students, I use only English. Even with French people I use English because I am not that competent in French. And I think that speaking a new language has an effect on identity. I am using frequently, Algerian Arabic, no Berber, Algerian Arabic French, English, some Spanish and Italian.	Using different languages in different contexts Being a multilingual person
I usually use my mother tongue only with my family and friends in my city. The majority of my friends here in the UK don't speak it. A flatmate of mine from china she heard me speaking shaoui with my family, she asked about it and I felt proud of telling her about it. There are some colleagues at uni who normally they speak Shaoui, and they belong to the same culture (shaoui). Sometimes I feel that they dislike speaking this dialect despite its value.	Using the dialect to show ethnicity
Stacy: My mother tongue is shaoui and I speak Arabic standard and some French and English.	Being a multilingual person.
When I speak English I feel a bit frustrated and anxious. I have a problem with the English language since it is not my first language. Sometimes, I am afraid of making mistakes in front of the audience...	Negative feeling about using English in communication
Nadia I am Shaouia... I am Berber but I don't... because my father and mother don't speak the language inside the house I just understand it.	Language and ethnicity
Nora: Most of people perceive algeria as an Arab country and that makes me sad, because we've got a diversity. We've got different cultures, different languages... mine is Berber so I am Berber or Amazigh yeah. I do speak Berber language, Tamazight, but most of the time we speak in French Berber and of course I am using Arabic with other Algerians because they cannot understand me, especially friends in here (Scotland). I'm always using Arabic and English of course, there are some who can understand me because they are speaking a language which is similar to mine, but they can't understand me 100%.	Multiple cultures and languages in Algeria. Negative feeling Being able to using different languages when communicating in different contexts.
Nora: Other people in other wilayas, regions, they are thinking that we are racist. This is something really really sad for me because we are just trying to look for our identity. We are looking to have it back. I feel that I am not free to represent my identity in Algeria.	Language and ethnicity, negative feeling
Selma I am very proud of my background, so I am originally Berber, but there is no classification for you (laughter) unfortunately. So sad when I need to classify	Language and ethnicity

myself I'll just choose Arab because I am supposed to be Berber, but I just say I am originally Berber Arab..	
So Arabic is my first language, with Berber (Tamazight), French is my second language, and English is the third (laughter) I am really proud of this. When people ask me about myself, I make sure to tell them this	multilingualism and empowerment
Latifa: once, I went to a shop and a lady asked me when I was helping her because she was an old lady. She told where are you from? And I told her I'm from Algeria. She told me "tu parles le Français? Do you speak French? I told her yes, then we had like a small chat in French, and I felt so proud because, okay they know that Algerians, we are educated; we speak more than one language, and yeah. And I feel proud that I know more than one language yeah.	Interacting with others using different language

Socio cultural adjustment

Ali: What a male can do, you find a female that can do the same. At night, back home, for a female to go out on her own, that's very rare because... probably the environment is not safe, but here in Scotland there is no such a thing. One of the things that helped me is that I have read about the British culture before coming in here. We didn't really get a cultural shock when we first came here. I think that's one of the things that helped us to easily cope with the live here... yeah...	Perception about gender equality in Scotland Before traveling abroad
So when you come here to Scotland and you find no big difference between the two genders it is almost 50/50 wherever you go. What a male can do, you find a female that can do the same. At night, back home, for a female to go out on her own, that's very rare because... probably the environment is not safe, but here in Scotland there is no such a thing; everyone is safe...yeah.	Male female equality.
I don't tend to let my Algerian culture affect me here because sometimes you cannot... how to say it... you are in a foreign country so you need to cope with the life here. Going to pub doesn't mean yeah I have to drink or something, I just like to go with friends but that doesn't mean drinking or doing stuff which are not part of our culture. And yes, there are things that do back home and still doing here, like going to the mosque and stuff like that.	Cultures tension Cultural adjustment
Latifa: For example I got many things from here like I can eat in the street, no one will look at me and laugh out loud in the street and when I went back to Algeria I was doing the same, and people looked at me as... this is something of disrespect or something like that. I forgot myself because... Yeah I got used with the things I do here yes.	Example of freedom of act as a woman.
Nadia: Here people are so friendly and there is culture, they preserve and protect their culture, but in England it's like modern life. But here in Scotland, they present their culture, even in the roads by wearing the kilts and playing the bag pipes. In England they don't do such things. The Scottish accent is very hard to understand, and I do have some Scottish friends, at the very first days I couldn't understand anything, I just reply by yes (laughter). But when I got involved by speaking with them every time, every day, now I understand everything they say	Perception of different cultures in the UK. Culture adjustment Scottish accent
Nora: In here, I can wear whatever I want, I know people will not look at me. Here I feel they are more open, they are not judging people which is the opposite in Algeria. I've never been abroad, this is my first experience. I do meet people from different cultures and they've got different backgrounds. This is something really amazing, it gives me the opportunity to discover and to acquire new things new knowledge. I felt like I was in a small box, I wasn't open minded, I didn't know the meaning of life now I'm more open yeah... I am seeing from another vision other aspects of life. Even for example where I live in the accommodation, sometimes we do parties in the kitchen, we play traditional songs, or songs that represent culture for each country like our dance, our music. So I'm even teaching them how to dance, and it makes me proud of my culture and my identity.	Freedom The transition from living in Algeria to living in Scotland. Cultural adjustment Living in the student accommodation as a way to

	socialise and meeting people from different countries.
I don't wear hijab, but if I wear it, I'm not gonna feel comfortable. I think that not wearing hijab helped me in blending in the society	Easy cultural adaptation
Selma: I didn't find myself in a situation where people treated me in a bad way or that I'm not welcomed. Most of people are nice here. I felt like something started to change here. I feel more comfortable and accepting the culture around me. I am accepting more people	interaction with the others. Culture adjustment.
Morad: It's good to respect other people and to know about them. My culture is here and their culture is there, and by knowing each other culture we can build that bridge in order to know.	Distance from the other culture.

<p>Ali: I do experience it myself, when introduce myself with just my name and country, you can see it in their faces and the way they behave with you. But when I mention that I am a PhD student in English language then people do pay attention or they change the way they talk to me. That's why I think that knowledge matters.</p> <p>I find very surprising when I first met my supervisor. I put him in a position very high for me since he is a professor as we used to deal with our professors back home. They are like ghosts, you only see them when they come to the department, and it is rare to get a chance to meet with one of them... but when I came here, and then I met with my supervisor for the first time, he is the dean of school, I found how humble he is. His career as a professor doesn't affect him how to deal with people he just treats you the same; a staff member as any of the other staff. That was really surprising for me.</p> <p>I have chosen to live in a student accommodation because there are many international people coming from all over the world. For example, Erasmus students come for four months then go, and other students come then go and I have the chance to knowing them and their different cultures. Even the way like... being in the accommodation with international people means you are always speaking in English, that's a good thing... But if you are in flat on your own you rarely use English. So I find it very beneficial living in a student accommodation.</p> <p>This picture was with my (Scottish) girlfriend that was the time when sometimes I have some much study to do so it is good to go for a trip. That picture was in Stirling in a safari park, we had a good day forgetting about studies and pressure in life in general, and just enjoyed our time. Going to safari park made me feel like I am back in Africa, you can see all the animals similar to what we have back home... yeah that was really good.</p>	<p>Interaction with the others.</p> <p>Culture shock</p> <p>The relationship with the supervisor</p> <p>Power distance is</p> <p>Living in a student accommodation and its advantages</p>
<p>Houda: I just say everything about myself, and I like being mindful about where I come from, because I'm proud of this. I don't mind if there are cultural differences because I believe that they are learning from us, like they want to know about our culture and about things they don't have, so I don't mind.</p> <p>I think that Algerians should be always aware that whenever they speak to other foreigners, they should mind that they reflect the other Algerians so you should have this kind of readiness. Because it happens to us like a German person or an Italian person, if he speaks or does anything, we think that he has an Italian identity or German identity so he should reflect that in the best way. But in the other things like the academic life, I believe that everyone is independent.</p> <p>I thought my experience would not be so different from the previous experience in the Algerian university, but gradually I came across other aspects like how to be involved within the society and how to know about other cultures and other people other nations. So I thought about how to start friending people. In the beginning I was not so friendly; all I was saying to myself is that I don't have time, I am here to concentrate on my studies and I don't need to be friend with everybody so bad for me. Then I changed my mind and I started friending people. I have a friend from the UK (England) and she was so helpful, she gave me advice on how to be</p>	<p>Interaction, Relationship,</p> <p>Being aware of the presence of cultural differences.</p> <p>Considering Algerians as a homogeneous entity.</p> <p>Culture shock Challenges faced during the PhD journey</p> <p>No balance between the social and the academic life.</p>

friends with people and how to make friends. I had many barriers and she helped me to distract those barriers.	Positive sentiment about her new friend.
Morad: It's good to respect other people and to know about them. My culture is here and their culture is there, and by knowing each other culture we can build that bridge in order to know.	Awareness of cultural differences
Nadia: English helped me to know so many people who became my best friends, and that helped to improve my English skills and to make successful conversations with them. I live in a student accommodation, I try to socialise with people from different cultures and countries and I realised that everyone has his own religion and I need to respect it. I showed this picture to my friend from the west and she was shocked. She told me that this looks like war not a wedding. Sometimes she finds me praying and she asks about that, but she never say something as I used to say about others. She respects my religion and learned to do the same.	Language as a means of socializing. Living in a student accommodation is an opportunity for socializing Cultural adjustment Using pictures to present her culture. Cultural adjustment Religion Cultural adjustment
Selma: Now I am more comfortable to introduce myself and keep a conversation with a native speaker. To speak about what I am doing in this country, what I used to there. To tell people about my country about my religion, my food, what can I do? I find it different in general.	Interacting with others and talking about culture in general. Cultural adjustment
Sara: My friend who is from china, we always try to take her culture and compare it with mine as I try to have the most of it. We talk about costumes, food and festivals...	
Ali: That picture was taken in the British museum, I remember that I went to see my friend in London. I haven't seen him for a long time. That was the first time that I got the chance to see London. The first time I went there I didn't like it, but at that day, he showed me many places that I didn't know about before, we had a good time. That makes me feel like having your friend, we were friends back home, and the way we were hanging out in London and stuff like that eating Algerian food, it makes you feel like you're back home. That picture was in last week in Loch Lomond, we rented a car. That's what I usually do when I'm not in a mood for study, I run out from study and go and have fun and discover Scotland. This picture was with my girlfriend that was the time when sometimes I have some much study to do so it is good to go for a trip.	Traveling Old friend Continuity of elements like memories, friendship. Traveling around Scotland with friends Study pressure.
Morad: This one was taken in Tunisia last summer, I met with many people from Italy Tunisia Algeria Libya... it was a good opportunity and I enjoyed myself in a country that is very close to us. We share a lot of cultural things, history, and identity. It was my first time there. Traveling abroad gives a person an occasion to see the way other people think to communicate with them, to build a strong relationship.	Traveling
Houda: I started going to trips organised by the university. I spent some good time with my friends.	Traveling with friends
Latifa: this picture was from last year, I went with my friends to a concert because I like the singer sami youcef yeah. [...] it was my dream to attend a concert to anybody (laughter) and sami youcef came to Glasgow last year and I like the kind of music	Going out with friends (females)

<p>he sings (soufi music) it is a type of music the expresses devotion to god, and it even enhance the ... physical and the spiritual aspects of the listener... yeah that's why I went and had a lot of fun with my friends. There are some friends who just went because it's a concert but after attending it was like fabulous yeah.</p> <p>yes, this picture is from a party called the Arabian tea party. It has been organized by the Muslim society at the UWS.. yeah, I went with my Algerian friends, and we decided to dress up Algerian traditional clothes all.. yeah. The party was for females, only for ladies, so e we were able to act freely and we took off our hijab, and we felt normal. Yes. The party was more religious, they were even playing religious music. But em me and my friends asked them if we can play Algerian music, so, since we played the Algerian music, the overall weather changed, and we started like dancing and teaching them to dance in Algerian way. And we had so so much fun in that party. And in that party I gained new friends yes, from other Arabic countries, and even Pakistan and so on.</p> <p>In this picture, I was still new here. Em, my favoured place Loch Lomond. Yeah, I went with my friends, Scottish and Pakistani, we had barbecue there. They were all the time eating, meanwhile I got fascinated of the views there, and I kept only taking pictures to the views.</p>	<p>Religious music</p> <p>Religiously accepted party</p> <p>traditional outfits.</p> <p>Friends from home culture</p> <p>Traveling around Scotland</p>
<p>Nadia: The first picture represent my favoured hobby, I think sport is very important for the physical and the mental aspects. Cycling help me reducing my stress, especially when I'm studying.</p> <p>This picture, was in Brehead, we went for skating.</p>	<p>Hobbies as a way of reducing stress from the studies.</p>
<p>Selma: We are a group of friends having a good time. We went for a walk and a barbecue at the same time. Here we are skipping from the PhD.</p> <p>I've been to Stirling, and there was a room in the castle with musical instruments. As you can see, there is English, Scottish culture. I found it very useful to take a picture here with these instruments because I am a fan of music, I like to sing to hear.</p>	<p>Going out with friends</p> <p>Traveling around Scotland and discovering new places.</p>

Identity negotiation

<p>Ahlam: The first thing that they taught us is we don't use names (titles, or honorifics) like doctor, or professor to communicate with them, but we have to use their first name and that's it. That gives you the insight that there is no barrier between the teacher and the student, so you start seeing yourself like you can achieve what they achieved. They teach you that, if he achieved that place, you will be able to achieve it.</p> <p>When you go abroad, all your identities that you took for granted when you were at home, you start showing them for others and be proud of them. Yes now I am proud to say that I am Amazigh, I was proud but now I can say it that I am an Amazigh not an Arab.</p> <p>When I was in Algeria, I wasn't brave enough to put my picture as a profile picture, or to post my pictures; others too. But when I came to the UK and started interacting with people, and they saw that if you have a real life identity and you are a person that exists in real life and the virtual world is another world. I am brave enough to do that even if my family doesn't like that.</p> <p>I don't see myself as a woman who has a role only limited to kitchen and family anymore. It's not about doing PhD or living abroad, it's about having that distance from where you are from, and interacting with others and see other women, even if they don't cook but they are appreciated. I don't think that a woman in my city or in my family she doesn't cook will be appreciated because she doesn't know how to cook properly. But when I came here I realised that all the roles that the society gave to me or to other women back home or my city or my family as cultural roles or... because of men power.</p>	<p>insight that there is no barrier between the teacher and the student</p> <p>Ethnic identity empowerment</p> <p>Online representation of self-identity</p> <p>Family and society boundaries.</p>
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	Revolting against Social roles for women.
<p>Nadia: I feel as a very strong woman, because seeking knowledge in one of the UK's universities makes me more mature and develops my self-independence. When I was in Algeria, I used to depend on my parents. My father is and always been responsible for us, but when I came here, I learned how to be self-independent and how to do everything by myself, otherwise, no one will do it for me.</p>	<p>Strong woman Independence on parents</p>
<p>Amanda As if I am saying that though I am in another country that's really different from mine and I am migrating, I won't forget. Holding the flag I am saying I am Algerian. The way I am putting the flag has something to do with gender (covering half of the face, mouth and nose) at that time, I was new in the UK, and I wasn't allowed to show my face. I posted that picture on Facebook and my family messaged me to delete it. Now I feel free and more independent, if I want to put my picture I will put it. Now I am doing so using messenger (application) the pressure is not as it was.</p> <p>Saying that I am a PhD student, gives you more confidence, more power, more energy, more existence. You see!</p> <p>I have a YouTube channel where I share my experiences in the UK. Like where I go, what I'm doing, what my university looking like, what I am doing in a daily life.</p>	<p>The national identity is emphasised by using the flag in the picture</p> <p>Empowerment, against social norms.</p> <p>Using social media to represent one self.</p> <p>Empowerment</p> <p>Representing one's self through social media</p>
<p>Nora: For them, when a woman study and have a high level they will respect her more, she will have more power of course.</p> <p>So being in here doing a PhD gave more power, especially in the way of thinking. I feel that I am not thinking the way I was in Algeria. I mean like critically.</p> <p>When I went back to Algeria to do my data collection with the Masters students, I wanted to give them something different to give them freedom to express themselves, to respect them, and to listen to their ideas. I wanted to deliver something different, because I do believe that everyone is different. I had the opportunity to teach them for a short period. So I felt really really proud, because, I can say all of the students were talking with me like I gave them something different, and they were really thankful to this, being different, and bringing something new for them which they're not used to it.</p>	<p>Women power and education</p>
<p>Houda: I am here in the UK and there is nothing that differs between men and women I feel like I have more power and equality.</p>	<p>Empowerment and equality</p>
<p>Ahlam: When I first came to Scotland I stayed in a student accommodation, I got many reactions as I mentioned before when I came during the terrorist attacks, some people have very weird looks.</p> <p>I got rejection many times, I got those weird looks, I had that negative feeling inside but I didn't let it dominating my behaviours.</p> <p>People were telling me how would you become a Muslim without even having the choice to have another religion? Because of my social behaviour, some people call me a sociable person. I know I am sociable and it affects me negatively sometimes. I went many times crying to my room, but I know that reflection afterwards, when reflect you learn a lot and develop that identity of being open with people and having a lot of friends.</p>	<p>Identity negotiation</p>
<p>Latifa: When I first came here in Scotland eee as you can see it is less accepted to Muslim people.</p> <p>For example, in shops, sometimes, the cashiers act normally with other people like "thank you darling... do you need a bag?" But with me I feel that they use different language "Hi... do you have a bag? Yes/ no" it's not like a normal conversation like this.</p>	<p>Identity negotiation</p>

<p>yeah. Here there were even Scottish girls.. yeah so they started like em having fun with us without any restrictions as I'm like you, I have hair as you have hair. So yeah we dance together, we do everything together.. yes. Here I felt so so comfortable just because I took off the hijab.</p>	
<p>Nora: For example, in Algeria, I don't feel like myself, I feel I'm always controlled and following the others and depending on the others. I see most of Algerians are following the life of others, that's why I don't feel free to do whatever I want.</p>	Identity negotiation
<p>Selma: When I firstly arrived here, there was not that much Muslim or veiled girls, especially in the university. Some people find it weird, I can tell from their eyes how they look at me. Some of them just tried to avoid me, other tried to smile at me or to speak to me but I didn't find myself in a situation where people treated me in a bad way or that I'm not welcomed. Most of people are nice here.</p>	Identity negotiation
<p>Sara: I use my dialect only with people who can use it, and I feel so comfortable. However, when I speak English I feel a bit frustrated and anxious.</p> <p>However in this country or at university, I feel frustrated and hesitated to introduce myself because I don't know those people, I don't know those lecturers. In addition, I have a problem with the English language since it is not my first language. Sometimes, I am afraid of making mistakes in front of the audience...</p>	Identity negotiation

Negative feelings

<p>Ahlam</p> <p>The main aim for a student is to study for a degree, and finish that degree and find a job. While the main aim behind learning is quite neglected by the university and I didn't find any support or guidance that we should show our identities as academics future academics or as students.</p> <p>when I started my PhD in my current university, the academic identity is very emphasised as a post graduate student, but sometimes they neglect that I am an international student that my experiences before doing a post graduate is different from those who already studied in the system of the country of the UK or in Scotland.</p> <p>For example there is no chances to interact with other international students, you can create chances outside the university or at the library but there is nothing organised by the university to put all the international students in contact with home students, there's not something like that. And as a PhD student you live in isolation so if you don't find those ways of interaction, you will never find them. So the university should work on balance.</p> <p>When I was in Algeria, I wasn't brave enough to put my picture as a profile picture, or to post my pictures; others too. But when I came to the UK and started interacting with people, and they saw that if you have a real life identity and you are a person that exists in real life and the virtual world is another world. So you need to show yourself, you need to have a place and it gives you an online identity through posting your pictures not the pictures of others. This is me, if someone looks for my name and finds my picture, in an academic setting or outside. So I started... I am brave enough to do that even if my family doesn't like that. I will face a lot of challenges, some people may not accept who I am, the independent, the open, and the curious me this is what I'm afraid of.</p>	<p>No support or guidance as a student back home.</p> <p>Experiencing a hard transition from home university to a UK university.</p> <p>How the university might provide support to international students</p> <p>The limited voice of women and their roles in home society.</p> <p>The experience abroad and empowerment through social media as an academic person.</p> <p>Future challenges</p>
<p>Latifa:</p>	

<p>I was like in the street waking, a Police man came to me, and he told me you need to disappear now because there is like a protest against refugees from Syria and Afghanistan...</p> <p>In ***** they were so so racist; they asked me to take off the scarf, and this is what I did I carried on two days without it for my security.</p> <p>The first days I came here I had like strong feelings I feel so bad missing my mum I had like four sessions and they were so helpful. They even helped me to develop my English by the way.</p> <p>I got many things from here like I can eat in the street, no one will look at me and laugh out loud in the street and when I went back to Algeria I was doing the same, and people looked at me as... this is something of disrespect or something like that. I forgot myself because... Yeah I got used with the things I do here yes.</p>	<p>Negative feeling after racist reaction when traveling abroad.</p> <p>Home sickness and culture shock.</p> <p>Reverse culture shock. Conservative society that limits women's freedom.</p>
<p>Ali</p> <p>And also you come here and you have that feeling that your family your friends, everyone you know are counting on you. You kind of feel some pressure. Sometimes you think about it in a positive way but most of the time it makes me feel that kind of pressure from deadlines to do this this this and this...</p>	
<p>Morad:</p> <p>The PhD life is very hard especially at the beginning... it's not only for me; it can be for everyone especially for overseas students. The different culture, system, and university can make very hard.</p>	<p>Experiencing a hard transition from home university to a UK university.</p>
<p>Nadia</p> <p>For example, buying meat, I need to eat only halal meat, so I need to travel more than 10 kilometres to get it. Another example is praying. I need to pray 5 times a day (uncomfortable) I find it very hard.</p> <p>Because before, as a Muslim myself (hesitating) I was stereotyping people without knowing them, I had an essentialist point of view. I was thinking that I can't make him or her as my friend because my culture is more preservative, they may be bad people. In Canterbury, we Algerians were living all together (50 people), even in the flat, I used to live with other three Algerian girls, so I didn't have the chance to talk to British. It was just inside the classroom or during workshops, I didn't have the chance to make friends with British or any other nationality. During the weekends, when I go home at night from the library, I see people drunk and dancing in the street, I was very shocked at the beginning. I was judging them without knowing them.</p>	<p>Examples about some things she finds challenging when living abroad.</p> <p>Self-awareness, culture shock based on ethnicity.</p> <p>Social isolation</p>
<p>Sara</p> <p>However in this country or at university, I feel frustrated and hesitated to introduce myself because I don't know those people, I don't know those lecturers. When I speak English I feel a bit frustrated and anxious.</p> <p>In my country, there are some families who see that the woman who travels outside her country is something forbidden.</p>	<p>Culture shock</p> <p>The limited freedom of women in home society.</p>

Positive feelings

<p>Ahlam</p> <p>When I came to the UK, I got in touch with academics, who made a difference. The first thing that they taught us is we don't use names (titles, or honorifics) like doctor, or professor to communicate with them, but we have to use their first name and that's it. That gives you the insight that there is no barrier between the teacher and the student, so you start seeing yourself like you can achieve what they achieved. They teach you that, if he achieved that place, you will be able to achieve it. They tech you to see yourself, and to appreciate yourself as a student to know our rights more, to know what you country can offer you and what you should offer back to your country. So, this is what I learned from academia.</p>	<p>Culture shock</p> <p>Narrow power gap between students and staff.</p>
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<p>Ali: During the process of selection, it was very tiring to come here to the UK. I think getting it, yes it made a huge impact on me. One of the things in terms of academic levels, it makes me feel that I really achieved something I dreamed of.</p> <p>Going back to Algeria, and getting your PhD from a foreign country, I think we... I got more chances to get a good job and a good life with that... Yeah.</p>	<p>Skills and abilities</p> <p>Future aspirations and plans.</p>
<p>Latifa: It was my dream to attend a concert to anybody (laughter) and Sami Yousef came to Glasgow last year and I like the kind of music he sings (soufi music) it is a type of music the expresses devotion to god, and it even enhance the ... physical and the spiritual aspects of the listener... yeah that's why I went and had a lot of fun with my friends. There are some friends who just went because it's a concert but after attending it was like fabulous yeah.</p> <p>It has been organized by the Muslim society at the UWS... Yeah, I went with my Algerian friends, and we decided to dress up Algerian traditional clothes all... Yeah. The party was for females, only for ladies, so e we were able to act freely and we took off our hijab, and we felt normal. Yes. The party was more religious, they were even playing religious music. But em me and my friends asked them if we can play Algerian music, so, since we played the Algerian music, the overall weather changed, and we started like dancing and teaching them to dance in Algerian way. And we had so so much fun in that party. And in that party I gained new friends yes, from other Arabic countries, and even Pakistan and so on.</p>	<p>New experience with friends.</p> <p>Religious music and culture</p> <p>Ethnicity and the representation the self.</p> <p>Positive feeling when interacting with others.</p>
<p>Morad: I put the Algerian flag around my neck all the day long. I want to say that I am still attached to my country, though I am abroad. That doesn't mean that you are abroad you can change everything or your identity can disappear</p>	<p>The national identity I emphasised by using the flag in the picture.</p>
<p>Nora: This is a new thing it was like at night with my friends. Sometimes we go outside to have fun and eat (laughter). This one was in an Italian restaurant, we were like discovering new recipes... when I was in Algeria, I've never done this, I mean to go out for discovering new food from other countries. This is a new thing for me, and I'm enjoying it. Going out at night is totally new, I'm not used to it in Algeria, but here it like something normal for them. Maybe it has to do with our culture or religion or about safety, it's not safe. I feel like I'm free to do whatever I want in here, it's not the same at all.</p>	<p>New experience, freedom, exploring other cultures.</p> <p>Food,</p> <p>Going out during the nighttime.</p>
<p>Stacy: This picture was more than four months ago, it was a kind of feast which people of the UK celebrate it. This is me with my friend from Algeria as well as other people. What's special in this picture is that it was taken at night, where I live, I would never be able to do that. But here (Scotland) is not the same. It was about 8 o'clock at night and I was so curious about what is going on there. I was thinking that it is safe and nothing would happen to me if I go outside even at night. At first, I felt a bit frustrated because I used to do so. At the same time I was comfortable because I wasn't alone since my friends came with me. During my experience abroad, I keep using the dialect and I keep cooking the traditional food whenever I have the chance.</p> <p>I felt that my English developed to a great instant in the sense that I can communicate much better that the way I used to be.</p>	<p>New experience (Halloween)</p> <p>Shared experience with friends is much easier to accept.</p> <p>Representing the ethnic culture through dialect and food.</p> <p>English Language development</p>